

A generalization of intrinsic geometry and its application to Hilbert's 6th problem

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Abstract The first main work of this paper is to generalize intrinsic geometry. (1) Riemannian manifold is generalized to geometrical manifold. (2) The expression of Erlangen program is improved, and the concept of intrinsic geometry is generalized, so that Riemannian intrinsic geometry which is based on the first fundamental form becomes a subgeometry of the generalized intrinsic geometry. The Riemannian geometry is thereby incorporated into the geometrical framework of improved Erlangen program. (3) The important concept of simple connection is discovered, which reflects more intrinsic properties of manifold than Levi-Civita connection.

The second main work of this paper is to apply the generalized intrinsic geometry to Hilbert's 6th problem at the most basic level. (1) It starts from an axiom and makes key principles, postulates and artificially introduced equations of fundamental physics all turned into theorems which automatically hold in intrinsic geometrical theory. (2) Intrinsic geometry makes gravitational field and gauge field unified essentially. Intrinsic geometry of external space describes gravitational field, and intrinsic geometry of internal space describes typical gauge field. They are unified into intrinsic geometry. (3) Intrinsic geometry makes gravitational theory and quantum mechanics have the same view of time and space and unified description of evolution.

Keywords Erlangen program · geometrical manifold · intrinsic geometry · simple connection · Riemannian geometry · reference-system · time metric · actual evolution

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Contents

0	Introduction	2
1	Improved expression of Erlangen program	6
2	Generalization of intrinsic geometry	8
2.1	Geometrical manifold	8
2.2	Slack-tights and metrics	9
2.3	Generalized intrinsic geometry	11
2.4	Kernal geometry	13
2.5	Riemannian geometry	13
2.6	Universal geometry	15
2.7	Simple connection	15

2.8	Summary of this section	18
3	Intrinsic geometrical solution for Hilbert's 6th problem	18
3.1	Axiom for Hilbert's 6th problem	18
3.2	Mathematical treatment of time and space	19
3.3	Mathematical treatment of evolution	19
3.3.1	Definition and coordinate form of evolution	19
3.3.2	Evolution lemma	21
3.3.3	Metric form of evolution	23
3.3.4	Mathematical treatment of actual evolution	24
3.3.5	Mathematical treatment of actual evolution of potential field	25
3.3.6	Mathematical treatment of actual evolution of general charge	26
3.3.7	Intrinsic geometrical treatment of conservation of energy-momentum	29
3.3.8	Two dual descriptions of gradient direction field	33
3.4	Intrinsic geometrical treatment of propagator and wave function	34
3.5	Summary of this section	36
4	Intrinsic geometrical treatment of inversion transformation	37
5	Intrinsic geometrical treatment of classical spacetime	38
5.1	Existence and uniqueness of submanifold with classical spacetime	38
5.2	Intrinsic geometrical treatment of gravitational field	40
5.3	Two coordinate representations of intrinsic geometrical property	42
5.4	Geometrical treatment of classical spacetime evolution	44
5.5	Intrinsic geometrical treatment of Legendre transformation and equation of motion	47
5.6	Intrinsic geometrical treatment of Dirac equation and gauge transformation	48
6	Several intrinsic geometrical properties in 5-dimensional case	52
7	Several intrinsic geometrical properties in 6-dimensional case	56
8	Several intrinsic geometrical properties in 8-dimensional case	58
9	Summary	66
	References	66

0 Introduction

(i) Intrinsic geometry.

In 1827, Friedrich Gauss created the theory of intrinsic geometry of surface in his article *Disquisitiones Generales Circa Superficies Curves*, and essentially unified the Euclidean geometry and various non-Euclidean geometries at that time. In 1854, Bernhard Riemann generalized Gauss's ideas of intrinsic geometry to high dimensions in his speech *Ueber Die Hypothesen, Welche Der Geometrie Zu Grunde Liegen*, and expressed the first fundamental form with metric tensor. In Riemannian geometry, all values of intrinsic geometrical properties are totally determined by metric tensor.

However, in this paper it is discovered that the traditional practice that characterizing intrinsic geometry with metric tensor is not necessarily able to cover all the intrinsic properties of manifold. It has been known for a long time that the coefficients of metric tensor surely remain unchanged when orthogonal transformations effect on semi-metric [14, 19]. Although there have been many studies on semi-metric, and some non-mathematical researches have shown advantages of semi-metric [13, 14, 53], however their mathematical meanings have not been studied sufficiently. Some articles treat semi-metric either as an alternative expression form of metric, or as an insignificant mathematical substitution [14]. And there is an article [11] which has noticed that semi-metric causes some indications beyond Riemannian geometry, but it argues that a well-done semi-metric theory should not cause such indications. We must see that the mathematical significance of semi-metric has not yet been fully revealed.

It is noticed that a traditional intrinsic geometrical property is an invariant under identical transformations of metric, and we can also speak of it as an invariant under orthogonal transformations of semi-metric. It indicates that two different properties under two different orthogonal transformations of semi-metric cannot be distinguished by the traditional intrinsic geometry. If

we take different orthogonal transformations of semi-metric at different points of a Riemannian manifold, the Riemannian manifold remains unchanged, and these orthogonal transformations just exactly constitute a local gauge transformation. That is to say, Riemannian geometry is still not exquisite enough. Therefore, there exists a kind of more extensive intrinsic geometry with Riemannian geometry as its subgeometry.

In order to understand the generalized concept of intrinsic geometry defined later more conveniently, the intuition of intrinsic geometry must be concisely explained here in a new way different from the perspective of metric of traditional intrinsic geometry.

Fig. 1 The intuition of intrinsic geometry of curve

First, consider the case of one-dimension, that is the intuition of intrinsic geometry of curve. As shown in Fig.1, select a curve L in the plane rectangular coordinate system. Project the coordinates of y axis onto L continuously and uniformly, and then onto x axis.

In this way, the original continuous and uniform coordinate distribution becomes a continuous but ununiform distribution via L as a medium, thus we obtain an interval S with some ununiform distribution shown in the right figure of Fig. 1. This is actually the intuition of intrinsic geometry of curve L . It can be said that curve S is curve L in intrinsic geometry.

Such an intuition of intrinsic geometry can be described strictly in the following way.

Let S be a one-dimensional manifold, which is homeomorphic to an Euclidean straight line. Take two coordinate charts (S, x) and (S, y) on S such that we have a coordinate relation $y = y(x)$.

As shown in the above figure, at every point of S , it shows a kind of intuition reflecting the degree of slackness and tightness of coordinate distribution of y axis in x axis. Such a degree of slackness and tightness can be strictly described by $\frac{dy}{dx}$. Then the one-dimensional manifold S given the degree of slackness and tightness $\frac{dy}{dx}$ is the curve L defined in way of intrinsic geometry.

The case of two-dimensional surface is similar. The intuition of intrinsic geometry of surface $z = e^{-(x^2+y^2)}$ in the left figure of Fig.2 can be shown by the degree of slackness and tightness of coordinate net (u^1, u^2) in coordinate system (x^1, x^2) at each point of the right figure of Fig.2. This degree of slackness and tightness can be strictly described by $\frac{\partial u^k}{\partial x^i}$ ($i, k = 1, 2$). It can be said that the degree of slackness and tightness $\frac{\partial u^k}{\partial x^i}$ of the right figure defines the surface of the left figure in way of intrinsic geometry. The coordinate net in this figure shows a special solution of

Fig. 2 The intuition of intrinsic geometry of surface

(u^1, u^2) such that

$$\begin{cases} u^1(x^1, x^2) = \frac{x^1}{\sqrt{(x^1)^2 + (x^2)^2}} \int_0^{\sqrt{(x^1)^2 + (x^2)^2}} \sqrt{1 + 4\rho^2 e^{-2\rho^2}} d\rho, \\ u^2(x^1, x^2) = \frac{x^2}{\sqrt{(x^1)^2 + (x^2)^2}} \int_0^{\sqrt{(x^1)^2 + (x^2)^2}} \sqrt{1 + 4\rho^2 e^{-2\rho^2}} d\rho. \end{cases}$$

These above are intuitive descriptions of two simple cases about one and two dimensions, emphasizing the central role of the degree of slackness and tightness $\frac{\partial u^k}{\partial x^i}$ determined by two coordinate systems in reflecting the intuition of intrinsic geometry. In this way, the general concept of intrinsic geometry will be defined strictly in this paper.

Such a generalized intrinsic geometry is worth studying. It is discovered in this paper, that the geometrical properties in such a geometry can just exactly reflect the physical properties of elementary particles in the Standard Model, which cannot be described by the traditional intrinsic geometry. With such a generalization, it is not only gravitational field but also gauge field, that can be described by intrinsic geometry, and further more the whole fundamental physics will be unified in the intrinsic geometry. Therefore, it will naturally give a solution for Hilbert's 6th problem.

(ii) Hilbert's 6th problem.

The purpose of Hilbert's 6th problem is to axiomatize the physics. Theoretical physics at the most basic level is an important aspect about it. The unity of the physical world has always been a belief held by many people. The history of theoretical physics is a process that the unity expands step by step. In this paper, it is essentially regarded as a process that the concept of geometry expands step by step.

(1) From Newtonian mechanics to special relativity [16], and then to general relativity [17, 18], it is a process that flat Riemannian geometry expands to general Riemannian geometry.

(2) Gauge field theory actually expresses a kind of geometry that cannot be described by Riemannian geometry. It is usually described by abstract connections on abstract fibre bundles, however, that is not concrete enough.

From the perspective of concrete constructivity, the generalization of intrinsic geometry in this paper makes the concept of geometry expand further more, thereby Riemannian geometry and gauge field geometry can be uniformly described by the generalized intrinsic geometry.

Besides the intrinsic geometry, the solution at the most basic level for Hilbert's 6th problem also depends on a constructivity method. There are two approaches to develop mathematical theory, one is the approach of concrete constructivity based on set theory, the other is the approach of abstract structure based on category theory. Although the effectivenesses of these two research approaches are the same, without either of them, the cognition to this mathematical intuition is incomplete.

For example, consider the concept of real number. From the approach of abstract structure, some conventions as the connotation of abstract structure are combined to form axiomatized definition of real number, i.e. a real number is an abstract element in the complete archimedean ordered field. From the approach of concrete constructivity, natural numbers are constructed from empty set, then integers and rational numbers are constructed, and then irrational numbers are constructed via Dedekind cut to form the real number set. Such two concepts of real number defined in two approaches reflect the same mathematical intuition. And such two theories of real number provide a complete cognition for the intuition of real number.

In the above sense, fundamental physical theories in history are too abstract and lack of concrete mathematical constructions. For examples:

(1) In electrodynamics, the relationship between mechanics and electromagnetics can be established just only by Lorentz force equation $\mathbf{F} = q(\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B})$. However, various variables in the formula are all abstract vectors and scalar, which are lack of concrete mathematical constructions. For example, \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} can only be distinguished ontologically, but as two abstract vectors there is no difference of mathematical connotation between them. As a result, the Lorentz force equation can just only be artificially introduced and regarded as a principle and cannot become a theorem automatically.

(2) After the establishment of quantum mechanics [3–5, 8, 9, 58–63], the quantum field theory established. The suggestion of Yang-Mills theory [73] eventually led to Glashow-Weinberg-Salam's unified theory of weak electricity [20, 29, 38, 41–43, 45, 57, 66], quantum chromodynamics [2, 6, 21, 24, 25, 27, 31–33, 56, 65] and various great unified theories [10, 23, 26, 49–51]. Not long ago, Yue-Liang Wu brought gravitational field into the framework of QFT in inertial system [68–72].

However, such fields are still abstractly defined functions and lack of concrete mathematical constructions. Both Hamiltonian function and Lagrangian function are abstract objects, because field functions composing them are abstract. On one hand, physics describes gauge field with abstract concept of connection on a fibre bundle, but without giving concrete mathematical constructions to the connections. On the other hand, the spinor field, which is composed of several complex-valued functions, is sometimes used to refer to a charged lepton field, and sometimes a neutrino field. It is not clear in physics that how to distinguish field function of charged lepton and field function of neutrino by mathematical constructions.

(3) Early Kaluza-Klein theory [44, 47, 48] and later string theory as well as superstring theory [1, 12, 28, 30, 34–37, 39, 40, 55, 64, 67] attempted to provide unified explanations of this problem in high dimensional space. But for Hilbert's 6th problem, they still cannot be regarded successful.

The details of the above theories will not be discussed here. What should be emphasized is that we will supply concrete mathematical constructions for the above various physical concepts from the perspective of intrinsic geometry, so that theoretical physics can be axiomatized at the most basic level.

It will start from a unique basic axiom, and strictly deduce the framework of physics, and turn principles, postulates, and artificially introduced equations into theorems, so as to give a kind of effective solution for Hilbert's 6th problem at the most basic level.

(iii) General definition of geometry.

In order to generalize intrinsic geometry, we have to make a few improvements to the expression form of Erlangen program. It is mainly based on the consideration of the following two issues.

(1) In history, there appeared two different approaches to unify Euclidean geometry and non-Euclidean geometries. One is from Gauss and Riemann, that is to say, Gauss-Bonnet theorem distinguishes geometries by angle sums of triangles. The other is the Erlangen program [46] proposed by Felix Klein in 1872. It distinguishes geometries by transformation groups.

However, Riemannian geometry was regarded as one that cannot be incorporated into the framework of Erlangen's program, so these two approaches still fail to associate clearly.

(2) Based on the idea of Erlangen program, starting from the second half of the 20th century, theoretical physics began to emphasize the notion of *symmetry* and research it with the concept of group extensively. It is right, but easy to cause a kind of misunderstanding, that is, symmetry and group are regarded as equivalent things.

In fact, the essential idea of symmetry is the invariance under transformations, and the essential idea of group is the relationship between transformations. The former is a geometrical property, and the latter is an algebraic property. Therefore, symmetry and group should not be confused.

In order to deal with the above two issues and to generalize intrinsic geometry, the expression form of Erlangen program will be improved in this paper. The main idea of this improvement has been referred to in literatures [15, 52], but they have not expressed this idea as a strict definition of general concept of geometry in an explicit form. Such a definition will be given below.

1 Improved expression of Erlangen program

Definition 1.1. Let C be a set and \sim a relation of equivalence. The classification C/\sim is called a **geometry** on C with respect to \sim . Let $t : C \rightarrow C$ be a transformation. If $\forall [c] \in C/\sim, \forall c \in [c]$ such that $t(c) \in [c]$, we say t is an **equivalent transformation** with respect to \sim . The totality T of all equivalent transformations on C with respect to \sim is called an **equivalent transformation set** on C with respect to \sim . Evidently, \sim and T are mutually determined, therefore, C/\sim can also be denoted by C/T .

$\forall [c] \in C/T$ is called a **geometrical object**. $\forall a \in [c]$ is called a **geometrical instance** of $[c]$. Denote $S \triangleq \bigcup_{c \in C} c$, each element in S is called a **point**, each subset of S is called a **geometrical figure**, and (S, T) is called a kind of **geometrical theory**.

Let H be a set, and let a map $h : C \rightarrow H$ satisfy $\forall c_1, c_2 \in C, c_1 \sim c_2 \Leftrightarrow h(c_1) = h(c_2)$. Then h induces a map $\tilde{h} : C/\sim \rightarrow H, [c] \mapsto h(c)$. Each of h and \tilde{h} is called a **geometrical property** on C . The image of h and \tilde{h} in H is called the **value** of geometrical property.

Suppose there are two relations of equivalence \sim_a and \sim_b on C . If $\sim_a \subset \sim_b$, we say geometry C/\sim_a is **larger** than C/\sim_b , and C/\sim_b is **smaller** than C/\sim_a , we also say C/\sim_b is a **subgeometry** of C/\sim_a .

Remark 1.1. The above definition is equivalent to the traditional expression of Erlangen program. It is remarkable that it characterizes geometry with a relation of equivalence, but not a group. Why a new definition should be adopted? Because it is very inconvenient to describe geometry in the traditional form of Erlangen program in the case where a group is difficult to expressed in an explicit form due to its complicated form or uncertain structure. But if we find a certain condition to define a relation of equivalence, according to the above new definition we are able to define our required geometry without specifying group structure. Thereby it will be convenient for our study, such as what Discussion 6.1 says. In addition, Definition 2.3.2 , Definition 2.4.2 , Definition 2.5.2 and section 2.6 are also treated in such a way.

In the past, Erlangen program was used to deal with groups with simple structure. The corresponding geometry was confined to either local of the manifold or homogeneous manifold such as constant curvature manifold. The Riemannian geometry was not incorporated into the framework of Erlangen program in traditional way. By contrast, based on the expression form of this paper, the definition of geometry can completely incorporate Riemannian geometry into the framework of improved Erlangen program, see Discussion 2.6.2 .

To say the least, if the group structure has to be emphasized, the following additional definition is needed. The elements in equivalent transformation set T naturally imply a group structure with respect to composite operation of maps. The group T is called the **transformation group of geometry** C/T , and C/T is called the **geometry of group** T . Therefore, the group structure exists on the equivalent transformation set naturally, and it is not necessary to make explicit requirements in the definition of geometry as the traditional form of Erlangen program. Suppose transformation group T_1 acting on S_1 and transformation group T_2 acting on S_2 are isomorphic. (S_1, T_1) and (S_2, T_2) are called **the same kind of geometrical theory**. If T_1 is a proper subgroup of T_2 , we say T_1 is **smaller** than T_2 , and T_2 **larger** than T_1 . Evidently, the smaller the group, the larger the geometry; conversely, the larger the group, the smaller the geometry.

Definition 1.2. On any set C , there must be a special geometry, which has only one equivalence class, that is C itself. This geometry is called a **universal geometry**. The set C is the only geometrical object in universal geometry, and it is called a **universal geometrical object**. Each geometrical property in universal geometry is called a **universal geometrical property**, and also called a **geometrical invariant** on C . Each universal geometrical property with its unique value is called a **geometrical identity** on C .

2 Generalization of intrinsic geometry

2.1 Geometrical manifold

Definition 2.1.1. Let M be a \mathfrak{D} -dimensional connected smooth real manifold. $\forall p \in M$, take a coordinate chart (U_p, φ_{U_p}) on a neighborhood U_p of p . They constitute a coordinate covering $\{(U_p, \varphi_{U_p})\}_{p \in M}$, which is called a **point-by-point covering**. φ_{U_p} is called a **coordinate frame** on neighborhood U_p of p . For the sake of simplicity, below U_p is denoted by U , and φ_{U_p} is denoted by φ_U .

For any two coordinate frames φ_U and ψ_U on neighborhood U of point p , if $f_p \triangleq \varphi_U \circ \psi_U^{-1} : \psi_U(U) \rightarrow \varphi_U(U)$ is a smooth homeomorphism, f_p is called a **(local) reference-system** on neighborhood U of point p , where ψ_U is the **basis coordinate frame** of f_p , and φ_U is the **performance coordinate frame** of f_p .

For any local reference-systems f_p and g_p at p , if the coordinate frames of f_p and the coordinate frames of g_p are C^∞ -compatible, we say f_p and g_p are C^∞ -**compatible**. The totality of the local reference-systems that are mutually C^∞ -compatible is called a **(local) reference-system space**, denoted by $REF_p(U)$ or REF_p .

The totality of all the local reference-systems with ψ_U as the basis coordinate frame is denoted by $REF_p(U, \psi_U)$.

The totality of all the local reference-systems with φ_U as the performance coordinate frame is denoted by $REF_p(\varphi_U, U)$.

Definition 2.1.2. Denote $REF \triangleq \bigcup_{p \in M} REF_p$, where $\forall p, q \in M$ all the elements in REF_p and REF_q are C^∞ -compatible.

If the map $f : M \rightarrow REF$, $p \mapsto f(p) \in REF_p$ satisfies that the slack-tights B_M^A and C_A^M in definition 2.2.2 are all smooth real functions on M , f is called a **reference-system** on M . The totality of all reference-systems which are mutually C^∞ -compatible on M is denoted by REF_M .

A differential manifold M with a reference-system f is called a **geometrical manifold** given shape by f , and denoted by (M, f) .

Definition 2.1.3. $\forall p \in M$, $\forall \rho_U \circ \psi_U^{-1} \in REF_p(U)$ induces two **(local) reference-system transformations**

$$\begin{cases} L_{\rho_U \circ \psi_U^{-1}} : REF_p(\psi_U, U) \rightarrow REF_p(\rho_U, U), & \psi_U \circ \varphi_U^{-1} \mapsto (\rho_U \circ \psi_U^{-1}) \circ (\psi_U \circ \varphi_U^{-1}) = \rho_U \circ \varphi_U^{-1}, \\ R_{\rho_U \circ \psi_U^{-1}} : REF_p(U, \rho_U) \rightarrow REF_p(U, \psi_U), & \varphi_U \circ \rho_U^{-1} \mapsto (\varphi_U \circ \rho_U^{-1}) \circ (\rho_U \circ \psi_U^{-1}) = \varphi_U \circ \psi_U^{-1}. \end{cases}$$

$\forall f \in REF_M$, $\forall p \in M$, suppose $L_{f(p)}$ and $R_{f(p)}$ are induced by $f(p)$. The maps $L_f : p \mapsto L_{f(p)} \triangleq L_{f(p)}$ and $R_f : p \mapsto R_{f(p)} \triangleq R_{f(p)}$ are called **reference-system transformations** on manifold M .

Remark 2.1.1. Suppose there is a reference-system f on manifold M . Construct reference-system e in the following way: $\forall p \in M$, on neighborhood U of point p , take the basis coordinate frame of $f(p)$ as the basis coordinate frame of $e(p)$, and take the same basis coordinate frame

of $f(p)$ as the performance coordinate frame of $e(p)$. Thus, reference-system transformation L_f sends e to f just exactly.

2.2 Slack-tights and metrics

Definition 2.2.1. For convenience, some index symbols have to be specified. In the absence of a special declaration, the indices used below are valued in the following range:

- (1) for basis coordinate frame (U, ξ) , indices $A, B, C, D, E = 1, 2, \dots, \mathfrak{D}$, such as ξ^A ;
- (2) for performance coordinate frame (U, x) , indices $M, N, P, Q, R = 1, 2, \dots, \mathfrak{D}$, such as x^M .

Definition 2.2.2. Let (M, f) be a geometrical manifold. $\forall p \in M$, on a neighborhood U_p of point p , let the coordinate representation of local reference-system $f(p)$ be $\xi^A = \xi^A(x^M)$, $x^M = x^M(\xi^A)$. Their derivative functions

$$\begin{cases} b_M^A : U_p \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, & q \mapsto b_M^A(q) \triangleq \frac{\partial \xi^A}{\partial x^M}(q), \\ c_A^M : U_p \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, & q \mapsto c_A^M(q) \triangleq \frac{\partial x^M}{\partial \xi^A}(q), \end{cases}$$

on U_p are called the **degrees of slackness and tightness** of $f(p)$, or **slack-tights** for short. If it is needed to emphasize $f(p)$ explicitly, b_M^A and c_A^M can be denoted by $(b_{f(p)})_M^A$ and $(c_{f(p)})_A^M$.

Define two kinds of smooth real functions on manifold M :

$$\begin{cases} B_M^A : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, & p \mapsto B_M^A(p) \triangleq (b_{f(p)})_M^A(p) \\ C_A^M : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, & p \mapsto C_A^M(p) \triangleq (c_{f(p)})_A^M(p) \end{cases},$$

then B_M^A and C_A^M are called the **slack-tights** of reference-system f on manifold M .

Discussion 2.2.1. Corresponding to the two coordinate frames of $f(p)$, the tangent space T_p at point p has two sets of natural bases $\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^A} \Big|_p, \frac{\partial}{\partial x^M} \Big|_p \in T_p$, and the cotangent space T_p^* also has two sets of natural bases $d\xi^A \Big|_p, dx^M \Big|_p \in T_p^*$. Thus, on U_p we have

$$(b_{f(p)})_M^A = \left\langle \frac{\partial}{\partial x^M} \Big|_p, d\xi^A \Big|_p \right\rangle, \quad (c_{f(p)})_A^M = \left\langle \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^A} \Big|_p, dx^M \Big|_p \right\rangle.$$

Therefore, $\forall p \in M$ we have

$$B_M^A(p) = \left\langle \frac{\partial}{\partial x^M} \Big|_p, d\xi^A \Big|_p \right\rangle(p), \quad C_A^M(p) = \left\langle \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^A} \Big|_p, dx^M \Big|_p \right\rangle(p).$$

which can concisely be denoted by

$$B_M^A = \left\langle \frac{\partial}{\partial x^M}, d\xi^A \right\rangle, \quad C_A^M = \left\langle \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^A}, dx^M \right\rangle.$$

Definition 2.2.3. Denote

$$\varepsilon_{MN} = \varepsilon^{MN} = \varepsilon_N^M \triangleq \begin{cases} 1, & M = N \\ 0, & M \neq N \end{cases}, \quad \delta_{AB} = \delta^{AB} = \delta_B^A \triangleq \begin{cases} 1, & A = B \\ 0, & A \neq B \end{cases}.$$

Let (M, f) be a geometrical manifold. $\forall p \in M$, let U be a neighborhood of point p .

(1) The coordinate frames (U, ξ^A) and (U, x^M) of $f(p)$ respectively inherit metric tensor fields

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{g} \triangleq \delta_{AB} d\xi^A \otimes d\xi^B = g_{MN} dx^M \otimes dx^N \\ \mathbf{h} \triangleq \varepsilon_{MN} dx^M \otimes dx^N = h_{AB} d\xi^A \otimes d\xi^B \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} g_{MN} = \delta_{AB} b_M^A b_N^B \\ h_{AB} = \varepsilon_{MN} c_A^M c_B^N \end{cases}.$$

If it is needed to emphasize $f(p)$ explicitly, g and h can be expressed as $g_{f(p)}$ and $h_{f(p)}$, then g_{MN} and h_{AB} can be expressed as $(g_{f(p)})_{MN}$ and $(h_{f(p)})_{AB}$.

(2) On manifold M , define smooth real functions

$$\begin{cases} G_{MN} : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, p \mapsto G_{MN}(p) \triangleq (g_{f(p)})_{MN}(p) \\ H_{AB} : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, p \mapsto H_{AB}(p) \triangleq (h_{f(p)})_{AB}(p) \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} \Delta_{AB} : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, p \mapsto \Delta_{AB}(p) \triangleq \delta_{AB} \\ E_{MN} : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, p \mapsto E_{MN}(p) \triangleq \varepsilon_{MN} \end{cases}.$$

Thus on the entire manifold M , two metric tensors \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{H} are constructed, the local restrictions of which can be expressed as

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{G} = \Delta_{AB} d\xi^A \otimes d\xi^B = G_{MN} dx^M \otimes dx^N \\ \mathbf{H} = E_{MN} dx^M \otimes dx^N = H_{AB} d\xi^A \otimes d\xi^B \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} G_{MN} = \Delta_{AB} B_M^A B_N^B \\ H_{AB} = E_{MN} C_A^M C_B^N \end{cases}.$$

Definition 2.2.4. Denote $d\xi_A \triangleq h_{AB} d\xi^B$, $dx_M \triangleq g_{MN} dx^N$, which induce $\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_A}$ and $\frac{\partial}{\partial x_M}$ in tangent space, such that $\langle \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_B}, d\xi_A \rangle = \delta_A^B$ and $\langle \frac{\partial}{\partial x_N}, dx_M \rangle = \varepsilon_M^N$. Denote

$$\begin{cases} c^{MA} \triangleq \frac{\partial x^M}{\partial \xi_A} \\ b^{AM} \triangleq \frac{\partial \xi^A}{\partial x_M} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} c_{AM} \triangleq \frac{\partial x_M}{\partial \xi^A} \\ b_{MA} \triangleq \frac{\partial \xi_A}{\partial x^M} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} \bar{b}_A^M \triangleq \frac{\partial \xi_A}{\partial x^M} \\ \bar{c}_M^A \triangleq \frac{\partial x^M}{\partial \xi_A} \end{cases}.$$

Define the following tensors:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{g} \triangleq \delta_{AB} d\xi^A \otimes d\xi^B = g_{MN} dx^M \otimes dx^N = g^{MN} dx_M \otimes dx_N \\ \mathbf{h} \triangleq \varepsilon_{MN} dx^M \otimes dx^N = h_{AB} d\xi^A \otimes d\xi^B = h^{AB} d\xi_A \otimes d\xi_B \end{cases},$$

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{x} \triangleq \delta^{AB} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^A} \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^B} = x^{MN} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^M} \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial x^N} = x_{MN} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_M} \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial x_N} \\ \mathbf{y} \triangleq \varepsilon^{MN} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^M} \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial x^N} = y^{AB} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^A} \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^B} = y_{AB} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_A} \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_B} \end{cases},$$

where

$$\begin{cases} g_{MN} = \delta_{AB} b_M^A b_N^B \\ g^{MN} = \delta_{AB} b^{AM} b^{BN} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} h_{AB} = \varepsilon_{MN} c_A^M c_B^N \\ h^{AB} = \varepsilon_{MN} c^{MA} c^{NB} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} x_{MN} = \delta^{AB} c_{AM} c_{BN} \\ x^{MN} = \delta^{AB} c_A^M c_B^N \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} y_{AB} = \varepsilon^{MN} b_{MA} b_{NB} \\ y^{AB} = \varepsilon^{MN} b_M^A b_N^B \end{cases}.$$

Proposition 2.2.1. $g_{MN} = x_{MN}$, $g^{MN} = x^{MN}$, $h_{AB} = y_{AB}$, $h^{AB} = y^{AB}$.

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} (1) g^{MP} b_M^C b_P^D &= \delta^{CD} \Rightarrow g^{MN} b_M^C b_N^D c_C^P c_D^Q = \delta^{CD} c_C^P c_D^Q \Rightarrow g^{PQ} = x^{PQ}. \\ x_{MN} &\triangleq \delta^{AB} c_{AM} c_{BN} \Rightarrow g^{PM} x_{MN} g^{NQ} = g^{PM} \delta^{AB} c_{AM} c_{BN} g^{NQ} = \delta^{AB} (c_{AM} g^{PM}) (c_{BN} g^{NQ}) = \\ \delta^{AB} c_A^P c_B^Q &= g^{PQ} \Rightarrow g^{PM} x_{MN} = \varepsilon_N^P \Rightarrow x_{MN} = g_{MN}. \\ (2) h^{AB} c_A^P c_B^Q &= \varepsilon^{PQ} \Rightarrow h^{AB} c_A^P c_B^Q b_P^C b_Q^D = \varepsilon^{PQ} b_P^C b_Q^D \Rightarrow h^{CD} = y^{CD}. \\ y_{AB} &\triangleq \varepsilon^{MN} b_{MA} b_{NB} \Rightarrow h^{CA} y_{AB} h^{BD} = h^{CA} \varepsilon^{MN} b_{MA} b_{NB} h^{BD} = \varepsilon^{MN} (b_{MA} h^{CA}) (b_{NB} h^{BD}) = \\ \varepsilon^{MN} b_M^C b_N^D &= h^{CD} \Rightarrow h^{CA} y_{AB} = \delta_B^C \Rightarrow y_{AB} = h_{AB}. \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

2.3 Generalized intrinsic geometry

Definition 2.3.1. Intrinsic geometry of reference-system.

(1) Intrinsic geometry of local reference-system.

$\forall f_p, g_p \in REF_p(U)$, let slack-tights of f_p and g_p be $(b_f)_M^A$ and $(b_g)_M^A$, respectively.

Define a relation of equivalence \cong , such that $f_p \cong g_p$ if and only if $\forall q \in U$, $(b_f)_M^A(q) = (b_g)_M^A(q)$. Thus, $REF_p(U)/\cong$ is called the **intrinsic geometry** on $REF_p(U)$, where the geometrical object $[f_p]$ is called the **core** of f_p .

(2) Intrinsic geometry of reference-system on manifold.

$\forall f, g \in REF_M$, let slack-tights of f and g be $(B_f)_M^A$ and $(B_g)_M^A$, respectively.

Define a relation of equivalence \equiv , such that $f \equiv g$ if and only if $\forall p \in M$, $f(p) \cong g(p)$. Thus, the geometry REF_M/\equiv is called the **strict intrinsic geometry** on REF_M .

Define a relation of equivalence \cong , such that $f \cong g$ if and only if $\forall p \in M$, $(B_f)_M^A(p) = (B_g)_M^A(p)$. Thus, the geometry REF_M/\cong is called the **intrinsic geometry** on REF_M , where the geometrical object $[f]$ is called the **core** of f . For convenience, $[f] \triangleq [p \mapsto f(p)]$ will also be expressed as $[f] : p \mapsto [f(p)]$.

Definition 2.3.2. Intrinsic geometry on geometrical manifold.

The totality of all the geometrical manifolds on M is denoted by $\mathcal{M}(M)$. Define a relation of equivalence \cong of geometrical manifolds, such that $(M, f) \cong (M, g)$ if and only if $f \cong g$. The geometry $\mathcal{C}(M) \triangleq \mathcal{M}(M)/\cong$ is called the **intrinsic geometry** on geometrical manifolds, where geometrical object $(M, [f])$ is called an **intrinsic geometrical manifold** given shape by $[f]$.

According to Definition 1.1, the value of each intrinsic geometrical property is completely depends on the core of reference-system, and thereby depends on the slack-tights B_M^A or C_A^M .

Definition 2.3.3. Intrinsic transformation.

(1) Local intrinsic transformation. $[f_p]$ induces equivalence classes $L_{[f_p]} : [h_p] \mapsto [f_p] \circ [h_p]$ and $R_{[f_p]} : [k_p] \mapsto [k_p] \circ [f_p]$ of $L_{f_p} : h_p \mapsto f_p \circ h_p$ and $R_{f_p} : k_p \mapsto k_p \circ f_p$. Then we say $L_{[f_p]}$ and $R_{[f_p]}$ are **local intrinsic transformations**.

(2) Intrinsic transformation on manifold. $[f]$ induces equivalence classes $L_{[f]} : [h] \mapsto [f] \circ [h]$ and $R_{[f]} : [k] \mapsto [k] \circ [f]$ of $L_f : h \mapsto f \circ h$ and $R_f : k \mapsto k \circ f$. Then we say $L_{[f]}$ and $R_{[f]}$ are **intrinsic transformations** of geometrical manifolds, or **general gauge transformations**, see Proposition 5.6.2 for reasons.

Discussion 2.3.1. Intrinsic transformation group.

(1) Locally, on the neighborhood of any point p on manifold M , the slack-tights b_M^A or c_A^M of a reference-system constitute a \mathfrak{D} -order invertible square matrix. The intrinsic geometry $REF_p(U)/\cong$ is isomorphic to general linear group $GL(\mathfrak{D}, \mathbb{R})$.

(2) On manifold M , an intrinsic transformation sends an intrinsic geometrical manifold to another intrinsic geometrical manifold. On one hand, on the premise of no requirement of smoothness for slack-tights, the intrinsic geometry $GL(M) \triangleq REF_M/\cong$ is isomorphic to general linear group $GL_M \triangleq \bigotimes_{p \in M} GL(\mathfrak{D}, \mathbb{R})_p$, where \bigotimes represents external direct product. On the other

hand, if we require that the slack-tights be smooth as it is stated in Definition 2.1.2 , $GL(M)$ is a subgroup of GL_M , and the restriction of $GL(M)$ at any point of M is isomorphic to $GL(\mathfrak{D}, \mathbb{R})$.

Suppose $S(M)$ is a subgroup of GL_M . The group structure of $S(M)$ may be complicated. The description of $S(M)$ would be cumbersome. It is because transformation groups at various points are different from each other in general, and also there are usually constraints of smoothness between adjacent points. According to the original form of Erlangen program, geometry is dependent on group, that is to say, if group structure does not described clearly, geometry could not be established. This is an important reason why in history Riemannian geometry was not incorporated into the framework of Erlangen program.

Now we have the concept of geometry of section 1 and the concept of reference-system of Definition 2.1.2 , then it is easy to unify the points of view of Riemannian geometry and Erlangen program. On one hand, with the concept of reference-system, it is possible to precisely describe transformation group $S(M)$, for example we have Definition 2.3.4 . On the other hand, more conveniently, it is even not necessary to specify detail informations of structure of transformation group $S(M)$, but we can take constraints for slack-tights, and thereby construct a relation of equivalence about reference-systems, then we are able to study geometry by the concepts of section 1 , just like what we do in Definition 2.3.2 , Definition 2.4.2 , Definition 2.5.2 and section 2.6 . More importantly, it will be seen later that it is not always convenient for us to immediately solve the elements of the transformation group corresponding to the symmetry conditions like those in Proposition 6.2 and Definition 8.3 , however, this does not prevent us from expounding its geometry. This is exactly what the concept of geometry of section 1 is expected to achieve.

Definition 2.3.4. The general linear group $GL(M)$ is called **intrinsic transformation group**, or **general gauge transformation group**.

Specially, for the case where the transformation groups at different points of manifold are isomorphic to each other, the general linear group $GL(\mathfrak{D}, \mathbb{R})$ is called **homogeneous intrinsic transformation group**. Furthermore:

Let S be a subgroup of $GL(\mathfrak{D}, \mathbb{R})$. If f satisfies the following two conditions: (1) $\forall p \in M, [f(p)] \in S$; (2) for any subgroup T of $S, \exists q \in M, [f(q)] \notin T$; then we say objects determined by f , such as $f, (M, [f]), L_{[f]}, R_{[f]}$, etc., are **generated by group S** . Thus, $S(M) \triangleq \{[f]|f \text{ is generated by group } S\}$ is evidently a subgroup of $GL(M)$.

In addition, as the equivalent transformation set, the totality of all intrinsic transformations generated by group S can be used to define a relation of equivalence \sim_S , so we can define a geometry $\mathcal{M}(M)/\sim_S$, which is called the **geometry of group $S(M)$** , also denoted by $\mathcal{M}(M)/S(M)$.

Let us define three important subgeometries of intrinsic geometry in the following three sections. They are kernal geometry, Riemannian geometry and universal geometry.

2.4 Kernal geometry

Definition 2.4.1. Let k be a reference-system on manifold M , and its slack-tights B_M^A constants. We say $L_{[k]}$ and $R_{[k]}$ induced by k are **flat transformations** of reference-systems, or **global gauge transformations**. Specially, if $\det[B_M^A] = 1$, we say $L_{[k]}$ and $R_{[k]}$ are **unimodular flat transformations** of reference-systems.

Definition 2.4.2. Let there be intrinsic geometrical manifolds $(M, [f])$ and $(M, [g])$. Define a relation of equivalence \simeq , such that $[f] \simeq [g]$ and $(M, [f]) \simeq (M, [g])$ if and only if there exists a flat transformation $F_{[k]}$ such that $F_{[k]}([f]) = [g]$, where $F_{[k]}$ represents $L_{[k]}$ or $R_{[k]}$.

The corresponding equivalence classes are denoted by $|f|$ and $(M, |f|)$ respectively, and $|f|$ is called the **kernal** of f . The geometry $\mathcal{C}(M)/\simeq$ is called the **kernal geometry** on geometrical manifolds, where the geometrical object $(M, |f|)$ is called a **kernal geometrical manifold**. Specially, if $F_{[k]}$ is a unimodular flat transformation, $\mathcal{C}(M)/\simeq$ is called a **regular kernal geometry**.

Remark 2.4.1. Kernal geometry is a subgeometry of the intrinsic geometry of Definition 2.3.2. It can be understood intuitively as follows. Consider Fig.1 of introduction section. Fix axis and scale, and rotate the entire curve L by an angle. The intrinsic geometrical curve S' now is different from the previous intrinsic geometrical curve S , but the major bending characteristics remain unchanged under the rotation. These bending characteristics are described by various regular kernal geometrical properties of $[S]$.

2.5 Riemannian geometry

Definition 2.5.1. Let k be a reference-system on manifold, and its slack-tights B_M^A satisfy $\Delta_{AB} B_M^A B_N^B = E_{MN}$. Then $L_{[k]}$ and $R_{[k]}$ induced by k are called **orthogonal transformations** of reference-systems.

Definition 2.5.2. Let there be intrinsic geometrical manifolds $(M, [f])$ and $(M, [g])$, and their slack-tights $(B_f)_M^A$ and $(B_g)_M^A$.

Define a relation of equivalence \simeq_O , such that $[f] \simeq_O [g]$ and $(M, [f]) \simeq_O (M, [g])$ if and only if there exists an orthogonal transformation $F_{[k]}$ such that $F_{[k]}([f]) = [g]$, where $F_{[k]}$ represents $L_{[k]}$ or $R_{[k]}$. The equivalence classes are denoted by $[f]_O$ and $(M, [f]_O)$ respectively. We say the geometry $\mathcal{C}(M)/\simeq_O$ is **Riemannian geometry**, and a geometrical object $(M, [f]_O)$ is a **Riemannian manifold**.

Proposition 2.5.1. $[f] \simeq_O [g]$ if and only if $(G_f)_{MN} = (G_g)_{MN}$.

Proof. We need to consider the cases of $F_{[k]} = R_{[k]}$ and $F_{[k]} = L_{[k]}$, respectively.

(1) Suppose $R_{[k]}$ is a transformation induced by reference-system k , such that $R_{[k]}([f]) = [g]$. Let the slack-tights of $[f]$ be $(B_f)_M^A$ and $(C_f)_A^M$, and the slack-tights of $[k]$ $(B_k)_A^{A'}$ and $(C_k)_{A'}^A$. Then the slack-tights of $[g]$ are $(B_g)_{M'}^{A'} = (B_k)_A^{A'} (B_f)_M^A$ and $(C_g)_{A'}^M = (C_k)_{A'}^A (C_f)_A^M$.

According to Definition 2.2.3 , the metric tensor of $[f]$ is $(G_f)_{MN} = \Delta_{AB}(B_f)_M^A(B_f)_N^B$, thereby the metric tensor of $[g]$ is $(G_g)_{MN} = \Delta_{A'B'}(B_g)_M^{A'}(B_g)_N^{B'} = \Delta_{A'B'} \left((B_k)_A^{A'}(B_f)_M^A \right) \left((B_k)_B^{B'}(B_f)_N^B \right) = \left(\Delta_{A'B'}(B_k)_A^{A'}(B_k)_B^{B'} \right) (B_f)_M^A(B_f)_N^B$. Hence, $(G_f)_{MN} = (G_g)_{MN}$ if and only if $\Delta_{A'B'}(B_k)_A^{A'}(B_k)_B^{B'} = \Delta_{AB}$, i.e. $R_{[k]}$ is orthogonal.

(2) Suppose $L_{[k]}$ is a transformation induced by reference-system k , such that $L_{[k]}([f]) = [g]$. Let the slack-tights of $[f]$ be $(B_f)_M^A$ and $(C_f)_A^M$, and the slack-tights of $[k]$ $(B_k)_{M'}^M$ and $(C_k)_{M'}^M$. Then the slack-tights of $[g]$ are $(B_g)_{M'}^A = (B_k)_{M'}^M(B_f)_M^A$ and $(C_g)_A^{M'} = (C_k)_M^{M'}(C_f)_A^M$.

According to Definition 2.2.4 , we consider tensors $(H_f)^{AB}$ and $(H_g)^{AB}$. $(H_f)^{AB} = (Y_f)^{AB} = E^{MN}(B_f)_M^A(B_f)_N^B$, $(H_g)^{AB} = E^{M'N'}(B_g)_{M'}^A(B_g)_{N'}^B = E^{M'N'} \left((B_k)_{M'}^M(B_f)_M^A \right) \left((B_k)_{N'}^N(B_f)_N^B \right) = \left(E^{M'N'}(B_k)_{M'}^M(B_k)_{N'}^N \right) (B_f)_M^A(B_f)_N^B$. Hence, $(H_f)^{AB} = (H_g)^{AB}$ if and only if $E^{M'N'}(B_k)_{M'}^M(B_k)_{N'}^N = E^{MN}$, i.e. $L_{[k]}$ is orthogonal.

Then due to $(H_f)^{AB} = (H_g)^{AB} \Leftrightarrow (G_f)^{MN} = (G_g)^{MN} \Leftrightarrow (G_f)_{MN} = (G_g)_{MN}$, the proposition is true. \square

Discussion 2.5.1. We notice that:

(1) Definition 2.5.2 tells us that Riemannian geometry is a subgeometry of intrinsic geometry of Definition 2.3.2 .

(2) Proposition 2.5.1 indicates that Definition 2.5.2 is consistent with the traditional definition of Riemannian manifold.

Hence, the intrinsic geometry of Definition 2.3.2 is larger than Riemannian geometry, and geometrical manifold is a more fundamental concept than Riemannian manifold. According to the point of view of Riemannian geometry, the ultimate origin of its geometrical property is metric. According to the point of view of geometrical manifold, the geometrical property has a more basic origin, which ultimately boils down to reference-system and its slack-tights B_M^A or C_A^M .

(1) In history, the slack-tights is called a semimetric in traditional theory of Riemannian geometry. Physicists noticed long ago [14,53] that when researching interactions between gravitational field and elementary particles, especially problems about spinor field, it can be described only by adopting semimetric representation, and it does not work by using metric representation. However, they did not realize that it means the connotation of traditional intrinsic geometry needs to be generalized.

(2) On one hand, it can be seen from Definition 2.2.3 that the slack-tights on geometrical manifold determine the metric on Riemannian manifold. On the other hand, even when the coefficients of metric tensors of two geometrical manifolds are completely the same, their slack-tights are not necessarily the same. These two aspects indicate that the theory of intrinsic geometry on geometrical manifold has richer geometrical properties than the traditional theory of intrinsic geometry on Riemannian manifold.

(3) It is important that there exists a concept of *simple connection* on geometrical manifold, see section 2.7 . If simple connection vanishes, Levi-Civita connection must vanish too. But conversely, if Levi-Civita connection vanishes, the simple connection does not necessarily vanish. Therefore, simple connection reflects more intrinsic properties of manifold than Levi-

Civita connection. It will be seen later that these properties just exactly can be used to describe the characteristics of gauge fields and elementary particles.

2.6 Universal geometry

Discussion 2.6.1. Let there be geometrical manifolds (M, f) and (M, g) . Define a relation of equivalence \sim , such that $(M, f) \sim (M, g)$ if and only if there exists $F_{[k]}$ such that $F_{[k]}([f]) = [g]$, where $F_{[k]}$ represents $L_{[k]}$ or $R_{[k]}$.

In fact such a transformation always exists, which is $L_{[g \circ f^{-1}]}$ or $R_{[f^{-1} \circ g]}$. Therefore, $\mathcal{M}(M)$ becomes the only equivalence class in the geometry $\tilde{\mathcal{M}}(M) \triangleq \mathcal{M}(M)/\sim$. It makes $\tilde{\mathcal{M}}(M)$ the universal geometry on geometrical manifolds.

Discussion 2.6.2. Make a summary for these subgeometries of intrinsic geometry. On geometrical manifold:

(1) An *intrinsic geometrical property* is an invariant under *identical intrinsic transformation* of reference-systems.

(2) A *kernal geometrical property* is an invariant under *flat transformation* of reference-systems.

(3) A *Riemannian geometrical property* is an invariant under *orthogonal transformation* of reference-systems.

(4) A *universal geometrical property* is an invariant under *arbitrary transformation* of reference-systems.

(5) Let e be the unit element of $GL(M)$. According to Remark 1.1, $\{e\}$ as the transformation group of intrinsic geometry is the smallest transformation group, and $GL(M)$ as the transformation group of universal geometry is the largest transformation group. In other words, on geometrical manifold, intrinsic geometry is the largest geometry, and universal geometry is the smallest geometry.

2.7 Simple connection

Discussion 2.7.1. Let Γ_{NP}^M be smooth real functions on manifold M . $\forall p \in M$, dx^M and $\frac{\partial}{\partial x^M}$ are natural basis vector fields in coordinate frame (U, x^M) of local reference-system $f(p)$. Consider the restriction of smooth real functions Γ_{NP}^M on U , affine connection can be expressed as:

$$D \frac{\partial}{\partial x^N} \triangleq \Gamma_{NP}^M dx^P \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial x^M}, \quad D dx^N \triangleq -\Gamma_{MP}^N dx^P \otimes dx^M. \quad (1)$$

In order to enable affine connection to describe intrinsic geometry, Γ_{NP}^M should be defined as the ones dependent on slack-tights B_M^A or C_A^M , such as Levi-Civita connection

$$\Gamma_{NP}^M \triangleq \frac{1}{2} G^{MQ} \left(\frac{\partial G_{NQ}}{\partial x^P} + \frac{\partial G_{PQ}}{\partial x^N} - \frac{\partial G_{NP}}{\partial x^Q} \right),$$

or other forms.

Levi-Civita connection is the unique torsion-free and metric-compatible connection, but it is not fundamental enough. On one hand it is because Levi-Civita connection cannot describe the

intrinsic properties determined by B_M^A and C_A^M when G_{MN} are all constants, on the other hand Levi-Civita connection is not simple enough.

The torsion-free condition is very helpful to simplify theoretical form, but the metric-compatible condition prevents further simplification of connection form. We consider that the metric-compatible condition $DG = 0$ was introduced to establish the intuition of Levi-Civita parallel displacement, but it is not the condition that more general concept of parallel displacement must rely on. Therefore, in order to simplify connection furthermore, it can be imagined that the torsion-free condition remains and the metric-compatible condition is given up. A nice choice is to adopt the following definition.

Definition 2.7.1. Let there be an affine connection D , which is expressed as equation (1) on performance coordinate frame (U, x^M) . If the connection coefficients are defined as

$$\Gamma_{NP}^M \triangleq \frac{1}{2} C_A^M \left(\frac{\partial B_N^A}{\partial x^P} + \frac{\partial B_P^A}{\partial x^N} \right) = -\frac{1}{2} \left(B_N^A \frac{\partial C_A^M}{\partial x^P} + B_P^A \frac{\partial C_A^M}{\partial x^N} \right), \quad (2)$$

D is called a **simple connection**.

Proposition 2.7.1. The simple connection is indeed an affine connection.

Proof. Let there be a reference-system f on manifold M . And let there be a local reference-system $t_p : x^{M'} = x^{M'}(x^M)$, which induces a reference-system transformation L_{t_p} sending $f(p) : x^M = x^M(\xi^A)$ to $h(p) \triangleq t_p \circ f(p) : x^{M'} = x^{M'}(\xi^A)$, where (U, ξ^A) is the common basis coordinate frame of $f(p)$ and $h(p)$. They can be expressed as a diagram:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} (U, \xi^A) & \xrightarrow{h(p)} & (U, x^{M'}) \\ f(p) \downarrow & \nearrow t_p & \\ (U, x^M) & & \end{array}$$

Let the slack-tights of t_p be

$$b_{M'}^M \triangleq \frac{\partial x^M}{\partial x^{M'}}, \quad c_M^{M'} \triangleq \frac{\partial x^{M'}}{\partial x^M}.$$

Let the slack-tights of f be B_M^A and C_A^M . For the restriction of them on U , the slack-tights applied transformation L_{t_p} are

$$B_{M'}^A = b_{M'}^M B_M^A, \quad C_A^{M'} = c_M^{M'} C_A^M.$$

According to Definition 2.7.1, the original simple connection and the one applied transformation L_{t_p} are respectively

$$(\Gamma_f)_{NP}^M \triangleq \frac{1}{2} C_A^M \left(\frac{\partial B_N^A}{\partial x^P} + \frac{\partial B_P^A}{\partial x^N} \right), \quad (\Gamma_f)_{N'P'}^{M'} \triangleq \frac{1}{2} C_A^{M'} \left(\frac{\partial B_{N'}^A}{\partial x^{P'}} + \frac{\partial B_{P'}^A}{\partial x^{N'}} \right).$$

Calculate the local transformation relation of the simple connection on U :

$$\begin{aligned}
(\Gamma_f)_{N'P'}^{M'} &\triangleq \frac{1}{2} C_A^{M'} \left(\frac{\partial B_{N'}^A}{\partial x^{P'}} + \frac{\partial B_{P'}^A}{\partial x^{N'}} \right) = \frac{1}{2} c_M^{M'} C_A^M \left(\frac{\partial (b_{N'}^N, B_N^A)}{\partial x^{P'}} + \frac{\partial (b_{P'}^P, B_P^A)}{\partial x^{N'}} \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2} c_M^{M'} C_A^M \left(\frac{\partial b_{N'}^N}{\partial x^{P'}} B_N^A + b_{N'}^N \frac{\partial B_N^A}{\partial x^{P'}} + \frac{\partial b_{P'}^P}{\partial x^{N'}} B_P^A + b_{P'}^P \frac{\partial B_P^A}{\partial x^{N'}} \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2} c_M^{M'} C_A^M \left(b_{N'}^N \frac{\partial B_N^A}{\partial x^{P'}} + b_{P'}^P \frac{\partial B_P^A}{\partial x^{N'}} \right) + \frac{1}{2} c_M^{M'} C_A^M \left(\frac{\partial b_{N'}^N}{\partial x^{P'}} B_N^A + \frac{\partial b_{P'}^P}{\partial x^{N'}} B_P^A \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2} c_M^{M'} C_A^M \left(\frac{\partial B_N^A}{\partial x^P} + \frac{\partial B_P^A}{\partial x^N} \right) b_{N'}^N b_{P'}^P + \frac{1}{2} c_M^{M'} \left(\frac{\partial b_{N'}^N}{\partial x^{P'}} + \frac{\partial b_{P'}^P}{\partial x^{N'}} \right) \\
&= (\Gamma_f)_{NP}^M c_M^{M'} b_{N'}^N b_{P'}^P + c_M^{M'} \frac{\partial b_{N'}^N}{\partial x^{P'}}.
\end{aligned}$$

This result is consistent with the general relation of local transformation of affine connection. So it has been proved that the simple connection $\Gamma_{NP}^M \triangleq \frac{1}{2} C_A^M \left(\frac{\partial B_N^A}{\partial x^P} + \frac{\partial B_P^A}{\partial x^N} \right)$ is indeed an affine connection, and evidently it is torsion-free. \square

Proposition 2.7.2. Suppose there are reference-systems g and k on manifold M . Let the slack-tights of g be $(B_g)_M^A$ and $(C_g)_M^A$. Let the slack-tights of k be $(B_k)_{M'}^{M'}$ and $(C_k)_{M'}^{M'}$. And let the slack-tights of $g' \triangleq L_k(g)$ be $(B_{g'})_{M'}^A = (B_g)_M^A (B_k)_{M'}^{M'}$ and $(C_{g'})_{M'}^A = (C_g)_M^A (C_k)_{M'}^{M'}$. Then let the simple connections of (M, g) , (M, k) and (M, g') be $(\Gamma_g)_{NP}^M$, $(\Gamma_k)_{N'P'}^{M'}$ and $(\Gamma_{g'})_{N'P'}^{M'}$, respectively. Thus,

$$(\Gamma_{g'})_{N'P'}^{M'} = (\Gamma_g)_{NP}^M (C_k)_{M'}^{M'} (B_k)_{N'}^N (B_k)_{P'}^P + (\Gamma_k)_{N'P'}^{M'}. \quad (3)$$

Proof. Calculate the following smooth functions of M on an arbitrary coordinate neighborhood.

$$\begin{aligned}
(\Gamma_{g'})_{N'P'}^{M'} &\triangleq \frac{1}{2} (C_{g'})_{M'}^{M'} \left(\frac{\partial (B_{g'})_{N'}^A}{\partial x^{P'}} + \frac{\partial (B_{g'})_{P'}^A}{\partial x^{N'}} \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2} (C_k)_{M'}^{M'} (C_g)_M^M \left(\frac{\partial ((B_k)_{N'}^N (B_g)_N^A)}{\partial x^{P'}} + \frac{\partial ((B_k)_{P'}^P (B_g)_P^A)}{\partial x^{N'}} \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2} (C_k)_{M'}^{M'} (C_g)_M^M \left(\frac{\partial (B_k)_{N'}^N}{\partial x^{P'}} (B_g)_N^A + (B_k)_{N'}^N \frac{\partial (B_g)_N^A}{\partial x^{P'}} + \frac{\partial (B_k)_{P'}^P}{\partial x^{N'}} (B_g)_P^A + (B_k)_{P'}^P \frac{\partial (B_g)_P^A}{\partial x^{N'}} \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2} (C_k)_{M'}^{M'} (C_g)_M^M \left((B_k)_{N'}^N \frac{\partial (B_g)_N^A}{\partial x^{P'}} + (B_k)_{P'}^P \frac{\partial (B_g)_P^A}{\partial x^{N'}} \right) \\
&+ \frac{1}{2} (C_k)_{M'}^{M'} (C_g)_M^M \left(\frac{\partial (B_k)_{N'}^N}{\partial x^{P'}} (B_g)_N^A + \frac{\partial (B_k)_{P'}^P}{\partial x^{N'}} (B_g)_P^A \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2} (C_k)_{M'}^{M'} (C_g)_M^M \left(\frac{\partial (B_g)_N^A}{\partial x^P} + \frac{\partial (B_g)_P^A}{\partial x^N} \right) (B_k)_{N'}^N (B_k)_{P'}^P + \frac{1}{2} (C_k)_{M'}^{M'} \left(\frac{\partial (B_k)_{N'}^N}{\partial x^{P'}} + \frac{\partial (B_k)_{P'}^P}{\partial x^{N'}} \right) \\
&= (\Gamma_g)_{NP}^M (C_k)_{M'}^{M'} (B_k)_{N'}^N (B_k)_{P'}^P + (\Gamma_k)_{N'P'}^{M'}.
\end{aligned}$$

\square

Remark 2.7.1. Simple connection proposed by this paper has two evident properties.

(1) Denote $\Gamma_{MNP} \triangleq G_{MM'}\Gamma_{NP}^{M'}$, $\Lambda_{MNP} \triangleq \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial G_{NM}}{\partial x^P} + \frac{\partial G_{PM}}{\partial x^N} - \frac{\partial G_{NP}}{\partial x^M} \right)$ then it is easy to verify

$$\Gamma_{MNP} = \frac{1}{2} \delta_{AB} B_M^B \left(\frac{\partial B_N^A}{\partial x^P} + \frac{\partial B_P^A}{\partial x^N} \right),$$

$$\Gamma_{MNP} + \Gamma_{NPM} + \Gamma_{PMN} = \Lambda_{MNP} + \Lambda_{NPM} + \Lambda_{PMN}.$$

(2) It is evident that when G_{MN} are all constants, Levi-Civita connection must be zero, and the corresponding Riemannian curvature tensor also must be zero. Meanwhile, simple connection is however not necessarily zero, and the corresponding Riemannian curvature tensor is also not necessarily zero. It indicates that simple connection reflects more intrinsic bending-properties of manifold than Levi-Civita connection.

2.8 Summary of this section

1. Riemannian manifold is generalized to geometrical manifold.
2. Intrinsic geometry is generalized, so that kernal geometry, Riemannian geometry and universal geometry are all subgeometries of intrinsic geometry.
3. The important concept of simple connection is defined, which is just exactly the key to describe elementary particles and gauge fields from the perspective of intrinsic geometry.

By applying the generalized intrinsic geometry, we are able to obtain an effective constructivity method for Hilbert's 6th problem. It can be used to unify elementary frameworks of theoretical physics.

3 Intrinsic geometrical solution for Hilbert's 6th problem

3.1 Axiom for Hilbert's 6th problem

We have to abstract and separate out physical connotations, so as to focus on mathematical constructions. A convenient way is to adopt the following axiom. There is only one axiom, and we do not need more.

The fundamental axiom. *Physical reality should be cognized by using the concept of reference-system on geometrical manifold.*

Such a concept of reference-system is strictly defined in Definition 2.1.2 . This axiom has an evident corollary as below, which can be called the *principle of universal relativity*.

Corollary. Universal physical property should be cognized by using universal geometrical property of geometrical manifold.

Such a concept of universal geometrical property is strictly defined in Definition 1.2 and section 2.6 . In the following sections, universal physical properties, such as time metric, space metric, evolution, etc., will be strictly defined as some universal geometrical properties of geometrical manifold. Other main conclusions, postulates and equations of fundamental physics can also be strictly defined, constructed and proved in pure mathematical sense.

3.2 Mathematical treatment of time and space

Definition 3.2.1. On a neighborhood U of point p , according to Definition 2.2.3, there are $d\xi^0$ and dx^0 defined on two coordinate frames (U, ξ^A) and (U, x^M) of $f(p)$ as

$$\begin{cases} (d\xi^0)^2 \triangleq \delta_{AB} d\xi^A d\xi^B = g_{MN} dx^M dx^N, \\ (dx^0)^2 \triangleq \varepsilon_{MN} dx^M dx^N = h_{AB} d\xi^A d\xi^B. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

We speak of $d\xi^0$ and dx^0 as **total space metrics** of (U, ξ^A) and (U, x^M) , or as **time metrics**.

On geometrical manifold (M, f) , $d\xi^0$ and dx^0 defined as

$$\begin{cases} (d\xi^0)^2 \triangleq \Delta_{AB} d\xi^A d\xi^B = G_{MN} dx^M dx^N \\ (dx^0)^2 \triangleq E_{MN} dx^M dx^N = H_{AB} d\xi^A d\xi^B \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

are called **total space metrics** or **time metrics** of M .

Remark 3.2.1. Such a new treatment about the concept of time in this paper is very important. It will make the two evolution notions of gravitational theory and quantum mechanics become unified and coordinated. In this way, time metric reflects the total evolution in the total-dimensional space, while a specific spatial metric reflects a partial evolution in a specific direction.

Definition 3.2.2. Let P and N be closed submanifolds of manifold $M = P \times N$. Denote $r \triangleq \dim P$. Let $s, i = 1, \dots, r$ and $a, m = r+1, \dots, \mathfrak{D}$. Select some proper coordinate frames $\{\xi^A\}$ and $\{x^M\}$ such that on P there are coordinate frames $\{\xi^s\}$ and $\{x^i\}$ inherited from M , and on N there are coordinate frames $\{\xi^a\}$ and $\{x^m\}$ inherited from M . Correspondingly, two subspace metrics can be defined on the coordinate neighborhoods on P and N respectively:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (d\xi^{(P)})^2 \triangleq \sum_{s=1}^r (d\xi^s)^2 = \delta_{st} d\xi^s d\xi^t \\ (dx^{(P)})^2 \triangleq \sum_{i=1}^r (dx^i)^2 = \varepsilon_{ij} dx^i dx^j \end{array} \right\}, \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (d\xi^{(N)})^2 \triangleq \sum_{a=r+1}^{\mathfrak{D}} (d\xi^a)^2 = \delta_{ab} d\xi^a d\xi^b \\ (dx^{(N)})^2 \triangleq \sum_{m=r+1}^{\mathfrak{D}} (dx^m)^2 = \varepsilon_{mn} dx^m dx^n \end{array} \right\}.$$

For convenience, N is called a **submanifold of internal space** and P is called a **submanifold of external space**. $d\xi^{(N)}$ and $dx^{(N)}$ are called **proptime metrics**.

3.3 Mathematical treatment of evolution

3.3.1 Definition and coordinate form of evolution

Definition 3.3.1.1. Let there be two reference-systems f and g on manifold M . If $\forall p \in M$, $f(p) \triangleq \varphi_U \circ \psi_U^{-1}$ and $g(p) \triangleq \varphi_U \circ \rho_U^{-1}$ have the same performance coordinate frame φ_U , namely it can be intuitively expressed as a diagram

$$\psi_U(U) \xrightarrow{f(p)} \varphi_U(U) \xleftarrow{g(p)} \rho_U(U),$$

we say f and g **motion relatively and interact mutually**, and also say that f **evolves** in g , or f **evolves** on geometrical manifold (M, g) . Meanwhile, g evolves in f , or say g evolves on (M, f) .

Definition 3.3.1.2. Let there be a one-parameter group of diffeomorphisms $\varphi_X : M \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow M$ acting on M . φ_X determines a smooth tangent vector field X on M . If X is nonzero everywhere, we say φ_X is a **set of evolution paths** on M , and X is an **evolution direction field** on M .

Let $T \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ be an interval. Suppose there is a smooth map $L_p : T \rightarrow M$ which is on the orbit $\varphi_{X,p}(t)$ of φ_X through p , and L_p is a regular submanifold of M , then the map L_p is called an **evolution path** through p , or **path** for short. The tangent vector $\frac{d}{dt} \triangleq [L_p] = X(p)$ is called an **evolution direction** at p . If it does not need to emphasize the point p , L_p can be denoted by L concisely.

Definition 3.3.1.3. $\forall p \in M$, let the coordinate representations of $f(p) \triangleq \varphi_U \circ \psi_U^{-1}$ be

$$x^M = x^M(\xi^A), \quad \xi^A = \xi^A(x^M),$$

and the coordinate representations of $g(p) \triangleq \varphi_U \circ \rho_U^{-1}$

$$x^M = x^M(\zeta^A), \quad \zeta^A = \zeta^A(x^M).$$

Then let time metrics on (U, φ_U) , (U, ψ_U) , (U, ρ_U) be dx^0 , $d\xi^0$, $d\zeta^0$, respectively.

Each path L_p is a 1-dimensional regular submanifold of M , therefore on open set $U_L \triangleq U \cap L_p$ there exist coordinate neighborhoods (U_L, φ_{UL}) , (U_L, ψ_{UL}) and (U_L, ρ_{UL}) such that the regular imbedding

$$\pi : L_p \rightarrow M, q \mapsto q \tag{6}$$

induces coordinate maps and parameter equations

$$\begin{cases} \psi_U \circ \pi \circ \psi_{UL}^{-1} : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\mathfrak{D}}, (\xi^0) \mapsto (\xi^A), & \xi^A = \xi^A(\xi^0) \\ \varphi_U \circ \pi \circ \varphi_{UL}^{-1} : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\mathfrak{D}}, (x^0) \mapsto (x^M), & x^M = x^M(x^0) \\ \rho_U \circ \pi \circ \rho_{UL}^{-1} : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\mathfrak{D}}, (\zeta^0) \mapsto (\zeta^A), & \zeta^A = \zeta^A(\zeta^0) \end{cases}$$

which satisfy $\sum_{A=1}^{\mathfrak{D}} \left(\frac{d\xi^A}{d\xi^0} \right)^2 = 1$, $\sum_{M=1}^{\mathfrak{D}} \left(\frac{dx^M}{dx^0} \right)^2 = 1$, $\sum_{A=1}^{\mathfrak{D}} \left(\frac{d\zeta^A}{d\zeta^0} \right)^2 = 1$.

Definition 3.3.1.4. $f(p) = \varphi_U \circ \psi_U^{-1}$ and $f^{-1}(p) = \psi_U \circ \varphi_U^{-1}$ on U induce reference-systems on U_L :

$$\begin{cases} f_L(p) \triangleq \varphi_{UL} \circ \psi_{UL}^{-1}, & x^0 = x^0(\xi^0) \\ f_L^{-1}(p) \triangleq \psi_{UL} \circ \varphi_{UL}^{-1}, & \xi^0 = \xi^0(x^0) \end{cases}.$$

Then we obtain the **coordinate form of evolution** of f :

$$\begin{cases} \xi^A = \xi^A(x^M) = \xi^A(x^0) \\ \xi^0 = \xi^0(x^0) \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} x^M = x^M(\xi^A) = x^M(\xi^0) \\ x^0 = x^0(\xi^0) \end{cases}. \tag{7}$$

3.3.2 Evolution lemma

Definition 3.3.2.1. Let L be a path on manifold M , $\forall p \in L$. Suppose $T_p(M)$ and $T_p(L)$ are the tangent spaces at p on M and L respectively, and $T_p^*(M)$ and $T_p^*(L)$ are the cotangent spaces.

$\forall p \in L$, the regular imbedding $\pi : L \rightarrow M$, $q \mapsto q$ induces tangent map and cotangent map

$$\begin{cases} \pi_*|_p : T_p(L) \rightarrow T_p(M), & [\gamma_L] \mapsto [\pi \circ \gamma_L], \\ \pi^*|_p : T_p^*(M) \rightarrow T_p^*(L), & df \mapsto d(f \circ \pi). \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Evidently, restricting on L , the tangent map is an injection, and the cotangent map is a surjection.

$\forall \frac{d}{dt_L} \in T_p(L)$, $\forall df \in T_p^*(M)$, denote

$$\frac{d}{dt} \triangleq \pi_*|_p \left(\frac{d}{dt_L} \right) \in T_p(M), \quad df_L \triangleq \pi^*|_p (df) \in T_p^*(L). \quad (9)$$

We say $\frac{d}{dt}$ and $\frac{d}{dt_L}$ are **equivalent**, df and df_L are **homomorphic**. They are denoted by

$$\frac{d}{dt} \cong \frac{d}{dt_L}, \quad df \simeq df_L. \quad (10)$$

The above locally defined concepts can also be applied to the entire manifold, and furthermore, they can be transplanted without hindrance to **any-order tensor product space** generated by tangent bundle and cotangent bundle, such as:

- (1) If $\frac{d}{dt} \cong \frac{d}{dt_L}$, then $\forall df$ we say $df \otimes \frac{d}{dt}$ and $df \otimes \frac{d}{dt_L}$ are **equivalent**, denoted by $df \otimes \frac{d}{dt} \cong df \otimes \frac{d}{dt_L}$.
- (2) If $df \simeq df_L$, then $\forall \frac{d}{dt}$ we say $df \otimes \frac{d}{dt}$ and $df_L \otimes \frac{d}{dt}$ are **homomorphic**, denoted by $df \otimes \frac{d}{dt} \simeq df_L \otimes \frac{d}{dt}$.

Proposition 3.3.2.1. If $\frac{d}{dt} \cong \frac{d}{dt_L}$ and $df \simeq df_L$, then $\left\langle \frac{d}{dt}, df \right\rangle = \left\langle \frac{d}{dt_L}, df_L \right\rangle$.

Proof. The tangent vectors $\frac{d}{dt}$ and $\frac{d}{dt_L}$ are respectively defined as equivalence classes $[\gamma]$ and $[\gamma_L]$ of parameter curves, the cotangent vectors df and df_L are respectively defined as equivalence classes $[f]$ and $[f_L]$ of smooth functions, which satisfy $\gamma = \pi \circ \gamma_L$, $f_L = f \circ \pi$. Hence,

$$\left\langle \frac{d}{dt}, df \right\rangle = \left\langle \frac{d}{dt_L}, df_L \right\rangle \Leftrightarrow \langle [\gamma], [f] \rangle = \langle [\gamma_L], [f_L] \rangle \Leftrightarrow \frac{d(f \circ \gamma)}{dt} = \frac{d(f_L \circ \gamma_L)}{dt},$$

where

$$f \circ \gamma = f \circ (\pi \circ \gamma_L), \quad f_L \circ \gamma_L = (f \circ \pi) \circ \gamma_L.$$

Evidently, $f \circ \gamma = f_L \circ \gamma_L$, which makes $\left\langle \frac{d}{dt}, df \right\rangle = \left\langle \frac{d}{dt_L}, df_L \right\rangle$ true. \square

Definition 3.3.2.2. $\forall p \in L$, on coordinate neighborhood U_L of point p , define

$$\begin{aligned} b_0^A &\triangleq \frac{d\xi^A}{dx^0}, & b_0^0 &\triangleq \frac{d\xi^0}{dx^0}, & c_0^M &\triangleq \frac{dx^M}{d\xi^0}, & c_0^0 &\triangleq \frac{dx^0}{d\xi^0}, \\ \varepsilon_0^M &\triangleq \frac{dx^M}{dx^0} = b_0^0 c_0^M = b_0^A c_A^M, & \delta_0^A &\triangleq \frac{d\xi^A}{d\xi^0} = c_0^0 b_0^A = c_0^M b_M^A. \end{aligned}$$

They determine the following smooth functions on the entire L :

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} B_0^A : L \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad p \mapsto B_0^A(p) \triangleq (b_{f(p)})_0^A(p) \\ C_0^M : L \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad p \mapsto C_0^M(p) \triangleq (c_{f(p)})_0^M(p) \end{array} \right\}, \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} B_0^0 : L \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad p \mapsto B_0^0(p) \triangleq (b_{f(p)})_0^0(p) \\ C_0^0 : L \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad p \mapsto C_0^0(p) \triangleq (c_{f(p)})_0^0(p) \end{array} \right\}.$$

For convenience, if no confusion, still using notations ε and δ , we also have smooth functions:

$$\varepsilon_0^M \triangleq B_0^0 C_0^M = B_0^A C_A^M, \quad \delta_0^A \triangleq C_0^0 B_0^A = C_0^M B_M^A.$$

Define $d\xi_0 \triangleq \frac{dx^0}{d\xi^0} dx^0$ and $dx_0 \triangleq \frac{d\xi^0}{dx^0} d\xi^0$, which induce $\frac{d}{d\xi_0}$ and $\frac{d}{dx_0}$, such that $\left\langle \frac{d}{d\xi_0}, d\xi_0 \right\rangle = 1$, $\left\langle \frac{d}{dx_0}, dx_0 \right\rangle = 1$. On U_L we also define

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{b}_A^0 &\triangleq \frac{d\xi_A}{dx_0}, \quad \bar{b}_0^0 \triangleq \frac{d\xi_0}{dx_0}, \quad \bar{c}_M^0 \triangleq \frac{dx_M}{d\xi_0}, \quad \bar{c}_0^0 \triangleq \frac{dx_0}{d\xi_0}, \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_M^0 &\triangleq \frac{dx_M}{dx_0} = \bar{b}_0^0 \bar{c}_M^0 = \bar{b}_A^0 \bar{c}_M^A, \quad \bar{\delta}_A^0 \triangleq \frac{d\xi_A}{d\xi_0} = \bar{c}_0^0 \bar{b}_A^0 = \bar{c}_M^0 \bar{b}_A^M. \end{aligned}$$

They determine the following smooth functions on the entire L :

$$\begin{cases} \bar{B}_A^0 : L \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, & p \mapsto \bar{B}_A^0(p) \triangleq (\bar{b}_{f(p)})_A^0(p) \\ \bar{C}_M^0 : L \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, & p \mapsto \bar{C}_M^0(p) \triangleq (\bar{c}_{f(p)})_M^0(p) \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} \bar{B}_0^0 : L \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, & p \mapsto \bar{B}_0^0(p) \triangleq (\bar{b}_{f(p)})_0^0(p) \\ \bar{C}_0^0 : L \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, & p \mapsto \bar{C}_0^0(p) \triangleq (\bar{c}_{f(p)})_0^0(p) \end{cases}. \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_M^0 \triangleq \bar{B}_0^0 \bar{C}_M^0 = \bar{B}_A^0 \bar{C}_M^A, \quad \bar{\delta}_A^0 \triangleq \bar{C}_0^0 \bar{B}_A^0 = \bar{C}_M^0 \bar{B}_A^M. \end{cases}$$

Proposition 3.3.2.2. (Evolution lemma). Let L be a path on manifold M . Suppose there are tangent vector fields $w^M \frac{\partial}{\partial x^M}$, $\bar{w}_M \frac{\partial}{\partial x_M}$ and cotangent vector fields $w_M dx^M$, $\bar{w}^M dx_M$ on M , and there are tangent vector fields $w^0 \frac{d}{dx^0}$, $\bar{w}_0 \frac{d}{dx_0}$ and cotangent vector fields $w_0 dx^0$, $\bar{w}^0 dx_0$ on L . Then the following conclusions hold:

$$\begin{cases} w^M \frac{\partial}{\partial x^M} \cong w^0 \frac{d}{dx^0} \Leftrightarrow w^M = w^0 \varepsilon_0^M \\ w_M dx^M \simeq w_0 dx^0 \Leftrightarrow \varepsilon_0^M w_M = w_0 \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} \bar{w}_M \frac{\partial}{\partial x_M} \cong \bar{w}_0 \frac{d}{dx_0} \Leftrightarrow \bar{w}_M = \bar{w}_0 \bar{\varepsilon}_M^0 \\ \bar{w}^M dx_M \simeq \bar{w}^0 dx_0 \Leftrightarrow \bar{\varepsilon}_M^0 \bar{w}^M = \bar{w}^0 \end{cases}.$$

Proof. The following locally discussion can also be applied to the entire manifold.

1. Consider the case that basis vectors are dx^M and $\frac{\partial}{\partial x^M}$.

For tangent vector,

$$\pi_* \left(\frac{d}{dx^0} \right) = \frac{dx^M}{dx^0} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^M} \Leftrightarrow \frac{dx^M}{dx^0} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^M} \cong \frac{d}{dx^0} \Leftrightarrow \varepsilon_0^M \frac{\partial}{\partial x^M} \cong \frac{d}{dx^0} \Leftrightarrow w^0 \varepsilon_0^M \frac{\partial}{\partial x^M} \cong w^0 \frac{d}{dx^0}.$$

Because the tangent map is an injection, then $w^M \frac{\partial}{\partial x^M} \cong w^0 \frac{d}{dx^0} \Leftrightarrow w^M = w^0 \varepsilon_0^M$.

For cotangent vector, $dx^M \simeq \varepsilon_0^M dx^0 \Rightarrow w_M dx^M \simeq \varepsilon_0^M w_M dx^0$, then $w_M dx^M \simeq w_0 dx^0 \Leftrightarrow \varepsilon_0^M w_M = w_0$.

2. Consider the case that basis vectors are dx_M and $\frac{\partial}{\partial x_M}$.

For tangent vector,

$$\pi_* \left(\frac{d}{dx_0} \right) = \frac{dx_M}{dx_0} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_M} \Leftrightarrow \frac{dx_M}{dx_0} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_M} \cong \frac{d}{dx_0} \Leftrightarrow \bar{\varepsilon}_M^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_M} \cong \frac{d}{dx_0} \Leftrightarrow \bar{w}_0 \bar{\varepsilon}_M^0 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_M} \cong \bar{w}_0 \frac{d}{dx_0}.$$

Because the tangent map is an injection, then $\bar{w}_M \frac{\partial}{\partial x_M} \cong \bar{w}_0 \frac{d}{dx_0} \Leftrightarrow \bar{w}_M = \bar{w}_0 \bar{\varepsilon}_M^0$.

For cotangent vector, $dx_M \simeq \bar{\varepsilon}_M^0 dx_0 \Rightarrow \bar{w}^M dx_M \simeq \bar{\varepsilon}_M^0 \bar{w}^M dx_0$, then $\bar{w}^M dx_M \simeq \bar{w}^0 dx_0 \Leftrightarrow \bar{\varepsilon}_M^0 \bar{w}^M = \bar{w}^0$. \square

3.3.3 Metric form of evolution

Definition 3.3.3.1. On U_L define

$$g_{00} \triangleq \frac{dx_0}{dx^0} = b_0^0 b_0^0, \quad g^{00} \triangleq \frac{dx^0}{dx_0} = c_0^0 c_0^0, \quad h_{00} \triangleq \frac{d\xi_0}{d\xi^0} = c_0^0 c_0^0, \quad h^{00} \triangleq \frac{d\xi^0}{d\xi_0} = b_0^0 b_0^0.$$

They determine the following smooth functions defined on L :

$$G_{00} \triangleq B_0^0 B_0^0, \quad G^{00} \triangleq C_0^0 C_0^0, \quad H_{00} \triangleq C_0^0 C_0^0, \quad H^{00} \triangleq B_0^0 B_0^0.$$

Proposition 3.3.3.1. On L , $\frac{d}{dx_0} = G^{00} \frac{d}{dx^0}$, $\frac{d}{d\xi_0} = H^{00} \frac{d}{d\xi^0}$.

Proof. At any point, tangent vector $\frac{d}{dx_0}$ can be expanded as $\frac{d}{dx_0} = X \frac{d}{dx^0}$ with respect to basis $\frac{d}{dx^0}$, and tangent vector $\frac{d}{d\xi_0}$ can be expanded as $\frac{d}{d\xi_0} = Y \frac{d}{d\xi^0}$ with respect to basis $\frac{d}{d\xi^0}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \frac{d}{dx_0}, dx_0 \right\rangle = 1 &\Leftrightarrow \left\langle X \frac{d}{dx^0}, g_{00} dx^0 \right\rangle = 1 \Leftrightarrow X g_{00} = 1 \Leftrightarrow X = \frac{1}{g_{00}} = g^{00} \Rightarrow \frac{d}{dx_0} = g^{00} \frac{d}{dx^0}, \\ \left\langle \frac{d}{d\xi_0}, d\xi_0 \right\rangle = 1 &\Leftrightarrow \left\langle Y \frac{d}{d\xi^0}, h_{00} d\xi^0 \right\rangle = 1 \Leftrightarrow Y h_{00} = 1 \Leftrightarrow Y = \frac{1}{h_{00}} = h^{00} \Rightarrow \frac{d}{d\xi_0} = h^{00} \frac{d}{d\xi^0}. \end{aligned}$$

This local conclusion can be applied to the entire path, so $\frac{d}{dx_0} = G^{00} \frac{d}{dx^0}$ and $\frac{d}{d\xi_0} = H^{00} \frac{d}{d\xi^0}$ hold on L . \square

Proposition 3.3.3.2. On L , $H_{00} = H_{AB} \delta_0^A \delta_0^B$, $G_{00} = G_{MN} \varepsilon_0^M \varepsilon_0^N$.

Proof. On a neighborhood U_L of any point on L ,

$$\begin{cases} h_{AB} \delta_0^A \delta_0^B = \varepsilon_{MN} c_A^M c_B^N \delta_0^A \delta_0^B = \varepsilon_{MN} \frac{dx^M}{d\xi^0} \frac{dx^N}{d\xi^0} = \frac{dx^0}{d\xi^0} \frac{dx^0}{d\xi^0} = h_{00} \\ g_{MN} \varepsilon_0^M \varepsilon_0^N = \delta_{AB} b_M^A b_N^B \varepsilon_0^M \varepsilon_0^N = \delta_{AB} \frac{d\xi^A}{dx^0} \frac{d\xi^B}{dx^0} = \frac{d\xi^0}{dx^0} \frac{d\xi^0}{dx^0} = g_{00} \end{cases}.$$

So $H_{00} = H_{AB} \delta_0^A \delta_0^B$ and $G_{00} = G_{MN} \varepsilon_0^M \varepsilon_0^N$ hold on the entire L . \square

Proposition 3.3.3.3. The following left-hand formulas are true on L . When $\mathfrak{D} > 1$, the right-hand formulas are in general false on L .

$$\begin{cases} G_{MN} dx^M \otimes dx^N \simeq G_{00} dx^0 \otimes dx^0, \\ G^{MN} dx_M \otimes dx_N \simeq G^{00} dx_0 \otimes dx_0, \\ H_{AB} d\xi^A \otimes d\xi^B \simeq H_{00} d\xi^0 \otimes d\xi^0, \\ H^{AB} d\xi_A \otimes d\xi_B \simeq H^{00} d\xi_0 \otimes d\xi_0. \end{cases} \quad \begin{cases} X^{MN} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^M} \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial x^N} \cong X^{00} \frac{d}{dx^0} \otimes \frac{d}{dx^0}, \\ X_{MN} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_M} \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial x_N} \cong X_{00} \frac{d}{dx_0} \otimes \frac{d}{dx_0}, \\ Y^{AB} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^A} \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^B} \cong Y^{00} \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \otimes \frac{d}{d\xi^0}, \\ Y_{AB} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_A} \otimes \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_B} \cong Y_{00} \frac{d}{d\xi_0} \otimes \frac{d}{d\xi_0}. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Due to Proposition 3.3.3.2 and evolution lemma, the left-hand formulas hold evidently. Now consider the right-hand ones.

On U_L when $\mathfrak{D} > 1$, x^{MN} cannot be expressed as the form like $y \varepsilon_0^M \varepsilon_0^N$. Otherwise, let $x^{MN} = y \varepsilon_0^M \varepsilon_0^N$, then the following two conclusions are in contradiction with each other:

$$\begin{cases} dx_M dx^M = x^{MN} dx_M dx_N = (y \varepsilon_0^M \varepsilon_0^N) dx_M dx_N = y \frac{dx^M dx_M dx^N dx_N}{dx^0 dx^0} = y g_{00} dx_M dx^M \Rightarrow y = \frac{1}{g_{00}} = g^{00}, \\ \mathfrak{D} = x^{MN} x_{MN} = (y \varepsilon_0^M \varepsilon_0^N) g_{MN} = y (g_{MN} \varepsilon_0^M \varepsilon_0^N) = y g_{00} \Rightarrow y = \frac{\mathfrak{D}}{g_{00}} = \mathfrak{D} g^{00}. \end{cases}$$

□

Remark 3.3.3.1. Due to the above proposition and section 2.2 , we know that although tensors \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{X} have relations $G_{MN} = X_{MN}$ and $G^{MN} = X^{MN}$ and tensors \mathbf{H} and \mathbf{Y} have relations $H_{AB} = Y_{AB}$ and $H^{AB} = Y^{AB}$, when considering evolution, \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{H} have better properties than \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} .

3.3.4 Mathematical treatment of actual evolution

Definition 3.3.4.1. Let \mathbb{V}^n be the totality of n -order tensor fields generated by tangent vector bundle and cotangent vector bundle on M . Then suppose $\mathbf{T} \triangleq t \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \otimes dx \right\} \in \mathbb{V}^n$, where smooth real functions t represent the coefficients of tensor \mathbf{T} . The regular imbedding $\pi : L \rightarrow M$ induces $t_L \triangleq t \circ \pi : L \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\mathbf{T}_L \triangleq t_L \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \otimes dx \right\}$.

(1) Let D be affine connection, and denote $t_{L,0} \triangleq t_{;Q}\varepsilon_0^Q$, then the **absolute differential** of \mathbf{T} and \mathbf{T}_L can be expressed as

$$\begin{cases} D\mathbf{T} \triangleq Dt \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \otimes dx \right\} \triangleq t_{;Q}dx^Q \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \otimes dx \right\}, \\ D_L\mathbf{T}_L \triangleq D_L t_L \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \otimes dx \right\} \triangleq t_{L;0}dx^0 \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \otimes dx \right\}, \end{cases}$$

where $Dt \triangleq t_{;Q}dx^Q$, $D_L t_L \triangleq t_{L;0}dx^0$.

(2) Gradient operator ∇ is called the **actual evolution**. The **absolute gradient** of \mathbf{T} and \mathbf{T}_L can be expressed as

$$\begin{cases} \nabla\mathbf{T} \triangleq \nabla t \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \otimes dx \right\} \triangleq t_{;Q} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^Q} \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \otimes dx \right\}, \\ \nabla_L\mathbf{T}_L \triangleq \nabla_L t_L \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \otimes dx \right\} \triangleq t_{L;0} \frac{d}{dx^0} \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \otimes dx \right\}, \end{cases}$$

where $\nabla t \triangleq t_{;Q} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^Q}$, $\nabla_L t_L \triangleq t_{L;0} \frac{d}{dx^0}$. The gradient direction (field) ∇t is called the **actual evolution direction (field)** of \mathbf{T} . The integral curve of ∇t is called the **gradient line** or **actual evolution path** of \mathbf{T} .

Proposition 3.3.4.1. $D\mathbf{T} \simeq D_L\mathbf{T}_L$ if L is an arbitrary path. $\nabla\mathbf{T} \cong \nabla_L\mathbf{T}_L$ if and only if L is the gradient line of \mathbf{T} .

Proof. According to definition, the first conclusion is evident. Now consider the second conclusion.

(1) The sufficiency. Let L be the gradient line of \mathbf{T} . $\forall p \in L$, the gradient direction at p is $t_{;Q} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^Q} \in T_p(M)$. Because tangent map is injection, there exists a unique $X \frac{d}{dx^0} \in T_p(L)$ such that $t_{;Q} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^Q} \cong X \frac{d}{dx^0}$. Applying evolution lemma we obtain

$$t_{;Q} = X \left. \frac{dx^Q}{dx^0} \right|_L, \quad dx^Q \simeq \left. \frac{dx^Q}{dx^0} \right|_L dx^0,$$

thereby

$$t_{;Q}dx^Q \simeq X \left. \frac{dx^Q}{dx^0} \right|_L \left. \frac{dx^Q}{dx^0} \right|_L dx^0.$$

According to Definition 3.3.1.3 , $(d\xi^0)^2 = \sum_{A=1}^{\mathcal{Q}} (d\xi^A)^2$ holds on U_L , i.e. $dx_0 dx^0 = dx_Q dx^Q$. Substitute it into the above formula, then we obtain $t_{;Q} dx^Q \simeq X dx^0$. Due to evolution lemma, $X = t_{;Q} \frac{dx^Q}{dx^0} = t_{L;0}$, and then $\nabla \mathbf{T} \cong \nabla_L \mathbf{T}_L$ holds.

(2) The necessity is evident. In fact, $\forall p \in L$, suppose tangent vector $t_{;0} \frac{d}{dx_0}$ on L makes $\nabla \mathbf{T} \cong \nabla_L \mathbf{T}_L$ hold, so $t_{;Q} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_Q} \cong t_{;0} \frac{d}{dx_0}$. And suppose $\forall p \in L$, $X_Q \frac{\partial}{\partial x_Q} \cong t_{;0} \frac{d}{dx_0}$. Because tangent map is injection, $X_Q = t_{;Q}$, which indicates that $X_Q \frac{\partial}{\partial x_Q}$ can only be the gradient direction. Additionally, p is arbitrary on L , hence L can only be the gradient line, not other paths. \square

Definition 3.3.4.2. According to evolution lemma, $\nabla \mathbf{T} \cong \nabla_L \mathbf{T}_L$ if and only if $t_{;Q} = t_{L;0} \varepsilon_Q^0$ or $t^{;Q} = t_L^{;0} \varepsilon_Q^0$. These two equations are called the **actual evolution equations** of \mathbf{T} .

Definition 3.3.4.3. Suppose there is a tensor product $\mathbf{U} \triangleq u_Q dx^Q \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \otimes dx \right\}$, such that the system of 1-order non-homogeneous linear equations $t_{;Q} = u_Q$ has a unique solution t . Then ∇t satisfies

$$u_Q dx^Q \simeq u_0 dx^0, \quad u_Q \frac{\partial}{\partial x_Q} \cong u_0 \frac{d}{dx_0}.$$

We say the actual evolution direction $\nabla t = u_Q \frac{\partial}{\partial x_Q}$ is **determined by** $u_Q dx^Q$.

Remark 3.3.4.1. Now for any universal geometrical property defined in form of tensor product on geometrical manifold, we are able to study its actual evolution in way of absolute gradient.

Then two important gradient directions will be discussed. One is the actual evolution of potential field of reference-system itself. The other is the case that general charge of one reference-system evolves in another reference-system. They are both attributed to geometrical properties of geometrical manifold.

3.3.5 Mathematical treatment of actual evolution of potential field

Definition 3.3.5.1. Suppose f evolves in g , that is, $\forall p \in M$, $(U, \xi^A) \xrightarrow{f(p)} (U, x^M) \xleftarrow{g(p)} (U, \zeta^A)$. We will always take the following notations in coordinate frame (U, x^M) .

(1) Let the connection of geometrical manifold (M, f) be Λ_{NP}^M . Let the connection of (M, g) be Γ_{NP}^M . Colon ":" is used to express the absolute derivative on (M, f) , and semicolon ";" is used to express the absolute derivative on (M, g) , e.g.:

$$u^Q_{;P} = \frac{\partial u^Q}{\partial x^P} + u^H \Lambda_{HP}^Q, \quad u^Q_{:P} = \frac{\partial u^Q}{\partial x^P} + u^H \Gamma_{HP}^Q.$$

We also call Λ_{NP}^M the potential field of f , and Γ_{NP}^M the potential field of g , or say potential for short. In order to describe intrinsic geometry, we must adopt affine connection dependent on slack-tights. It can be either Levi-Civita connection or simple connection of Definition 2.7.1 . Because the scope of applicability of simple connection is larger than Levi-Civita connection, we suppose Λ_{NP}^M and Γ_{NP}^M are both simple connections.

(2) Let the coefficients of Riemannian curvature of (M, f) be K_{NPQ}^M . Let the coefficients of Riemannian curvature of (M, g) be R_{NPQ}^M . Thus,

$$\begin{cases} K_{NPQ}^M \triangleq \frac{\partial \Lambda_{NQ}^M}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Lambda_{NP}^M}{\partial x^Q} + \Lambda_{NQ}^H \Lambda_{HP}^M - \Lambda_{NP}^H \Lambda_{HQ}^M, \\ R_{NPQ}^M \triangleq \frac{\partial \Gamma_{NQ}^M}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{NP}^M}{\partial x^Q} + \Gamma_{NQ}^H \Gamma_{HP}^M - \Gamma_{NP}^H \Gamma_{HQ}^M. \end{cases}$$

(3) The values of indices of internal space and external space are taken according to Definition 5.1.1 .

Discussion 3.3.5.1. Consider evolution of f . Denote $\rho_{N0}^M \triangleq K_{NPQ}^M \cdot^P \varepsilon_0^Q$, then we have $K_{NPQ}^M \cdot^P dx^Q \simeq \rho_{N0}^M dx^0$ in an arbitrary direction.

Specially, we have $K_{NPQ}^M \cdot^P \frac{\partial}{\partial x^Q} \simeq \rho_{N0}^M \frac{d}{dx_0}$ in the gradient direction determined by $K_{NPQ}^M \cdot^P dx^Q$. Now due to Proposition 3.3.2.2 , we obtain the actual evolution equation $K_{NPQ}^M \cdot^P = \rho_{N0}^M \varepsilon_0^Q$. Denote $j_{NQ}^M \triangleq \rho_{N0}^M \varepsilon_0^Q$, then we obtain

$$K_{NPQ}^M \cdot^P = j_{NQ}^M, \quad (11)$$

which is called the **general Yang-Mills field equation** of f . Then due to Proposition 3.3.4.1 we directly obtain the following theorem.

Proposition 3.3.5.1. (Evolution theorem of general gauge field). ρ_{N0}^M and j_{NQ}^M are both intrinsic geometrical properties of (M, f) . Equation $K_{NPQ}^M \cdot^P = j_{NQ}^M$ holds if and only if its evolution direction field is the gradient direction field determined by $K_{NPQ}^M \cdot^P dx^Q$.

Definition 3.3.5.2. Besides ρ_{N0}^M , there are also $\rho_N^{M0} \triangleq G^{00} \rho_{N0}^M$, $\rho_{MN0} \triangleq G_{MM'} \rho_{N0}^{M'}$ and $\rho_{MN}^0 \triangleq G^{00} \rho_{MN0}$. We call each of them a **general charge**, or **charge** for short.

3.3.6 Mathematical treatment of actual evolution of general charge

Discussion 3.3.6.1. Without loss of generality, on geometrical manifold (M, g) we can discuss the actual evolution of charge tensor $\mathbf{F}^0 \triangleq \rho_{MN}^0 dx^M \otimes dx^N$ of f in way of absolute gradient. For the sake of simplicity, denote ρ_{MN}^0 by ρ_{MN} concisely.

The absolute differential of \mathbf{F}^0 on (M, g) is $D\mathbf{F}^0 \triangleq D\rho_{MN} \otimes dx^M \otimes dx^N$, where $D\rho_{MN} \triangleq \rho_{MN;R} dx^R$, and D is the simple connection of (M, g) .

The absolute gradient of \mathbf{F}^0 on (M, g) is $\nabla\mathbf{F}^0 \triangleq \nabla\rho_{MN} \otimes dx^M \otimes dx^N$, where $\nabla\rho_{MN} \triangleq \rho_{MN;R} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^R}$.

Due to Proposition 3.3.4.1 , we directly obtain the following theorem.

Proposition 3.3.6.1. (General charge evolution theorem) The following relations are true on geometrical manifold (M, g) if and only if evolution direction field of ρ_{MN} is the gradient direction field $\nabla\rho_{MN}$.

$$\begin{cases} \rho_{MN;R} dx^R \simeq \rho_{MN;0} dx^0 & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \rho_{MN;R} dx^R \simeq \rho_{MN;0} dx^0 \\ \rho_{MN;R} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^R} \cong \rho_{MN;0} \frac{d}{dx^0} \end{array} \right. , & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \rho_{MN;R} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^R} \cong \rho_{MN;0} \frac{d}{dx^0} \\ \rho_{MN;R} dx^R \simeq \rho_{MN;0} dx^0 \end{array} \right. , \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

which are called **charge evolution equations**.

Definition 3.3.6.1. For more convenience, further abbreviate the notation ρ_{MN} to ρ .

- (1) Call $E^0 \triangleq \rho^{;0} \triangleq \rho^{;R}\varepsilon_R^0$ and $E_0 \triangleq \rho_{;0} \triangleq \rho_{;R}\varepsilon_0^R$ the **total energy** or **total mass** of ρ .
- (2) Call $p^R \triangleq \rho^{;R}$ and $p_R \triangleq \rho_{;R}$ the **momentum** of ρ .
- (3) Call $H^0 \triangleq \frac{d\rho}{dx_0}$ and $H_0 \triangleq \frac{d\rho}{dx^0}$ the **canonical energy** of ρ .
- (4) Call $P^R \triangleq \frac{\partial\rho}{\partial x_R}$ and $P_R \triangleq \frac{\partial\rho}{\partial x^R}$ the **canonical momentum** of ρ .
- (5) Call $V^0 \triangleq E^0 - H^0$ and $V_0 \triangleq E_0 - H_0$ the **potential energy** of interaction.
- (6) Call $V^R \triangleq p^R - P^R$ and $V_R \triangleq p_R - P_R$ the **momentum** of interaction.

Proposition 3.3.6.2. If and only if evolution direction of ρ evolving in g is the gradient direction $\nabla\rho$, equation

$$E_0 E^0 = p_R p^R$$

holds, which is called the **general energy-momentum equation** of ρ .

Proof. According to Proposition 3.3.6.1 , gradient direction is equivalent to

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} E_0 dx^0 \simeq p_R dx^R \\ E_0 \frac{d}{dx_0} \cong p_R \frac{\partial}{\partial x_R} \end{array} \right\}, \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} E^0 dx_0 \simeq p^R dx_R \\ E^0 \frac{d}{dx^0} \cong p^R \frac{\partial}{\partial x^R} \end{array} \right\}. \quad (13)$$

Then we obtain the directional derivative in gradient direction:

$$\left\langle E_0 \frac{d}{dx_0}, E_0 dx^0 \right\rangle = \left\langle p_R \frac{\partial}{\partial x_R}, p_M dx^M \right\rangle,$$

i.e. $G^{00} E_0 E_0 = G^{RM} p_R p_M$, or $E_0 E^0 = p_R p^R$. \square

Proposition 3.3.6.3. The following equations

$$p^R = E^0 \frac{dx^R}{dx^0}, \quad p_R = E_0 \frac{dx_R}{dx_0} \quad (14)$$

hold if and only if the evolution direction of ρ is the gradient direction $\nabla\rho$.

Proof. According to Proposition 3.3.6.1 , gradient direction is equivalent to $p^R \frac{\partial}{\partial x^R} \cong E^0 \frac{d}{dx^0}$ and $p_R \frac{\partial}{\partial x_R} \cong E_0 \frac{d}{dx_0}$. Then due to evolution lemma we immediately obtain $p^R = E^0 \frac{dx^R}{dx^0}$ and $p_R = E_0 \frac{dx_R}{dx_0}$. \square

Remark 3.3.6.1. In the gradient direction, the conclusion of this proposition is consistent with the traditional $p = mv$.

Definition 3.3.6.2. Let \mathbb{L} be the totality of paths from a to b . And suppose $L_\rho \in \mathbb{L}$, and the evolution parameter x^0 satisfies $t_a \triangleq x^0(a) < x^0(b) \triangleq t_b$. The functional

$$s_{\rho W}(L_\rho) \triangleq \int_{L_\rho} D\rho = \int_{L_\rho} p_R dx^R = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} E_0 dx^0$$

is called **general evolution quantity** of ρ .

Proposition 3.3.6.4. (Extreme value theorem of general evolution quantity) Suppose $\Gamma_{NP}^M \varepsilon_0^P = 0$, then L_ρ is the gradient line of ρ if and only if $\delta s_{\rho W}(L_\rho) = 0$.

Proof. Let the parameter equation of L_ρ be

$$x^R = x^R(x^0), \quad t_a \leq x^0 \leq t_b.$$

Let the parameter equation of $L_\rho + \delta L_\rho$ be

$$x^R = x^R(x^0) + \delta x^R(x^0), \quad t_a \leq x^0 \leq t_b, \quad \delta x^R(t_a) = \delta x^R(t_b) = 0.$$

Let the unit tangent vector on L_ρ at any x^0 be

$$X \triangleq \pi_* \left(\frac{d}{dx^0} \right) \triangleq \frac{dx^R}{dx^0} \Big|_{x^0} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^R} = \varepsilon_0^R(x^0) \frac{\partial}{\partial x^R}.$$

And let the unit tangent vector on $L_\rho + \delta L_\rho$ be

$$X + \delta X \triangleq \frac{d(x^R + \delta x^R)}{dx^0} \Big|_{x^0} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^R} = \left(\frac{dx^R}{dx^0} + \delta \frac{dx^R}{dx^0} \right) \Big|_{x^0} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^R} = \left(\varepsilon_0^R(x^0) + \delta \varepsilon_0^R(x^0) \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial x^R}.$$

Then consider the variation of $s_{\rho W}(L_\rho)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta s_{\rho W}(L_\rho) &= \Delta \int_{L_\rho} p_R \varepsilon_0^R dx^0 = \int_{L_\rho + \delta L_\rho} p_R \varepsilon_0^R dx^0 - \int_{L_\rho} p_R \varepsilon_0^R dx^0 \\ &= \int_{L_\rho + \delta L_\rho} \rho_{;R} \varepsilon_0^R dx^0 - \int_{L_\rho} \rho_{;R} \varepsilon_0^R dx^0 = \int_{L_\rho + \delta L_\rho} \langle X, D\rho \rangle dx^0 - \int_{L_\rho} \langle X, D\rho \rangle dx^0 \\ &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \langle X + \delta X, D\rho(x^R + \delta x^R) \rangle dx^0 - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \langle X, D\rho(x^R) \rangle dx^0 \\ &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left\langle X + \delta X, D\rho(x^R) + \frac{\partial D\rho(x^R)}{\partial x^M} \delta x^M + o(\delta x) \right\rangle dx^0 - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \langle X, D\rho(x^R) \rangle dx^0 \\ &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left(\langle X + \delta X, D\rho \rangle + \left\langle X + \delta X, \frac{\partial D\rho}{\partial x^M} \delta x^M \right\rangle \right) dx^0 - \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \langle X, D\rho \rangle dx^0 + o(\delta x) \\ &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \left(\langle \delta X, D\rho \rangle + \left\langle X, \frac{\partial D\rho}{\partial x^M} \delta x^M \right\rangle \right) dx^0 + o(\delta x) \\ &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} (\langle \delta X, D\rho \rangle + \langle X, \delta D\rho \rangle) dx^0 + o(\delta x) = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \langle \delta X, D\rho \rangle dx^0 + \delta \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \rho_{;0} dx^0 + o(\delta x), \end{aligned}$$

then due to $\Gamma_{NP}^M \varepsilon_0^P = 0$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta s_{\rho W}(L_\rho) &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \langle \delta X, D\rho \rangle dx^0 + \delta \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \frac{d\rho}{dx^0} dx^0 + o(\delta x) \\ &= \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \langle \delta X, D\rho \rangle dx^0 + o(\delta x). \end{aligned}$$

Thus we obtain

$$\delta s_{\rho W} = \int_{t_a}^{t_b} \langle \delta X, D\rho \rangle dx^0.$$

When $b \rightarrow a$, $\delta ds_{\rho W} = \langle \delta X, D\rho \rangle dx^0$. The directional derivative $\langle X, D\rho \rangle = \rho_{;0} \cos \theta$, where θ is the included angle between evolution direction X and the gradient direction. Then $\langle \delta X, D\rho \rangle = \rho_{;0} \delta \cos \theta = -\rho_{;0} \sin \theta \delta \theta$. Now

$$\delta ds_{\rho W} = -\rho_{;0} \sin \theta \delta \theta dx^0.$$

Hence, for general ρ , $\delta ds_{\rho W} = 0$ if and only if $\sin \theta = 0$, namely evolution direction at this point is exactly the gradient direction (take the positive direction without loss of generality).

Take integration from a to b , then $\delta \int_{t_a}^{t_b} ds_{\rho W} = 0$ if and only if evolution direction at each point of L_ρ is the gradient direction of ρ . In other words, $\delta s_{\rho W} = 0$ if and only if L_ρ is the gradient line of ρ . \square

Remark 3.3.6.2. In the Minkowski coordinate frame defined later, evolution parameter x^0 will be changed to \tilde{x}^τ , then there still exists a concept of gradient direction. Correspondingly, the evolution quantity $\int_{t_a}^{t_b} E_0 dx^0$ will present as $\int_{\tau_a}^{\tau_b} \tilde{m}_\tau d\tau$, where \tilde{m}_τ is rest-mass. Thus, the principle of least action will become a theorem, no longer as a principle.

3.3.7 Intrinsic geometrical treatment of conservation of energy-momentum

The most general abstract theory about conserved quantity is the Neother's theorem. However, it is not enough to just only content with abstract point of view. In consideration of that a conserved quantity is a geometrical property, we need to study its concrete construction in way of intrinsic geometry.

Definition 3.3.7.1. Denote

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\rho \Gamma_G] \triangleq \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x^G} - \rho_{;G} \triangleq \frac{\partial \rho_{MN}}{\partial x^G} - \rho_{MN;G} = \rho_{MH} \Gamma_{NG}^H + \rho_{HN} \Gamma_{MG}^H, \\ [\rho \Gamma_0] \triangleq \frac{d\rho}{dx^0} - \rho_{;0} \triangleq \frac{d\rho_{MN}}{dx^0} - \rho_{MN;0} = \rho_{MH} \Gamma_{N0}^H + \rho_{HN} \Gamma_{M0}^H. \end{array} \right. \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\rho \Gamma^Q] \triangleq G^{GQ} [\rho \Gamma_G], \\ [\rho \Gamma^0] \triangleq G^{00} [\rho \Gamma_0]. \end{array} \right.$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\rho B_{PQ}] \triangleq \rho_{MH} \left(\frac{\partial \Gamma_{NQ}^H}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{NP}^H}{\partial x^Q} \right) + \rho_{HN} \left(\frac{\partial \Gamma_{MQ}^H}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{MP}^H}{\partial x^Q} \right), \\ [\rho R_{PQ}] \triangleq \rho_{MH} R_{NPQ}^H + \rho_{HN} R_{MPQ}^H. \end{array} \right. \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\rho F_{PQ}] \triangleq \frac{\partial [\rho \Gamma_Q]}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial [\rho \Gamma_P]}{\partial x^Q}, \\ [\rho E_{PQ}] \triangleq [\rho \Gamma_Q]_{;P} - [\rho \Gamma_P]_{;Q}. \end{array} \right.$$

Proposition 3.3.7.1. The following two equations hold:

$$(1) [\rho F_{PQ}] = [\rho E_{PQ}];$$

$$(2) [\rho F_{PQ}] - [\rho B_{PQ}] = \left(\rho_{MH,P} \Gamma_{NQ}^H - \rho_{MH,Q} \Gamma_{NP}^H \right) + \left(\rho_{HN,P} \Gamma_{MQ}^H - \rho_{HN,Q} \Gamma_{MP}^H \right).$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} [\rho E_{PQ}] &= [\rho \Gamma_Q]_{;P} - [\rho \Gamma_P]_{;Q} = \left(\rho_{MH} \Gamma_{NQ}^H + \rho_{HN} \Gamma_{MQ}^H \right)_{;P} - \left(\rho_{MH} \Gamma_{NP}^H + \rho_{HN} \Gamma_{MP}^H \right)_{;Q} \\ &= \rho_{MH} \left(\Gamma_{NQ;P}^H - \Gamma_{NP;Q}^H \right) + \rho_{HN} \left(\Gamma_{MQ;P}^H - \Gamma_{MP;Q}^H \right) + \left(\rho_{MH;P} \Gamma_{NQ}^H - \rho_{MH;Q} \Gamma_{NP}^H \right) \\ &\quad + \left(\rho_{HN;P} \Gamma_{MQ}^H - \rho_{HN;Q} \Gamma_{MP}^H \right) \\ &= \rho_{MH} \left(\Gamma_{NQ;P}^H - \Gamma_{NP;Q}^H \right) + \rho_{HN} \left(\Gamma_{MQ;P}^H - \Gamma_{MP;Q}^H \right) + \left(\rho_{MH;P} \Gamma_{NQ}^H + \rho_{HN;P} \Gamma_{MQ}^H \right) \\ &\quad - \left(\rho_{MH;Q} \Gamma_{NP}^H + \rho_{HN;Q} \Gamma_{MP}^H \right) - \left(\rho_{MG} \Gamma_{HP}^G \Gamma_{NQ}^H - \rho_{MG} \Gamma_{HQ}^G \Gamma_{NP}^H \right) - \left(\rho_{GN} \Gamma_{HP}^G \Gamma_{MQ}^H - \rho_{GN} \Gamma_{HQ}^G \Gamma_{MP}^H \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \rho_{MH} \left(\Gamma_{NQ;P}^H - \Gamma_{NP;Q}^H \right) + \rho_{HN} \left(\Gamma_{MQ;P}^H - \Gamma_{MP;Q}^H \right) + \left(\rho_{MH,P} \Gamma_{NQ}^H + \rho_{HN,P} \Gamma_{MQ}^H \right) \\
&\quad - \left(\rho_{MH,Q} \Gamma_{NP}^H + \rho_{HN,Q} \Gamma_{MP}^H \right) - \left(\rho_{MH} \Gamma_{GP}^H \Gamma_{NQ}^G - \rho_{MH} \Gamma_{GQ}^H \Gamma_{NP}^G \right) - \left(\rho_{HN} \Gamma_{GP}^H \Gamma_{MQ}^G - \rho_{HN} \Gamma_{GQ}^H \Gamma_{MP}^G \right) \\
&= \left(\rho_{MH,P} \Gamma_{NQ}^H + \rho_{HN,P} \Gamma_{MQ}^H \right) - \left(\rho_{MH,Q} \Gamma_{NP}^H + \rho_{HN,Q} \Gamma_{MP}^H \right) \\
&\quad + \rho_{MH} \left(\Gamma_{NQ;P}^H - \Gamma_{NP;Q}^H + \Gamma_{GQ}^H \Gamma_{NP}^G - \Gamma_{GP}^H \Gamma_{NQ}^G \right) + \rho_{HN} \left(\Gamma_{MQ;P}^H - \Gamma_{MP;Q}^H + \Gamma_{GQ}^H \Gamma_{MP}^G - \Gamma_{GP}^H \Gamma_{MQ}^G \right) \\
&= \left(\rho_{MH,P} \Gamma_{NQ}^H - \rho_{MH,Q} \Gamma_{NP}^H \right) + \left(\rho_{HN,P} \Gamma_{MQ}^H - \rho_{HN,Q} \Gamma_{MP}^H \right) + \rho_{MH} \left(\frac{\partial \Gamma_{NQ}^H}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{NP}^H}{\partial x^Q} \right) \\
&\quad + \rho_{HN} \left(\frac{\partial \Gamma_{MQ}^H}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{MP}^H}{\partial x^Q} \right) \\
&= \left(\rho_{MH,P} \Gamma_{NQ}^H - \rho_{MH,Q} \Gamma_{NP}^H \right) + \left(\rho_{HN,P} \Gamma_{MQ}^H - \rho_{HN,Q} \Gamma_{MP}^H \right) + [\rho B_{PQ}] \\
&= \frac{\partial}{\partial x^P} \left(\rho_{MH} \Gamma_{NQ}^H + \rho_{HN} \Gamma_{MQ}^H \right) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x^Q} \left(\rho_{MH} \Gamma_{NP}^H + \rho_{HN} \Gamma_{MP}^H \right) \\
&= \frac{\partial [\rho \Gamma_Q]}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial [\rho \Gamma_P]}{\partial x^Q} = [\rho F_{PQ}].
\end{aligned}$$

□

Proposition 3.3.7.2. The following two equations hold:

$$\begin{aligned}
(1) \quad & \frac{\partial p_P}{\partial x^Q} - \frac{\partial p_Q}{\partial x^P} - [\rho F_{PQ}] = 0; \\
(2) \quad & \frac{dp_P}{dx^0} - \frac{\partial E_0}{\partial x^P} + p_Q \frac{\partial \varepsilon_0^Q}{\partial x^P} - [\rho F_{PQ}] \varepsilon_0^Q = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. According to Definition 3.3.6.1 ,

$$\frac{\partial P_P}{\partial x^Q} - \frac{\partial P_Q}{\partial x^P} = 0 \Leftrightarrow \frac{\partial p_P}{\partial x^Q} - \frac{\partial p_Q}{\partial x^P} + \frac{\partial [\rho \Gamma_P]}{\partial x^Q} - \frac{\partial [\rho \Gamma_Q]}{\partial x^P} = 0 \Leftrightarrow \frac{\partial p_P}{\partial x^Q} - \frac{\partial p_Q}{\partial x^P} - [\rho F_{PQ}] = 0.$$

According to Definition 3.3.1.2 , any evolution path L is defined on an orbit of φ_X . Therefore, φ_X can make the function $\varepsilon_0^Q|_L$ that is defined on L extend smoothly to a function ε_0^Q that is defined on M .

Now we consider $\pi^* \left(\frac{\partial p_P}{\partial x^Q} dx^Q - \frac{\partial p_Q}{\partial x^P} dx^P - [\rho F_{PQ}] dx^Q \right)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi^* : \frac{\partial p_P}{\partial x^Q} dx^Q &\mapsto \frac{\partial p_P}{\partial x^Q} \varepsilon_0^Q|_L dx^0 = \frac{dp_P}{dx^0} dx^0, \\
\pi^* : \frac{\partial p_Q}{\partial x^P} dx^P &\mapsto \frac{\partial p_Q}{\partial x^P} \varepsilon_0^Q|_L dx^0 = \frac{\partial (p_Q \varepsilon_0^Q)}{\partial x^P} dx^0 - p_Q \frac{\partial \varepsilon_0^Q}{\partial x^P} dx^0 = \frac{\partial E_0}{\partial x^P} dx^0 - p_Q \frac{\partial \varepsilon_0^Q}{\partial x^P} dx^0, \\
\pi^* : [\rho F_{PQ}] dx^Q &\mapsto [\rho F_{PQ}] \varepsilon_0^Q dx^0.
\end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\frac{dp_P}{dx^0} dx^0 - \frac{\partial E_0}{\partial x^P} dx^0 + p_Q \frac{\partial \varepsilon_0^Q}{\partial x^P} dx^0 - [\rho F_{PQ}] \varepsilon_0^Q dx^0 = 0,$$

finally

$$\frac{dp_P}{dx^0} - \frac{\partial E_0}{\partial x^P} + p_Q \frac{\partial \varepsilon_0^Q}{\partial x^P} - [\rho F_{PQ}] \varepsilon_0^Q = 0.$$

□

Proposition 3.3.7.3. With torsion-free connection, the following two equations hold:

$$\begin{aligned}
(1) \quad & p_{P;Q} - p_{Q;P} - [\rho B_{PQ}] = 0; \\
(2) \quad & p_{P;0} - E_{0;P} + p_Q \varepsilon_{0;P}^Q - [\rho B_{PQ}] \varepsilon_0^Q = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. According to Proposition 3.3.7.2 , $\frac{\partial p_P}{\partial x^Q} - \frac{\partial p_Q}{\partial x^P} - [\rho F_{PQ}] = 0$. Substitute equation (2) of Proposition 3.3.7.1 into this one, then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\partial p_P}{\partial x^Q} - \frac{\partial p_Q}{\partial x^P} - \left(\rho_{MH,P} \Gamma_{NQ}^H - \rho_{MH,Q} \Gamma_{NP}^H \right) - \left(\rho_{HN,P} \Gamma_{MQ}^H - \rho_{HN,Q} \Gamma_{MP}^H \right) = [\rho B_{PQ}] \\
\Leftrightarrow & \frac{\partial \rho_{MN;P}}{\partial x^Q} - \frac{\partial \rho_{MN;Q}}{\partial x^P} - \left(\rho_{MH,P} \Gamma_{NQ}^H - \rho_{MH,Q} \Gamma_{NP}^H \right) - \left(\rho_{HN,P} \Gamma_{MQ}^H - \rho_{HN,Q} \Gamma_{MP}^H \right) = [\rho B_{PQ}] \\
\Leftrightarrow & \left(\frac{\partial \rho_{MN;P}}{\partial x^Q} - \rho_{MH,P} \Gamma_{NQ}^H - \rho_{HN,P} \Gamma_{MQ}^H \right) - \left(\frac{\partial \rho_{MN;Q}}{\partial x^P} - \rho_{MH,Q} \Gamma_{NP}^H - \rho_{HN,Q} \Gamma_{MP}^H \right) = [\rho B_{PQ}] \\
\Leftrightarrow & \left(\frac{\partial \rho_{MN;P}}{\partial x^Q} - \rho_{MH,P} \Gamma_{NQ}^H - \rho_{HN,P} \Gamma_{MQ}^H - \rho_{MN;H} \Gamma_{PQ}^H \right) \\
& - \left(\frac{\partial \rho_{MN;Q}}{\partial x^P} - \rho_{MH,Q} \Gamma_{NP}^H - \rho_{HN,Q} \Gamma_{MP}^H - \rho_{MN;H} \Gamma_{QP}^H \right) + \rho_{MN;H} \left(\Gamma_{PQ}^H - \Gamma_{QP}^H \right) = [\rho B_{PQ}] \\
\Leftrightarrow & \rho_{MN;P;Q} - \rho_{MN;Q;P} = [\rho B_{PQ}] \\
\Leftrightarrow & p_{P;Q} - p_{Q;P} - [\rho B_{PQ}] = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Consider $\pi^* (p_{P;Q} dx^Q - p_{Q;P} dx^Q - [\rho B_{PQ}] dx^Q)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi^* : p_{P;Q} dx^Q & \mapsto p_{P;Q} \varepsilon_0^Q \Big|_L dx^0 = p_{P;0} dx^0, \\
\pi^* : p_{Q;P} dx^Q & \mapsto p_{Q;P} \varepsilon_0^Q \Big|_L dx^0 = \left((p_Q \varepsilon_0^Q)_{;P} - p_Q \varepsilon_{0;P}^Q \right) dx^0 = E_{0;P} dx^0 - p_Q \varepsilon_{0;P}^Q dx^0, \\
\pi^* : [\rho B_{PQ}] dx^Q & \mapsto [\rho B_{PQ}] \varepsilon_0^Q dx^0.
\end{aligned}$$

Then

$$p_{P;0} dx^0 - E_{0;P} dx^0 + p_Q \varepsilon_{0;P}^Q dx^0 - [\rho B_{PQ}] \varepsilon_0^Q dx^0 = 0,$$

finally

$$p_{P;0} - E_{0;P} + p_Q \varepsilon_{0;P}^Q - [\rho B_{PQ}] \varepsilon_0^Q = 0.$$

□

Proposition 3.3.7.4. With torsion-free connection, the following three equations hold:

- (1) $p_{P;Q} - p_{Q;P} - [\rho R_{PQ}] = 0$;
- (2) $p_{P;0} - E_{0;P} + p_Q \varepsilon_{0;P}^Q - [\rho R_{PQ}] \varepsilon_0^Q = 0$;
- (3) $[\rho B_{PQ}] = [\rho R_{PQ}]$.

Proof. The covariant derivatives of

$$p_P \triangleq \rho_{;P} \triangleq \rho_{MN;P} = \rho_{MN,P} - \rho_{MH} \Gamma_{NP}^H - \rho_{HN} \Gamma_{MP}^H$$

are

$$\begin{aligned}
p_{P;Q} &= \rho_{MN;P;Q} = \rho_{MN;P,Q} - \rho_{MH;P} \Gamma_{NQ}^H - \rho_{HN;P} \Gamma_{MQ}^H - \rho_{MN;H} \Gamma_{PQ}^H, \\
p_{Q;P} &= \rho_{MN;Q;P} = \rho_{MN;Q,P} - \rho_{MH;Q} \Gamma_{NP}^H - \rho_{HN;Q} \Gamma_{MP}^H - \rho_{MN;H} \Gamma_{QP}^H.
\end{aligned}$$

Subtract them:

$$\begin{aligned}
& p_{P;Q} - p_{Q;P} \\
&= (\rho_{MN;P,Q} - \rho_{MN;Q,P}) + (\rho_{MH;Q}\Gamma_{NP}^H - \rho_{MH;P}\Gamma_{NQ}^H) + (\rho_{HN;Q}\Gamma_{MP}^H - \rho_{HN;P}\Gamma_{MQ}^H) \\
&+ (\rho_{MN;H}\Gamma_{QP}^H - \rho_{MN;H}\Gamma_{PQ}^H) \\
&= (\rho_{MN;P,Q} - \rho_{MN;Q,P}) + (\rho_{MH;Q}\Gamma_{NP}^H - \rho_{MH;P}\Gamma_{NQ}^H) + (\rho_{HN;Q}\Gamma_{MP}^H - \rho_{HN;P}\Gamma_{MQ}^H) \\
&= (\rho_{MN,P} - \rho_{MH}\Gamma_{NP}^H - \rho_{HN}\Gamma_{MP}^H)_{,Q} - (\rho_{MN,Q} - \rho_{MH}\Gamma_{NQ}^H - \rho_{HN}\Gamma_{MQ}^H)_{,P} \\
&\quad + (\rho_{MH,Q} - \rho_{MG}\Gamma_{HQ}^G - \rho_{GH}\Gamma_{MQ}^G)\Gamma_{NP}^H - (\rho_{MH,P} - \rho_{MG}\Gamma_{HP}^G - \rho_{GH}\Gamma_{MP}^G)\Gamma_{NQ}^H \\
&\quad + (\rho_{HN,Q} - \rho_{HG}\Gamma_{NQ}^G - \rho_{GN}\Gamma_{HQ}^G)\Gamma_{MP}^H - (\rho_{HN,P} - \rho_{HG}\Gamma_{NP}^G - \rho_{GN}\Gamma_{HP}^G)\Gamma_{MQ}^H \\
&= \left((\rho_{MH}\Gamma_{NQ}^H)_{,P} + (\rho_{HN}\Gamma_{MQ}^H)_{,P} \right) - \left((\rho_{MH}\Gamma_{NP}^H)_{,Q} + (\rho_{HN}\Gamma_{MP}^H)_{,Q} \right) \\
&\quad + (\rho_{MH,Q} - \rho_{MG}\Gamma_{HQ}^G - \rho_{GH}\Gamma_{MQ}^G)\Gamma_{NP}^H - (\rho_{MH,P} - \rho_{MG}\Gamma_{HP}^G - \rho_{GH}\Gamma_{MP}^G)\Gamma_{NQ}^H \\
&\quad + (\rho_{HN,Q} - \rho_{HG}\Gamma_{NQ}^G - \rho_{GN}\Gamma_{HQ}^G)\Gamma_{MP}^H - (\rho_{HN,P} - \rho_{HG}\Gamma_{NP}^G - \rho_{GN}\Gamma_{HP}^G)\Gamma_{MQ}^H \\
&= (\rho_{MH}\Gamma_{NQ,P}^H + \rho_{HN}\Gamma_{MQ,P}^H) - (\rho_{MH}\Gamma_{NP,Q}^H + \rho_{HN}\Gamma_{MP,Q}^H) \\
&\quad + (-\rho_{MG}\Gamma_{HQ}^G\Gamma_{NP}^H - \rho_{GH}\Gamma_{MQ}^G\Gamma_{NP}^H) - (-\rho_{MG}\Gamma_{HP}^G\Gamma_{NQ}^H - \rho_{GH}\Gamma_{MP}^G\Gamma_{NQ}^H) \\
&\quad + (-\rho_{HG}\Gamma_{NQ}^G\Gamma_{MP}^H - \rho_{GN}\Gamma_{HQ}^G\Gamma_{MP}^H) - (-\rho_{HG}\Gamma_{NP}^G\Gamma_{MQ}^H - \rho_{GN}\Gamma_{HP}^G\Gamma_{MQ}^H) \\
&= \rho_{MH}(\Gamma_{NQ,P}^H - \Gamma_{NP,Q}^H + \Gamma_{GP}^H\Gamma_{NQ}^G - \Gamma_{GQ}^H\Gamma_{NP}^G) + \rho_{HN}(\Gamma_{MQ,P}^H - \Gamma_{MP,Q}^H + \Gamma_{GP}^H\Gamma_{MQ}^G - \Gamma_{GQ}^H\Gamma_{MP}^G) \\
&= \rho_{MH}R_{NPQ}^H + \rho_{HN}R_{MPQ}^H = [\rho R_{PQ}].
\end{aligned}$$

That is $p_{P;Q} - p_{Q;P} - [\rho R_{PQ}] = 0$. And compare it with equation (1) of Proposition 3.3.7.3, then $[\rho B_{PQ}] = [\rho R_{PQ}]$ is obtained. Finally, due to equation (2) of Proposition 3.3.7.3, $p_{P;0} - E_{0;P} + p_Q \varepsilon_{0;P}^Q - [\rho R_{PQ}] \varepsilon_0^Q = 0$ holds. \square

Definition 3.3.7.2. According to the above propositions, equations

$$\begin{cases} F_P \triangleq \frac{dp_P}{dx^0} = \frac{\partial E_0}{\partial x^P} - p_Q \frac{\partial \varepsilon_0^Q}{\partial x^P} + [\rho F_{PQ}] \varepsilon_0^Q, \\ f_P \triangleq p_{P;0} = E_{0;P} - p_Q \varepsilon_{0;P}^Q + [\rho R_{PQ}] \varepsilon_0^Q. \end{cases}$$

are called the **general Lorentz force equations**, and the intrinsic geometrical properties F_P and f_P are called **general forces** on ρ .

Proposition 3.3.7.5. Suppose there is a tensor Y_{MN} satisfies $Y_{MN}^{;M} = -G^{00}(E_{0;N} - p_Q \varepsilon_{0;N}^Q + [\rho R_{NQ}] \varepsilon_0^Q) - \varepsilon_M^0{}^{;M} p_N$, and let $W_{MN} \triangleq E_0 \varepsilon_M^0 \varepsilon_N^0$, then in gradient direction of ρ , intrinsic geometrical property $T_{MN} \triangleq W_{MN} + Y_{MN}$ satisfies

$$T_{MN}^{;M} = 0,$$

which can be called the **conservation of energy-momentum** of ρ .

Proof. According to Proposition 3.3.6.3, $E_0 \varepsilon_N^0 = p_N$ in gradient direction of ρ . Then

$$W_{MN}^{;M} = (\varepsilon_M^0 p_N)^{;M} = p_N^{;M} \varepsilon_M^0 + \varepsilon_M^0{}^{;M} p_N = p_N^{;0} + \varepsilon_M^0{}^{;M} p_N = -Y_{MN}^{;M},$$

Thus, $(W_{MN} + Y_{MN})^{;M} = 0$, that is $T_{MN}^{;M} = 0$. \square

3.3.8 Two dual descriptions of gradient direction field

Discussion 3.3.8.1. For any two non-vanishing smooth tangent vector fields X and Y on manifold M , let L_Y be the Lie derivative operator induced by the one-parameter group of diffeomorphisms φ_Y corresponding to Y . According to a well-known theorem [7], Lie derivative equation $[X, Y] = L_Y X$ holds.

On one hand, suppose H is the field of unit tangent vector in gradient directions of ρ , and φ_H is the one-parameter group of diffeomorphisms corresponding to H , and the parameter of φ_H is x^0 . The Lie derivative equation induced by φ_H is $[X, H] = L_H X$. Lie derivative operator L_H and tangent vector field $\frac{d}{dx^0}$ are both uniquely determined by H , so it can be denoted that $\frac{d}{dx^0} X \triangleq L_H X$. Thus, $[X, H] = L_H X$ becomes $[X, H] = \frac{d}{dx^0} X$.

On the other hand, the regular imbedding of path induces $H \cong H_L$. Then according to Proposition 3.3.2.1, for any smooth function f , equation $\langle H, df \rangle = \langle H_L, df_L \rangle$ holds. Notice that H_L and $\frac{d}{dx^0}$ are the same, hence we have $Hf = \frac{d}{dx^0} f_L$.

In a word, L_H and H_L are both uniquely determined by the gradient direction H . Due to the above discussion, we immediately obtain the following proposition.

Proposition 3.3.8.1. Let H be the field of unit tangent vector in gradient directions of ρ , for any X and any f , equations

$$[X, H] = \frac{d}{dx^0} X, \quad Hf = \frac{d}{dx^0} f_L \quad (15)$$

hold if and only if $\frac{d}{dx^0}$ is the field of unit tangent vector in gradient directions of ρ .

Definition 3.3.8.1. Equation $[X, H] = \frac{d}{dx^0} X$ is called the **general Heisenberg equation**. Equation $Hf = \frac{d}{dx^0} f_L$ is called the **general Schrödinger equation**.

Discussion 3.3.8.2. Both the two equations describe gradient direction field. H not only can be taken as the gradient direction determined by $D\rho$, but can also taken as the gradient direction of any other geometrical property.

According to Definition 3.3.4.1, gradient operator is a universal geometrical property of geometrical manifold, so these two equations remain unchanged under arbitrary transformation of reference-systems. These two equations reflect two descriptions of the same geometrical property by two mutually dual linear spaces, which are tangent bundle and cotangent bundle.

From real-valued evolution equations on tangent bundle and cotangent bundle, we can surely deduce complex-valued evolution equations on operator space and state space, such as section 5.6. What they describe is none other than gradient direction. It is true both for wave function and field function.

We can say that the value of gradient direction is determined by intrinsic geometry, and it is independent of either real-valued form or complex-valued form. The effectivenesses of describing intrinsic geometry with complex-valued form and real-valued form are the same. In a word, there is no need to be constrained on theoretical forms. Intrinsic geometry and gradient direction are the very essences which should be grasped.

The only necessity of using complex form is that it is the most convenient for describing the coherent superposition of propagator. However, it is a different problem from that of this section and it will be specifically discussed in the next section. In order to achieve the purpose of clarifying concepts, it is beneficial to separate the two equations here from the construction of coherent superposition of propagators of the next section.

3.4 Intrinsic geometrical treatment of propagator and wave function

Discussion 3.4.1. Intrinsic geometry relies on reference-system on manifold, hence:

(1) It is impossible for the coordinate of a single point to reflect the full picture of intrinsic geometrical shape of manifold.

(2) It is also impossible for a single gradient direction to reflect the full picture of intrinsic geometrical shape of manifold.

In order to describe the intrinsic geometrical shape of (M, g) , it is meaningful to study distribution of gradient directions of ρ on (M, g) . Intuitively:

(1) If g is trivial, the gradient direction field of ρ distributes uniformly on the flat (M, g) .

(2) If g is non-trivial, the intrinsic geometrical shape of (M, g) effects the distribution of gradient directions of ρ .

Definition 3.4.1. Let ρ be a geometrical property determined by f , then ρ is a universal geometrical property on (M, g) , and $H \triangleq \nabla\rho$ is a gradient direction field of ρ on (M, g) .

Let \mathfrak{T} be the totality of flat transformations defined in section 2.4. $\forall T \in \mathfrak{T}$, the flat transformation $T : f \mapsto Tf$ induces a transformation $T_* : \rho \mapsto T_*\rho$. Denote $H_T \triangleq \nabla(T_*\rho)$, $|\rho| \triangleq \{\rho_T \triangleq T_*\rho | T \in \mathfrak{T}\}$ and $|H| \triangleq \{H_T | T \in \mathfrak{T}\}$.

Let φ_H be the one-parameter group of diffeomorphisms corresponding to H , the parameter of which is x^0 . $\forall a \in M$, suppose $\varphi_{H,a}$ is the orbit through point a . Without loss of generality, let $a = \varphi_{H,a}(0)$. We say $\varphi_{|H|,a} \triangleq \{\varphi_{X,a} | X \in |H|\}$ is a **system of gradient lines** of $|\rho|$ through a . $\forall t \in \mathbb{R}^+$, we say $\varphi_{|H|,a}(t) \triangleq \{\varphi_{X,a}(t) | X \in |H|\}$ is the **evolution image** of a at $x^0 = t$.

$\forall \Omega \subseteq \mathfrak{T}$, $|H_\Omega| \triangleq \{H_T | T \in \Omega\}$ is a subset of $|H|$, and $\varphi_{|H_\Omega|,a} \triangleq \{\varphi_{X,a} | X \in |H_\Omega|\}$ is a subset of $\varphi_{|H|,a}$. Correspondingly, $\forall t \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $\varphi_{|H_\Omega|,a}(t) \triangleq \{\varphi_{H,a}(t) | X \in |X_\Omega|\}$ is a subset of $\varphi_{|H|,a}(t)$.

$\forall a \in M$, the restrictions of $|H|$ and $|H_\Omega|$ at a are denoted by $|H(a)| \triangleq \{H_T(a) | T \in \mathfrak{T}\}$ and $|H_\Omega(a)| \triangleq \{H_T(a) | T \in \Omega\}$, respectively.

Remark 3.4.1. When $t = 0$, intuitively, the gradient directions $|H(a)|$ of $|\rho|$ start from a and point to all directions around a uniformly. If (M, g) is not flat, when evolving to a certain time $t > 0$, the distribution of gradient directions on $\varphi_{|H|,a}(t)$ is no longer as uniform as they are around a . The following definition precisely characterizes such a distribution, which thereby reflect the intrinsic geometrical shape in a new approach.

Definition 3.4.2. (Evolution distribution). Let transformation $L_{g^{-1}}$ act on g , then we obtain the trivial $e \triangleq L_{g^{-1}}(g)$. Now (M, g) is sent to a flat (M, e) , and the gradient direction field $|H|$ of $|\rho|$ on (M, g) is sent to a gradient direction field $|O|$ of $|\rho|$ on (M, e) . Correspondingly, $\varphi_{|H|,a}(t)$ is

sent to $\varphi_{|O|,a}(t)$. In a word, $L_{g^{-1}}$ induces the following two maps:

$$g_*^{-1} : |H| \rightarrow |O|, \quad g_{**}^{-1} : \varphi_{|H|,a} \rightarrow \varphi_{|O|,a}.$$

$\forall |H_\Omega| \subseteq |H|$, denote $|O_\Omega| \triangleq g_*^{-1}(|H_\Omega|) \subseteq |O|$ and $\varphi_{|O_\Omega|,a} \triangleq g_{**}^{-1}(\varphi_{|H_\Omega|,a}) \subseteq \varphi_{|O|,a}$. Furthermore, $\forall t \in \mathbb{R}^+$, we say the measure $P(\varphi_{|O_\Omega|,a}(t)) = P(g_{**}^{-1}(\varphi_{|H_\Omega|,a}(t)))$ is the **distribution of gradient directions** of $|\rho|$ on $\varphi_{|H_\Omega|,a}(t)$, or the **evolution distribution** of $|\rho|$ at time $x^0 = t$ after starting from a in directions $|H_\Omega|$.

Due to $\mathfrak{T} \cong GL(\mathfrak{D}, \mathbb{R})$, let Ω be a certain neighborhood of T , with respect to the topology of $GL(\mathfrak{D}, \mathbb{R})$. Now at the starting point a , we say $|H_\Omega(a)|$ is a neighborhood of $H_T(a)$, and $|O_\Omega(a)| \triangleq g_*^{-1}(|H_\Omega(a)|)$ is a neighborhood of $O_T(a) \triangleq g_*^{-1}(H_T(a))$.

When Ω is sufficiently small, $|H_\Omega(a)|$ and $|O_\Omega(a)|$ are both sufficiently small, and $\forall t \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $\varphi_{|H_\Omega|,a}(t)$ and $\varphi_{|O_\Omega|,a}(t)$ are also sufficiently small. Concretely, when $\Omega \rightarrow T$, $H_T = \lim_{\Omega \rightarrow T} |H_\Omega|$, $H_T(a) = \lim_{\Omega \rightarrow T} |H_\Omega(a)|$, and the evolution image $\varphi_{|H_\Omega|,a}(t)$ of a at t will approach to a point $b_T \triangleq \varphi_{H_T,a}(t) = \lim_{|H_\Omega(a)| \rightarrow H_T(a)} \varphi_{|H_\Omega|,a}(t)$.

The limit

$$w_a(b_T) \triangleq \frac{dV_{O_T}}{dV_{H_T}} \triangleq \lim_{\Omega \rightarrow T} \frac{P(\varphi_{|O_\Omega|,a}(t))}{P(\varphi_{|H_\Omega|,a}(t))} = \lim_{\Omega \rightarrow T} \frac{P(g_{**}^{-1}(\varphi_{|H_\Omega|,a}(t)))}{P(\varphi_{|H_\Omega|,a}(t))} \quad (16)$$

is called the **distribution density of gradient directions** at time $x^0 = t$ after starting from a in direction H_T , or **distribution density of evolution**.

Remark 3.4.2. Radon-Nikodym theorem [54] guarantees the existence of such a limit. And evidently such a distribution density is an intrinsic geometrical property of (M, g) .

For any two points a and b on manifold M , it anyway makes sense to discuss the gradient line of $|\rho|$ from a to b . It is because even if the gradient line of ρ starting from a does not pass through b , it just only needs to carry out a certain flat transformation T defined in section 2.4 to obtain a $\rho' \triangleq T_*\rho$ so that the gradient line of ρ' starting from a can just exactly pass through b . Intuitively, when $|\rho|$ takes two different initial directions of motion, $|\rho|$ presents as ρ and ρ' , respectively.

Definition 3.4.3. (Evolutor) $\forall a, b \in M$, if $\exists \rho' \in |\rho|$ such that a and b are both on the gradient line $L(b, a)$ of ρ' , then we say $L(b, a)$ is a gradient line of $|\rho|$.

According to Definition 3.3.6.2, let $s_L(b, a)$ be the evolution quantity on $L(b, a)$. Denote $r_L(b, a) \triangleq \sqrt{w_a(b)}$, $R_L(b, a) \triangleq r_L(b, a)e^{is_L(b, a)}$, which are both intrinsic geometrical properties of (M, g) . We say $R_L(b, a)$ is the **evolutor** of $|\rho|$ on $L(b, a)$.

Definition 3.4.4. (Propagator) Let $\mathfrak{L}(b, a)$ be the totality of gradient lines of $|\rho|$ from a to b . $\forall L(b, a) \in \mathfrak{L}(b, a)$, let $R_L(b, a)$ be the evolutor of $|\rho|$ on $L(b, a)$. The intrinsic geometrical property

$$K(b, a) \triangleq \sum_{L \in \mathfrak{L}(b, a)} R_L(b, a) \quad (17)$$

is called the **propagator** of $|\rho|$ from a to b .

Remark 3.4.3. Abstractly, propagator is defined as the Green function of evolution equation. Concretely, propagator still needs a constructive definition. One method is to construct with

Feynman path integral [22] $\int_{x_a}^{x_b} e^{iS} \mathcal{D}x(t)$, which is expressed in form of functional integral. However, until now the functional integral has strict definition just in some special cases, but the strict definition in general case is still an unsolved problem.

Definition 3.4.4 reduces the scope of summation to the totality of gradient lines from a to b . If (M, g) is flat, $|\rho|$ has a unique gradient line from a to b , but it is not unique for general (M, g) .

Remark 3.4.4. As the simplest example, consider the propagator of free particle.

In this case (M, g) is flat. In sense of Remark 3.4.1, the system of gradient lines of $|\rho|$ starting from a spreads uniformly in all directions around a . No matter where b is, $w_a(b)$ is identically equal to 1. Then for a fixed b , the evolutor on gradient line $L(b, a)$ is $R_L(b, a) = r_L(b, a)e^{is_L(b, a)} = \sqrt{w_a(b)}e^{is_L(b, a)} = e^{is_L(b, a)}$. Because there is only one element in $\mathcal{L}(b, a)$, the propagator is $K(b, a) = R_L(b, a) = e^{is_L(b, a)}$. Of course, if normalizing on wavefront, there would be a coefficient of normalization.

Definition 3.4.5. (Wave function). Let a be a point on geometrical manifold (M, g) . $\forall a_0 \in M$, $d(a, a_0)$ is the geodesic distance between a_0 and a . Denote $\Sigma_a(a_0) \triangleq \{q \in M | d(a, q) = d(a, a_0)\}$. If function $\psi : M \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ satisfies both the following two conditions, then ψ is called a **wave function** of $|\rho|$ on (M, g) .

- (1) $\exists r > 0$ such that $\lim_{d(a, a_0) \rightarrow r} \psi(a_0) = 0$, or $\lim_{d(a, a_0) \rightarrow \infty} \psi(a_0) = 0$.
 (2) $\forall a_0, a \in M$,

$$\psi(a) = \int_{\Sigma_a(a_0)} K(a, q) \psi(q) d\sigma_q.$$

Remark 3.4.5. The propagator $K(a, q)$ is an intrinsic geometrical property of (M, g) , so the above defined wave function ψ is also an intrinsic geometrical property of (M, g) .

3.5 Summary of this section

1. This section proposes an intrinsic geometrical solution for Hilbert's 6th problem at the most basic level, that is, starting from an axiom, based on intrinsic geometry, the theoretical framework at the most basic level of physics is deduced in sense of pure mathematics.

2. Postulates that have a status as principle in physics are theorems that hold automatically in intrinsic geometry, such as Yang-Mills field equation, Lorentz force equation, energy-momentum equation, conservation law of energy-momentum, gravitational field equation(see Discussion 5.4.4), least action principle, Schrödinger equation, Heisenberg equation, Dirac equation(see section 5.6), etc., which in intrinsic geometry are no longer necessary to be regarded as principles and postulates.

In addition, this section adopts general coordinate form, the evolution parameter of which is x^0 . In section 5.2, the Minkowski coordinate will be constructed, the evolution parameter of which is x^τ . It has to be emphasized that no matter what coordinate forms are adopted, their geometrical essences are the same. Intrinsic geometrical properties in some special cases will be discussed in the following sections.

4 Intrinsic geometrical treatment of inversion transformation

In this section, indices of internal and external space are taken values according to Definition 5.1.1 .

Definition 4.1. Let the local coordinate representation of reference-system k be $x'^j = -\delta_i^j x^i$, $x'^m = \delta_m^n x^m$, then we say $P \triangleq L_{[k]} : x^i \rightarrow -x^i, x^m \rightarrow x^m$ is **parity inversion**. Let the local coordinate representation of reference-system h be $x'^j = \delta_i^j x^i$, $x'^n = -\delta_m^n x^m$, then we say $C \triangleq L_{[h]} : x^i \rightarrow x^i, x^m \rightarrow -x^m$ is **charge conjugate inversion**. In addition, denote $T_0 : x^0 \rightarrow -x^0$, which is called **time coordinate inversion**.

Their composition $CPT_0 : x^Q \rightarrow -x^Q, x^0 \rightarrow -x^0$ is called **total inversion of coordinates**.

Definition 4.2. Reviewing Definition 3.2.1 , without loss of generality, positive or negative sign of metric, which marks two opposite directions of evolution, is independent of positive or negative sign of coordinate. Let N be a closed submanifold of M , and its metric be $dx^{(N)}$. The transformation $T_0^{(N)} : dx^{(N)} \rightarrow -dx^{(N)}$ is called a **single inversion of space metric** on N . Specially, when $N = M$, $T_0^{(M)} : dx^0 \rightarrow -dx^0$ is called a **single inversion of time metric**.

Denote the totality of closed submanifolds of M by $\mathfrak{B}(M)$, and denote $T^{(M)} \triangleq \prod_{B \in \mathfrak{B}(M)} T_0^{(B)}$. We say $T^{(M)}$ is **total inversion of metrics**.

Definition 4.3. $T \triangleq T^{(M)}T_0$ is called **time inversion**. The joint transformation of total inversion of coordinates CPT_0 and total inversion of metrics $T^{(M)}$ is called **space-time inversion**, that is $CPT_0T^{(M)} = CPT$.

Remark 4.1. Summarize the above definitions, then we have:

$$\begin{aligned} CPT_0 : x^Q &\rightarrow -x^Q, x^0 \rightarrow -x^0, dx^Q \rightarrow dx^Q, dx^0 \rightarrow dx^0, \\ T^{(M)} : x^Q &\rightarrow x^Q, x^0 \rightarrow x^0, dx^Q \rightarrow -dx^Q, dx^0 \rightarrow -dx^0, \\ CPT : x^Q &\rightarrow -x^Q, x^0 \rightarrow -x^0, dx^Q \rightarrow -dx^Q, dx^0 \rightarrow -dx^0. \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 4.1. Consider CPT on g . Denote $s \triangleq \int_L D\rho$, and $D_P e^{is} \triangleq \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x^P} + i[\rho\Gamma_P] \right) e^{is}$, then:

(1) $CPT : D\rho \rightarrow D\rho$, (2) $CPT : D_P e^{is} \rightarrow -D_P e^{is}$.

Proof. (1) On one hand, for $CP : x^R \rightarrow -x^R$ we have $CP : \frac{\partial}{\partial x^R} \rightarrow -\frac{\partial}{\partial x^R}$. According to the definition of simple connection we obtain $CP : \Gamma_{NP}^M \rightarrow -\Gamma_{NP}^M$. In consideration of that ρ is determined by f , so ρ is required to remain unchanged under transformations of g .

Due to $p_R \triangleq \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x^R} + [\rho\Gamma_P]$ we know $CP : p_R \rightarrow -p_R$. On the other hand, according to the definition of T we immediately obtain $T : dx^R \rightarrow -dx^R$. In summary, we have $CPT : p_R dx^R \rightarrow (-p_R)(-dx^R)$, that is $CPT : D\rho \rightarrow D\rho$.

(2) On one hand, in consideration of $CP : \frac{\partial}{\partial x^P} + i[\rho\Gamma_P] \rightarrow -\frac{\partial}{\partial x^P} - i[\rho\Gamma_P]$, and due to $s \triangleq \int_L D\rho = \int_L p_R dx^R$ we know $CP : s \rightarrow -s$, hence $CP : \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x^P} + i[\rho\Gamma_P] \right) e^{is} \rightarrow \left(-\frac{\partial}{\partial x^P} - i[\rho\Gamma_P] \right) e^{-is}$, that is $CP : D_P e^{is} \rightarrow -D_P e^{-is}$. On the other hand, $\frac{\partial}{\partial x^P} + i[\rho\Gamma_P]$ and p_R are both independent of metrics, therefore $\frac{\partial}{\partial x^P} + i[\rho\Gamma_P]$ and p_R both remain unchanged under transformation T . Due to $T : dx^R \rightarrow -dx^R$, then $T : p_R dx^R \rightarrow -p_R dx^R$, that is

$T : D\rho \rightarrow -D\rho$, hence $T : s \rightarrow -s$. Moreover, $T : D_P e^{is} \rightarrow D_P e^{-is} = D_P (e^{is})^*$. In summary, we have $CPT : D_P e^{is} \rightarrow -D_P (e^{-is})^* = -D_P e^{is}$. \square

Remark 4.2. The above proposition gives the intrinsic geometrical origin of CPT invariance. In addition, in physics there is a complex conjugation in time inversion about wave function $T : \psi(x, t) \rightarrow \psi^*(x, -t)$, the mathematical origin of which can essentially be attributed to Definition 4.1, Definition 4.2 and Definition 4.3. In fact we have the following proposition, where the coordinate \tilde{x}^μ is Minkowski coordinate defined in section 5.2 such that $\tilde{x}^i = x^i$, $\tilde{x}^0 = x^0$, and Minkowski metric satisfies $(d\tilde{x}^\tau)^2 = (d\tilde{x}^0)^2 - \sum_i (d\tilde{x}^i)^2$, $\tilde{m}_\tau \triangleq \tilde{\rho}_{;\tau}$.

Proposition 4.2. Denote $S \triangleq \int_L \tilde{m}_\tau d\tilde{x}^\tau$ and $\psi(\tilde{x}^i, \tilde{x}^0) \triangleq f(\tilde{x}^i, \tilde{x}^0) e^{iS}$, then $T : \psi(\tilde{x}^i, \tilde{x}^0) \rightarrow \psi^*(\tilde{x}^i, -\tilde{x}^0)$.

Proof. According to Definition 4.3 we know $T : \tilde{m}_\tau \rightarrow \tilde{m}_\tau$, $d\tilde{x}^\tau \rightarrow -d\tilde{x}^\tau$, $\tilde{x}^0 \rightarrow -\tilde{x}^0$, therefore $T : \tilde{m}_\tau d\tilde{x}^\tau \rightarrow -\tilde{m}_\tau d\tilde{x}^\tau$, then $T : S \rightarrow -S$, $f(\tilde{x}^i, \tilde{x}^0) \rightarrow f(\tilde{x}^i, -\tilde{x}^0)$, and furthermore $T : f(\tilde{x}^i, \tilde{x}^0) e^{iS} \rightarrow f(\tilde{x}^i, -\tilde{x}^0) e^{-iS}$, that is $T : \psi(\tilde{x}^i, \tilde{x}^0) \rightarrow \psi^*(\tilde{x}^i, -\tilde{x}^0)$. \square

5 Intrinsic geometrical treatment of classical spacetime

5.1 Existence and uniqueness of submanifold with classical spacetime

Definition 5.1.1. Suppose $M = P \times N$, $\mathcal{D} \triangleq \dim M$ and $r \triangleq \dim P = 3$. According to Definition 3.2.2, we have a submanifold of external space P and a submanifold of internal space N . P inherits coordinate $\{\xi^s\}\{x^i\}$ from M , and N inherits coordinate $\{\xi^a\}\{x^m\}$ from M . The values of indices are specified as follows.

(1) Total indices of basis coordinate frame ξ are $A, B, C, D = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{D}$. Total indices of performance coordinate frame x are $M, N, P, Q = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{D}$.

(2) External indices of ξ are $s, t, u, v = 1, 2, \dots, r$. Internal indices of ξ are $a, b, c, d = r + 1, r + 2, \dots, \mathcal{D}$.

(3) External indices of x are $i, j, k, l = 1, 2, \dots, r$. Internal indices of x are $m, n, p, q = r + 1, r + 2, \dots, \mathcal{D}$.

(4) Regular indices of ξ are $S, T, U, V = 1, 2, \dots, r, \tau$. Minkowski indices of ξ are $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta = 0, 1, 2, \dots, r$.

(5) Regular indices of x are $I, J, K, L = 1, 2, \dots, r, \tau$. Minkowski indices of x are $\mu, \nu, \rho, \sigma = 0, 1, 2, \dots, r$.

Definition 5.1.2. Let there be a smooth tangent vector field X on (M, f) . If $\forall p \in M$, $X(p) = b^A \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^A} \Big|_p = c^M \frac{\partial}{\partial x^M} \Big|_p$ satisfies that b^a are not all zero and c^m are not all zero, then we say X is **internal-directed**.

Proposition 5.1.1. Suppose $M = P \times N$ and X is a smooth tangent vector field on M . Fix a point $o \in M$. If X is internal-directed, then:

(1) There exist a unique $(r + 1)$ -dimensional regular submanifold $\gamma : \tilde{M} \rightarrow M$, $p \mapsto p$ and a unique smooth tangent vector field \tilde{X} on \tilde{M} such that: (i) $P \times \{o\}$ is a closed submanifold of

\tilde{M} , (ii) tangent map $\gamma_* : T(\tilde{M}) \rightarrow T(M)$ satisfies that $\forall q \in \tilde{M}$, $\gamma_* : \tilde{X}(q) \mapsto X(q)$. Such an \tilde{M} is called a **submanifold with classical spacetime** determined by X through o .

(2) Let φ_X be the one-parameter group of diffeomorphisms on M corresponding to X , and $\varphi_{\tilde{X}}$ the one-parameter group of diffeomorphisms on \tilde{M} corresponding to \tilde{X} . Thus, we have $\varphi_{\tilde{X}} = \varphi_X|_{\tilde{M}}$.

Proof. Step 1: construction of \tilde{M} . We can define a closed submanifold $P \times \{o\}$ on M through o via parameter equation $x^m = x_o^m$. Then let $\varphi_X : M \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow M$ be the one-parameter group of diffeomorphisms corresponding to X . Restrict φ_X to $P \times \{o\}$ and we obtain

$$\varphi_X|_{P \times \{o\}} : P \times \{o\} \times \{t\} \mapsto P' \times \{o'\},$$

where points o and o' are on the same orbit $L_o \triangleq \varphi_{X,o}$. $P \times \{o\}$ and $P' \times \{o'\}$ are both homeomorphic to P . If we do not distinguish P and P' , we have

$$\varphi_X|_{P \times \{o\}} : P \times \{o\} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow P \times L_o.$$

Then consider all of such $\{o\}$ on the entire orbit L_o , and we obtain a map

$$\varphi_X|_{P \times L_o} : P \times L_o \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow P \times L_o.$$

Denote $\tilde{M} \triangleq P \times L_o$, then

$$\varphi_X|_{\tilde{M}} : \tilde{M} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \tilde{M}$$

constitutes a one-parameter group of diffeomorphisms on \tilde{M} .

Step 2: constructions of $\gamma : \tilde{M} \rightarrow M$ and \tilde{X} . Because X is internal-directed, the restriction of X to $L_o \triangleq \varphi_{X,o} : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow M$ is non-vanishing everywhere and L_o is an injection. The image set of L_o can also be denoted by L_o . $\forall t \in \mathbb{R}$, $q \triangleq \varphi_{X,o}(t) \in L_o$, we can define a closed submanifold N_q on M through q via parameter equation $x^i = x_q^i$, and N_q is homeomorphic to N . Due to the one-to-one correspondence between q and N_q , $L_o \rightarrow N$ is a regular imbedding. Furthermore:

(1) $\gamma : P \times L_o \rightarrow P \times N$ is a regular imbedding, that is, $\gamma : \tilde{M} \rightarrow M$. Hence the tangent map $\gamma_* : T(\tilde{M}) \rightarrow T(M)$ is an injection. Therefore, the smooth tangent vector \tilde{X} which satisfies $\forall q \in \tilde{M}$, $\gamma_* : \tilde{X}(q) \mapsto X(q)$ is uniquely defined by X via γ_*^{-1} .

(2) We notice that $o \in \tilde{M}$, hence $L_o \triangleq \varphi_{X,o}$ is an orbit of $\varphi_X|_{\tilde{M}}$. In consideration of that L_o uniquely determines γ , and γ uniquely determines γ_* , and γ_*^{-1} uniquely determines \tilde{X} , so finally \tilde{X} is uniquely determined by $\varphi_X|_{\tilde{M}}$. Thus, we have $\varphi_{\tilde{X}} = \varphi_X|_{\tilde{M}}$.

In summary of (1) and (2), it also indicates that \tilde{M} is determined by X , therefore it is unique. \square

Remark 5.1.1. (1) \tilde{M} is not independent of M , but determined by smooth tangent vector field X on M .

(2) \tilde{M} is a regular submanifold of M , so not all intrinsic geometrical properties of M can be inherited by \tilde{M} .

(3) The correspondence between \tilde{X} and the restriction of X to \tilde{M} is one-to-one. For convenience, we later will not distinguish the notations X and \tilde{X} on \tilde{M} , but uniformly denote them by X .

(4) An arbitrary path $\tilde{L} : T \rightarrow \tilde{M}, t \mapsto p$ on \tilde{M} uniquely corresponds to a path $L \triangleq \gamma \circ \tilde{L} : T \rightarrow M, t \mapsto p$ on M . Evidently the image sets of L and \tilde{L} are the same, that is, $L(T) = \tilde{L}(T)$. For convenience, we later will not distinguish the notations L and \tilde{L} on \tilde{M} , but uniformly denote them by L .

5.2 Intrinsic geometrical treatment of gravitational field

Proposition 5.2.1. Let \tilde{M} be the submanifold with classical spacetime determined by X on (M, f) , and L be a path on an orbit of $\varphi_{\tilde{X}}$ of \tilde{M} . $\forall p \in L$, suppose on neighborhood U that

$$f(p) : \xi^A = \xi^A(x^M) = \xi^A(x^0), \quad \xi^0 = \xi^0(x^0).$$

Thus: (1) There exists a unique local reference-system $\tilde{f}(p)$ on $\tilde{U} \triangleq U \cap \tilde{M}$ such that

$$\tilde{f}(p) : \xi^U = \xi^U(x^K) = \xi^U(x^0), \quad \xi^0 = \xi^0(x^0)$$

$$\text{and } (dx^\tau)^2 = \sum_{m=r+1}^{\mathfrak{D}} (dx^m)^2, \quad (d\xi^\tau)^2 = \sum_{a=r+1}^{\mathfrak{D}} (d\xi^a)^2.$$

(2) The above coordinate frames (\tilde{U}, ξ^U) and (\tilde{U}, x^K) of $\tilde{f}(p)$ uniquely determine coordinate frames $(\tilde{U}, \tilde{\xi}^\alpha)$ and $(\tilde{U}, \tilde{x}^\mu)$, such that

$$\tilde{f}(p) : \tilde{\xi}^\alpha = \tilde{\xi}^\alpha(\tilde{x}^\mu) = \tilde{\xi}^\alpha(\tilde{x}^\tau), \quad \tilde{\xi}^\tau = \tilde{\xi}^\tau(\tilde{x}^\tau)$$

and coordinates $\tilde{\xi}^s = \xi^s, \tilde{\xi}^\tau = \xi^\tau, \tilde{\xi}^0 = \xi^0, \tilde{x}^i = x^i, \tilde{x}^\tau = x^\tau, \tilde{x}^0 = x^0$.

Proof. (1) According to the proof of previous proposition, if L is on an orbit of $\varphi_{\tilde{X}}$, L is a regular submanifold of N . Let the metrics on N be $(dx^\tau)^2 = \sum_{m=r+1}^{\mathfrak{D}} (dx^m)^2$ and $(d\xi^\tau)^2 = \sum_{a=r+1}^{\mathfrak{D}} (d\xi^a)^2$. Review Definition 3.3.1.3 and we know the regular imbedding $\pi : L \rightarrow N, q \mapsto q$ induces parameter equations $x^m = x_\tau^m(x^\tau)$ and $\xi^a = \xi_\tau^a(\xi^\tau)$ of L . Then substitute them into $f(p)$ and we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \xi^A = \xi^A(x^M) = \xi^A(x^0) &\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \xi^u = \xi^u(x^k, x_\tau^m(x^\tau)) = \xi_L^u(x^0) \\ \xi_\tau^a(\xi^\tau) = \xi^a(x^k, x_\tau^m(x^\tau)) = \xi_L^a(x^0) \end{cases} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \xi^u = \xi^u(x^k, x_\tau^m(x^\tau)) = \xi_L^u(x^0) \\ \xi^\tau = (\xi_\tau^a)^{-1} \circ \xi^a(x^k, x_\tau^m(x^\tau)) = (\xi_\tau^a)^{-1} \circ \xi_L^a(x^0) \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \xi^u = \xi^u(x^k, x^\tau) = \xi_L^u(x^0) \\ \xi^\tau = \xi^\tau(x^k, x^\tau) = \xi_L^\tau(x^0) \end{cases} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \xi^U = \xi^U(x^K) = \xi_L^U(x^0), \quad \text{abbreviated to } \xi^U = \xi^U(x^K) = \xi^U(x^0). \end{aligned}$$

(2) As same as the above, we also obtain $x^K = x^K(\xi^U) = x^K(\xi^0)$. The relation between two parameters x^0 and x^τ of L can be expressed as $x^\tau = x_L^\tau(\xi^0(x^0))$, and the relation between two parameters ξ^0 and ξ^τ can be expressed as $\xi^\tau = \xi_L^\tau(x^0(\xi^0))$. Substitute them into $\tilde{f}(p)$, then

$$\xi^U = \xi^U(x^K) = \xi^U(x^0) \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \xi^u = \xi^u(x^k, x_L^\tau(\xi^0(x^0))) = \xi_L^u(x^0((x_L^\tau)^{-1}(x^\tau))) \\ \xi_L^\tau(x^0(\xi^0)) = \xi^\tau(x^k, x_L^\tau(\xi^0(x^0))) = \xi_L^\tau(x^0((x_L^\tau)^{-1}(x^\tau))) \\ \xi^0((\xi_L^\tau)^{-1}(\xi^\tau)) = (x_L^\tau)^{-1}(x^\tau) \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \xi^u = \xi^u(x^k, x_L^\tau(\xi^0(x^0))) = \xi_L^u(x^0((x_L^\tau)^{-1}(x^\tau))) \\ \xi^0 = \xi^0((\xi_L^\tau)^{-1}(\xi^\tau(x^k, x_L^\tau(\xi^0(x^0)))) = (x_L^\tau)^{-1}(x^\tau), \text{ abbreviated to } \\ \xi^\tau = \xi_L^\tau(x^0((x_L^\tau)^{-1}(x^\tau))) \end{cases} \begin{cases} \xi^u = \tilde{\xi}^u(x^k, x^0) = \tilde{\xi}_L^u(x^\tau) \\ \xi^0 = \tilde{\xi}^0(x^k, x^0) = \tilde{\xi}_L^0(x^\tau) \\ \xi^\tau = \tilde{\xi}^\tau(x^\tau) \end{cases} .$$

Denote $\tilde{\xi}^s \triangleq \xi^s$, $\tilde{\xi}^\tau \triangleq \xi^\tau$, $\tilde{\xi}^0 \triangleq \xi^0$, $\tilde{x}^i \triangleq x^i$, $\tilde{x}^\tau \triangleq x^\tau$, $\tilde{x}^0 \triangleq x^0$, hence we have $\tilde{\xi}^\alpha = \tilde{\xi}^\alpha(\tilde{x}^\mu) = \tilde{\xi}_L^\alpha(\tilde{x}^\tau)$, $\tilde{\xi}^\tau = \tilde{\xi}^\tau(\tilde{x}^\tau)$, abbreviated to $\tilde{\xi}^\alpha = \tilde{\xi}^\alpha(\tilde{x}^\mu) = \tilde{\xi}^\alpha(\tilde{x}^\tau)$, $\tilde{\xi}^\tau = \tilde{\xi}^\tau(\tilde{x}^\tau)$. \square

Definition 5.2.1. \tilde{f} is called a **classical spacetime reference-system** on \tilde{M} , and (\tilde{M}, \tilde{f}) is called a **gravitational manifold**. (\tilde{U}, ξ^U) and (\tilde{U}, x^K) are called **regular coordinate frames** on (\tilde{M}, \tilde{f}) , meanwhile $(\tilde{U}, \tilde{\xi}^\alpha)$ and $(\tilde{U}, \tilde{x}^\mu)$ are called **Minkowski coordinate frames** on (\tilde{M}, \tilde{f}) .

Remark 5.2.1. \tilde{f} is uniquely determined by f , and \tilde{f} encapsulates the internal space of f . Although (\tilde{M}, \tilde{f}) can reflect intrinsic geometrical properties of external space of (M, f) , it cannot totally reflect intrinsic geometrical properties of internal space of (M, f) . There is a further illustration in Discussion 5.4.2 .

In addition, \tilde{f} presents locally as $\tilde{f}(p)$, so the mathematical origin of the principle of equivalence has been able to be attributed to Definition 2.1.2 , Definition 2.2.2 and Definition 5.2.1 . Of course its physical connotation can only be endowed by the fundamental axiom of section 3.1 . Besides, with respect to the gravitational field equation, see Discussion 5.4.4 .

It is well-known that there is no logically strict definition of inertial system in physics. However, now we can give a strict definition to inertial system from the perspective of intrinsic geometry. It is a reference-system, not a coordinate frame.

Definition 5.2.2. Suppose we have a geometrical manifold (\tilde{M}, \tilde{g}) . $F_{\tilde{g}}$ is a transformation induced by \tilde{g} .

(1) According to Discussion 5.3.2 , if $d\tilde{\zeta}^\tau = d\tilde{x}^\tau$, then we must have $\tilde{G}_{\mu\nu} = \tilde{\Delta}_{\alpha\beta} \tilde{B}_\mu^\alpha \tilde{B}_\nu^\beta = \tilde{E}_{\mu\nu}$. Thus, we say \tilde{g} is **orthogonal**, $F_{\tilde{g}}$ is an **orthogonal transformation**, and (\tilde{M}, \tilde{g}) is an **isotropic spacetime**. For convenience, $d\tilde{\zeta}^\tau$ and $d\tilde{x}^\tau$ are uniformly denoted by $d\tau$.

(2) If the slack-tights \tilde{B}_μ^α and \tilde{C}_α^μ of \tilde{g} are constants on \tilde{M} , then we say \tilde{g} is **flat**, $F_{\tilde{g}}$ is a **flat transformations**, and (\tilde{M}, \tilde{g}) is a **flat spacetime**.

(3) If \tilde{g} is both orthogonal and flat, then we say \tilde{g} is an **inertial-system**, $F_{\tilde{g}}$ is a **Lorentz transformations**, and the isotropic and flat (\tilde{M}, \tilde{g}) is **Minkowski spacetime**.

Proposition 5.2.2. Let L be a path on \tilde{M} , and \tilde{U} be a coordinate neighborhood. Denote $\tilde{U}_L \triangleq \tilde{U} \cap L$, and $c \triangleq |dx^i/dx^0|$. If $\forall q \in \tilde{U}_L$, tangent vector $[L] \in T_q(M)$ is not internal-directed, then: (i) we have $c = 1$ on path \tilde{U}_L . (ii) $c = 1$ remains unchanged under orthogonal transformation. (iii) $c = 1$ remains unchanged under Lorentz transformation.

Proof. In regular coordinate frame (\tilde{U}, x^K) , \tilde{U}_L can be described by equations $x^i = x^i(x^0)$ and $x^\tau = const$ about parameter x^0 . We notice that $x^\tau = const$, so there does not exist an equation of \tilde{U}_L with respect to parameter \tilde{x}^τ in Minkowski coordinate frame $(\tilde{U}, \tilde{x}^\mu)$. Therefore, we always have $d\tilde{x}^\tau = dx^\tau = 0$ on \tilde{U}_L . Thus, $c = |dx^i/dx^0| = \left| \pm dx^i / \sqrt{(dx^i)^2 + (dx^\tau)^2} \right| = |\pm dx^i/dx^i| = 1$. According to Definition 5.2.2 , an orthogonal transformation satisfies $d\tilde{\zeta}^\tau = d\tilde{x}^\tau = 0$, hence

$c' = |d\zeta^s/d\zeta^0| = |\pm d\zeta^s/d\zeta^s| = 1$. It is naturally true for Lorentz transformation as an orthogonal one. \square

Remark 5.2.2. The above proposition indicates the limitation of Minkowski coordinate, and also turns the principle of constancy of light velocity to a theorem, i.e. conclusion (iii). Its mathematical origin can be attributed to Definition 3.2.1 .

Discussion 5.2.1. Let $\tilde{\rho}$ be a charge of \tilde{f} , and L be a gradient line of $\tilde{\rho}$ on (\tilde{M}, \tilde{g}) .

(1) In the basis coordinate frame $\{\tilde{\zeta}^\alpha\}$ of \tilde{g} , suppose the parameter equation of L satisfies $\tilde{\zeta}^s = \text{const}$. Thus on L we have velocity $\frac{d\tilde{\zeta}^s}{d\tau} = 0$ and proper time $d\tilde{\zeta}^0 = d\tau$. This is the intrinsic geometrical treatment of the inertial relative rest state of physics, which is not a stopped evolution, but just an evolution in a special direction.

(2) In the performance coordinate frame $\{\tilde{x}^\mu\}$ of \tilde{g} , on L we have velocity $\frac{d\tilde{x}^i}{d\tau} = \tilde{C}_0^i$ and coordinate time $d\tilde{x}^0 = \tilde{C}_\tau^0 d\tau$, where the slack-tights \tilde{C}_α^μ are constants. This is the intrinsic geometrical treatment of the inertial relative motion of physics.

5.3 Two coordinate representations of intrinsic geometrical property

Discussion 5.3.1. According to Definition 3.3.2.2 , suppose the slack-tights of (\tilde{M}, \tilde{f}) about regular coordinate x^K are B_I^S and C_S^I , such that

$$\begin{cases} d\xi^S = B_I^S dx^I \simeq B_0^S dx^0 \\ C_0^I \frac{\partial}{\partial x^I} \simeq C_0^0 \frac{d}{dx^0} = \frac{d}{d\xi^0} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} dx^I = C_S^I d\xi^S \simeq C_0^I d\xi^0 \\ B_0^S \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^S} \simeq B_0^0 \frac{d}{d\xi^0} = \frac{d}{dx^0} \end{cases}. \quad (19)$$

The slack-tights of (\tilde{M}, \tilde{f}) about Minkowski coordinate \tilde{x}^μ are \tilde{B}_μ^α and \tilde{C}_α^μ , such that

$$\begin{cases} d\tilde{\xi}^\alpha = \tilde{B}_\mu^\alpha d\tilde{x}^\mu \simeq \tilde{B}_\tau^\alpha d\tilde{x}^\tau \\ \tilde{C}_\tau^\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} \simeq \tilde{C}_\tau^\tau \frac{d}{d\tilde{x}^\tau} = \frac{d}{d\tilde{\xi}^\tau} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} d\tilde{x}^\mu = \tilde{C}_\alpha^\mu d\tilde{\xi}^\alpha \simeq \tilde{C}_\tau^\mu d\tilde{\xi}^\tau \\ \tilde{B}_\tau^\alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{\xi}^\alpha} \simeq \tilde{B}_\tau^\tau \frac{d}{d\tilde{\xi}^\tau} = \frac{d}{d\tilde{x}^\tau} \end{cases}. \quad (20)$$

Applying the chain rule of differentiation, it is not difficult to obtain the following relations between regular slack-tights and Minkowski slack-tights via formula (18).

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{B}_i^s = -B_i^s \\ \tilde{B}_i^0 = -\frac{B_i^\tau}{\delta_0^\tau} \\ \tilde{C}_\tau^i = \frac{C_0^i}{\delta_0^\tau} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} \tilde{B}_\tau^s = B_\tau^s \\ \tilde{B}_\tau^0 = \frac{B_\tau^\tau}{\delta_0^\tau} \\ \tilde{C}_\tau^\tau = \frac{C_0^\tau}{\delta_0^\tau} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} \tilde{B}_0^s = B_0^s \\ \tilde{B}_0^0 = \frac{B_0^\tau}{\delta_0^\tau} \\ \tilde{C}_\tau^0 = \frac{C_0^0}{\delta_0^\tau} \end{cases}; \quad \begin{cases} \tilde{C}_s^i = -C_s^i \\ \tilde{C}_s^0 = -\frac{C_s^\tau}{\varepsilon_0^\tau} \\ \tilde{B}_\tau^s = \frac{B_0^s}{\varepsilon_0^\tau} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} \tilde{C}_\tau^i = C_\tau^i \\ \tilde{C}_\tau^0 = \frac{C_\tau^\tau}{\varepsilon_0^\tau} \\ \tilde{B}_\tau^\tau = \frac{B_0^\tau}{\varepsilon_0^\tau} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} \tilde{C}_0^i = C_0^i \\ \tilde{C}_0^0 = \frac{C_0^\tau}{\varepsilon_0^\tau} \\ \tilde{B}_\tau^0 = \frac{B_0^0}{\varepsilon_0^\tau} \end{cases},$$

$$\begin{cases} B_i^s = -\tilde{B}_i^s \\ B_i^\tau = -\frac{\tilde{B}_i^0}{\delta_0^\tau} \\ C_0^i = -\frac{\tilde{C}_\tau^i}{\delta_0^\tau} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} B_0^s = \tilde{B}_0^s \\ B_0^\tau = \frac{\tilde{B}_0^0}{\delta_0^\tau} \\ C_0^0 = \frac{\tilde{C}_\tau^0}{\delta_0^\tau} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} B_\tau^s = \tilde{B}_\tau^s \\ B_\tau^\tau = \frac{\tilde{B}_\tau^0}{\delta_0^\tau} \\ C_0^\tau = \frac{\tilde{C}_\tau^\tau}{\delta_0^\tau} \end{cases}; \quad \begin{cases} C_s^i = -\tilde{C}_s^i \\ C_s^\tau = -\frac{\tilde{C}_s^0}{\varepsilon_0^\tau} \\ B_0^s = \frac{\tilde{B}_\tau^s}{\varepsilon_0^\tau} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} C_0^i = \tilde{C}_0^i \\ C_0^\tau = \frac{\tilde{C}_0^0}{\varepsilon_0^\tau} \\ B_0^0 = \frac{\tilde{B}_\tau^0}{\varepsilon_0^\tau} \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} C_\tau^i = \tilde{C}_\tau^i \\ C_\tau^\tau = \frac{\tilde{C}_\tau^0}{\varepsilon_0^\tau} \\ B_0^\tau = \frac{\tilde{B}_\tau^\tau}{\varepsilon_0^\tau} \end{cases},$$

where

$$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_J^I \triangleq C_S^I B_J^S, & \delta_T^S \triangleq B_I^S C_T^I, & \varepsilon_0^I \triangleq B_0^0 C_0^I = B_0^S C_0^I, & \delta_0^S \triangleq C_0^0 B_0^S = C_0^I B_0^I. \\ \tilde{\varepsilon}_\nu^\mu \triangleq \tilde{C}_\alpha^\mu \tilde{B}_\nu^\alpha, & \tilde{\delta}_\beta^\alpha \triangleq \tilde{B}_\mu^\alpha \tilde{C}_\beta^\mu, & \tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^\mu \triangleq \tilde{B}_\tau^\tau \tilde{C}_\tau^\mu = \tilde{B}_\tau^\alpha \tilde{C}_\tau^\mu, & \tilde{\delta}_\tau^\alpha \triangleq \tilde{C}_\tau^\tau \tilde{B}_\tau^\alpha = \tilde{C}_\tau^\mu \tilde{B}_\tau^\mu. \end{cases}$$

The evolution lemma of Proposition 3.3.2.2 can be expressed in Minkowski coordinate as

$$\begin{cases} w^\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} \cong w^\tau \frac{d}{d\tilde{x}^\tau} \Leftrightarrow w^\mu = w^\tau \tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^\mu, & \begin{cases} \bar{w}_\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}_\mu} \cong \bar{w}_\tau \frac{d}{d\tilde{x}_\tau} \Leftrightarrow \bar{w}_\mu = \bar{w}_\tau \tilde{\varepsilon}_\mu^\tau, \\ \bar{w}^\mu d\tilde{x}_\mu \cong \bar{w}^\tau d\tilde{x}_\tau \Leftrightarrow \tilde{\varepsilon}_\mu^\tau \bar{w}^\mu = \bar{w}^\tau \end{cases} \end{cases},$$

where $\tilde{\varepsilon}_\nu^\mu \triangleq \tilde{B}_\alpha^\mu \tilde{C}_\nu^\alpha = \varepsilon_\nu^\mu$, $\tilde{\delta}_\beta^\alpha \triangleq \tilde{C}_\mu^\alpha \tilde{B}_\beta^\mu = \delta_\beta^\alpha$, $\tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^\mu \triangleq \tilde{B}_\tau^\tau \tilde{C}_\tau^\mu = \tilde{B}_\tau^\alpha \tilde{C}_\tau^\mu$, $\tilde{\delta}_\tau^\alpha \triangleq \tilde{C}_\tau^\tau \tilde{B}_\tau^\alpha = \tilde{C}_\tau^\mu \tilde{B}_\tau^\mu$.

Discussion 5.3.2. According to Definition 3.2.1, on the neighborhood \tilde{U} of p on (\tilde{M}, f) , time metrics $d\xi^0$ and dx^0 of $\tilde{f}(p)$ in coordinate frames (\tilde{U}, ξ^S) and (\tilde{U}, x^I) satisfy

$$\begin{cases} (d\xi^0)^2 \triangleq \sum_{s=1}^r (d\xi^s)^2 + (d\xi^\tau)^2 = \delta_{ST} d\xi^S d\xi^T = \delta_{ST} b_I^S b_J^T dx^I dx^J = g_{IJ} dx^I dx^J, \\ (dx^0)^2 \triangleq \sum_{i=1}^r (dx^i)^2 + (dx^\tau)^2 = \varepsilon_{IJ} dx^I dx^J = \varepsilon_{IJ} c_S^I c_T^J d\xi^S d\xi^T = h_{ST} d\xi^S d\xi^T. \end{cases}$$

where $(d\xi^\tau)^2 \triangleq \sum_{a=r+1}^{\mathfrak{D}} (d\xi^a)^2$ and $(dx^\tau)^2 \triangleq \sum_{m=r+1}^{\mathfrak{D}} (dx^m)^2$. As differential forms defined on manifold, time metrics of (\tilde{M}, \tilde{f}) satisfy

$$\begin{cases} (d\xi^0)^2 \triangleq \Delta_{ST} d\xi^S d\xi^T = G_{IJ} dx^I dx^J, & \begin{cases} G_{IJ} \triangleq \Delta_{ST} B_I^S B_J^T, \\ H_{ST} \triangleq E_{IJ} C_S^I C_T^J. \end{cases} \\ (dx^0)^2 \triangleq E_{IJ} dx^I dx^J = H_{ST} d\xi^S d\xi^T. \end{cases}$$

Denote

$$\tilde{\varepsilon}_{\mu\nu} = \tilde{\varepsilon}^{\mu\nu} \triangleq \begin{cases} 1 & \mu = \nu = 0 \\ -1, & \mu = \nu \neq 0 \\ 0, & \mu \neq \nu \end{cases}, \quad \tilde{\delta}_{\alpha\beta} = \tilde{\delta}^{\alpha\beta} \triangleq \begin{cases} 1 & \alpha = \beta = 0 \\ -1, & \alpha = \beta \neq 0 \\ 0, & \alpha \neq \beta \end{cases}.$$

Thus, we can define **proper-times** $d\tilde{\xi}^\tau$ and $d\tilde{x}^\tau$ in Minkowski coordinate frames $(\tilde{U}, \tilde{\xi}^\alpha)$ and $(\tilde{U}, \tilde{x}^\mu)$ as below:

$$\begin{cases} (d\tilde{\xi}^\tau)^2 = (d\xi^0)^2 - \sum_{s=1}^r (d\xi^s)^2 = \tilde{\delta}_{\alpha\beta} d\tilde{\xi}^\alpha d\tilde{\xi}^\beta = \tilde{\delta}_{\alpha\beta} \tilde{b}_\mu^\alpha \tilde{b}_\nu^\beta d\tilde{x}^\mu d\tilde{x}^\nu = \tilde{g}_{\mu\nu} d\tilde{x}^\mu d\tilde{x}^\nu, \\ (d\tilde{x}^\tau)^2 = (dx^0)^2 - \sum_{i=1}^r (dx^i)^2 = \tilde{\varepsilon}_{\mu\nu} d\tilde{x}^\mu d\tilde{x}^\nu = \tilde{\varepsilon}_{\mu\nu} \tilde{c}_\alpha^\mu \tilde{c}_\beta^\nu d\tilde{\xi}^\alpha d\tilde{\xi}^\beta = \tilde{h}_{\alpha\beta} d\tilde{\xi}^\alpha d\tilde{\xi}^\beta. \end{cases}$$

And there are differential forms on (\tilde{M}, \tilde{f}) as below:

$$\begin{cases} (d\tilde{\xi}^\tau)^2 \triangleq \tilde{\Delta}_{\alpha\beta} d\tilde{\xi}^\alpha d\tilde{\xi}^\beta = \tilde{G}_{\mu\nu} d\tilde{x}^\mu d\tilde{x}^\nu, & \begin{cases} \tilde{G}_{\mu\nu} \triangleq \tilde{\Delta}_{\alpha\beta} \tilde{B}_\mu^\alpha \tilde{B}_\nu^\beta, \\ \tilde{H}_{\alpha\beta} \triangleq \tilde{E}_{\mu\nu} \tilde{C}_\alpha^\mu \tilde{C}_\beta^\nu. \end{cases} \\ (d\tilde{x}^\tau)^2 \triangleq \tilde{E}_{\mu\nu} d\tilde{x}^\mu d\tilde{x}^\nu = \tilde{H}_{\alpha\beta} d\tilde{\xi}^\alpha d\tilde{\xi}^\beta. \end{cases}$$

It is easy to know there are relations between regular metric G_{IJ} and Minkowski metric $\tilde{G}_{\mu\nu}$ as below:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} G_{\tau\tau} = \frac{\tilde{G}_{\tau\tau}}{\tilde{G}_{00}} G_{00} = \frac{\tilde{\delta}_\tau^0 \tilde{\delta}_\tau^0}{\tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^0 \tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^0} \tilde{G}_{\tau\tau} \tilde{G}_{00} \\ G_{i\tau} = -\frac{\tilde{G}_{i0}}{\tilde{G}_{00}} \tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^0 G_{00} = -\frac{\tilde{\delta}_\tau^0 \tilde{\delta}_\tau^0}{\tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^0} \tilde{G}_{\tau\tau} \tilde{G}_{i0} \\ G_{\tau j} = -\frac{\tilde{G}_{0j}}{\tilde{G}_{00}} \tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^0 G_{00} = -\frac{\tilde{\delta}_\tau^0 \tilde{\delta}_\tau^0}{\tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^0} \tilde{G}_{\tau\tau} \tilde{G}_{0j} \\ G_{ij} = -\frac{\tilde{G}_{ij}}{\tilde{G}_{00}} G_{00} = -\frac{\tilde{\delta}_\tau^0 \tilde{\delta}_\tau^0}{\tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^0 \tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^0} \tilde{G}_{\tau\tau} \tilde{G}_{ij} \end{array} \right. , \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{G}_{00} = \frac{G_{00}}{G_{\tau\tau}} \tilde{G}_{\tau\tau} = \frac{\delta_0^\tau \delta_0^\tau}{\varepsilon_0^\tau \varepsilon_0^\tau} G_{00} G_{\tau\tau} \\ \tilde{G}_{i0} = -\frac{G_{i\tau}}{G_{\tau\tau}} \varepsilon_0^\tau \tilde{G}_{\tau\tau} = -\frac{\delta_0^\tau \delta_0^\tau}{\varepsilon_0^\tau} \frac{G_{00}}{G_{\tau\tau}} G_{i\tau} \\ \tilde{G}_{0j} = -\frac{G_{\tau j}}{G_{\tau\tau}} \varepsilon_0^\tau \tilde{G}_{\tau\tau} = -\frac{\delta_0^\tau \delta_0^\tau}{\varepsilon_0^\tau} \frac{G_{00}}{G_{\tau\tau}} G_{\tau j} \\ \tilde{G}_{ij} = -\frac{G_{ij}}{G_{\tau\tau}} \tilde{G}_{\tau\tau} = -\frac{\delta_0^\tau \delta_0^\tau}{\varepsilon_0^\tau \varepsilon_0^\tau} \frac{G_{00}}{G_{\tau\tau}} G_{ij} \end{array} \right. .$$

Denote $\tilde{G}_{\tau\tau} \triangleq \tilde{B}_\tau^\tau \tilde{B}_\tau^\tau$, $\tilde{G}^{\tau\tau} \triangleq \tilde{C}_\tau^\tau \tilde{C}_\tau^\tau$, then it is easy to obtain relations:

$$\tilde{G}_{\tau\tau} = \frac{\delta_0^\tau \delta_0^\tau}{\varepsilon_0^\tau \varepsilon_0^\tau} G_{00}, \quad G_{00} = \frac{\tilde{\delta}_\tau^0 \tilde{\delta}_\tau^0}{\tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^0 \tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^0} \tilde{G}_{\tau\tau}.$$

5.4 Geometrical treatment of classical spacetime evolution

Discussion 5.4.1. The absolute differential and absolute gradient of section 3.3.4 can be expressed on \tilde{M} in Minkowski coordinate as:

(1) Let \tilde{D} be affine connection on \tilde{M} , and denote $\tilde{t}_{L;\tau} \triangleq \tilde{t}_{;\sigma} \tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^\sigma$, then the absolute differential of \tilde{T} and \tilde{T}_L are

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{D}\tilde{T} \triangleq \tilde{D}\tilde{t} \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}} \otimes d\tilde{x} \right\} \triangleq \tilde{t}_{;\sigma} d\tilde{x}^\sigma \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}} \otimes d\tilde{x} \right\}, \\ \tilde{D}_L \tilde{T}_L \triangleq \tilde{D}_L \tilde{t}_L \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}} \otimes d\tilde{x} \right\} \triangleq \tilde{t}_{L;\tau} d\tilde{x}^\tau \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}} \otimes d\tilde{x} \right\}, \end{array} \right.$$

where $\tilde{D}\tilde{t} \triangleq \tilde{t}_{;\sigma} d\tilde{x}^\sigma$, $\tilde{D}_L \tilde{t}_L \triangleq \tilde{t}_{L;\tau} d\tilde{x}^\tau$.

(2) The gradient operator $\tilde{\nabla}$ is the actual evolution on \tilde{M} . Thus, the absolute gradient of \tilde{T} and \tilde{T}_L are

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \tilde{\nabla}\tilde{T} \triangleq \tilde{\nabla}\tilde{t} \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}} \otimes d\tilde{x} \right\} \triangleq \tilde{t}_{;\sigma} \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}_\sigma} \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}} \otimes d\tilde{x} \right\}, \\ \tilde{\nabla}_L \tilde{T}_L \triangleq \tilde{\nabla}_L \tilde{t}_L \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}} \otimes d\tilde{x} \right\} \triangleq \tilde{t}_{L;\tau} \frac{d}{d\tilde{x}_\tau} \otimes \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}} \otimes d\tilde{x} \right\}, \end{array} \right.$$

where $\tilde{\nabla}\tilde{t} \triangleq \tilde{t}_{;\sigma} \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}_\sigma}$, $\tilde{\nabla}_L \tilde{t}_L \triangleq \tilde{t}_{L;\tau} \frac{d}{d\tilde{x}_\tau}$.

Now Proposition 3.3.4.1 can be expressed as: $\tilde{D}\tilde{T} \simeq \tilde{D}_L \tilde{T}_L$ if L is an arbitrary path. $\tilde{\nabla}\tilde{T} \simeq \tilde{\nabla}_L \tilde{T}_L$ if and only if L is the gradient line of \tilde{T} . The actual evolution equation of \tilde{T} is $\tilde{t}_{;\sigma} = \tilde{t}_{L;\tau} \tilde{\varepsilon}_\sigma^\tau$ or $\tilde{t}^{;\sigma} = \tilde{t}_L^{;\tau} \tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^\sigma$.

Discussion 5.4.2. Similar to Discussion 3.3.5.1 we have $\tilde{K}_{\nu\rho\sigma}^{\mu;\rho} = \tilde{j}_{\nu\sigma}^\mu$, where $\tilde{\rho}_{\nu\tau}^\mu \triangleq \tilde{K}_{\nu\rho\sigma}^{\mu;\rho} \tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^\sigma$, $\tilde{j}_{\nu\sigma}^\mu \triangleq \tilde{\rho}_{\nu\tau}^\mu \tilde{\varepsilon}_\sigma^\tau$. Consider the case where external space is flat, then just only the internal component $\tilde{\rho}_{0\tau}^0$ does not vanish. Thus we have **Minkowski Yang-Mills field equation**

$$\tilde{K}_{0\rho\sigma}^0{}^{;\rho} = \tilde{j}_{0\sigma}^0,$$

where $\tilde{j}_{0\sigma}^0 \triangleq \tilde{\rho}_{0\tau}^0 \tilde{\varepsilon}_\sigma^\tau$.

Now there is a problem. Several internal dimensions of (M, f) become just one dimension of (\tilde{M}, \tilde{f}) via the encapsulation of classical spacetime. (M, f) has several internal charges ρ_{n0}^m , but (\tilde{M}, \tilde{f}) has just one, which is $\rho_{\tau 0}^\tau$ in regular form, or $\tilde{\rho}_{0\tau}^0$ in Minkowski form. As what Remark 5.2.1 says, (\tilde{M}, \tilde{f}) cannot totally reflect all the intrinsic geometrical properties of internal space of (M, f) .

On the premise of not abandoning the four-dimensional spacetime, if we want to describe gauge fields, the only way is to put those degrees of freedom of internal space to the phase of complex-valued field function. This way is effective, but not natural at all.

The logically more natural way is to abandon the framework of four-dimensional spacetime. We should put internal space and external space together to describe their unified intrinsic geometry, rather than based on the rigid intuition of four-dimensional spacetime, artificially setting up several abstract degrees of freedom which are irrelevant to the concept of time and space to describe the so called gauge fields.

Both for gauge fields and for gravitational fields, their concepts of time and space should be unified. The gravitational fields are described by the intrinsic geometry of external space, and the gauge fields are described by the intrinsic geometry of internal space. They are unified in intrinsic geometry.

Therefore, the complex-valued expression form of traditional gauge field theory is a historical necessity, but not a logical necessity. It can be seen later that as long as expanding those encapsulated dimensions, we can clearly illustrate the geometrical properties of internal space. Especially, if understanding in way of intrinsic geometry, some man-made postulates of Standard Model of particle physics will be unnecessary, because they will appear automatically.

Definition 5.4.1. Denote $\tilde{\rho}_{\mu\nu}^\tau$ of \tilde{f} concisely by $\tilde{\rho}$. According to section 3.3.6, we have the following definitions in Minkowski coordinate on (\tilde{M}, \tilde{g}) .

- (1) Call $\tilde{m}^\tau \triangleq \tilde{\rho}^{i\tau}$ and $\tilde{m}_\tau \triangleq \tilde{\rho}_{i\tau}$ the **rest mass** of $\tilde{\rho}$.
- (2) Call $\tilde{p}^\mu \triangleq \tilde{\rho}^{i\mu}$ and $\tilde{p}_\mu \triangleq \tilde{\rho}_{i\mu}$ the **energy-momentum** of $\tilde{\rho}$, and $\tilde{E}^0 \triangleq \tilde{p}^0$, $\tilde{E}_0 \triangleq \tilde{p}_0$ the **energy** of $\tilde{\rho}$.
- (3) Call $\tilde{M}^\tau \triangleq \frac{d\tilde{\rho}}{d\tilde{x}^\tau}$ and $\tilde{M}_\tau \triangleq \frac{d\tilde{\rho}}{d\tilde{x}^\tau}$ the **canonical rest mass** of $\tilde{\rho}$.
- (4) Call $\tilde{P}^\mu \triangleq \frac{\partial\tilde{\rho}}{\partial\tilde{x}^\mu}$ and $\tilde{P}_\mu \triangleq \frac{\partial\tilde{\rho}}{\partial\tilde{x}^\mu}$ the **canonical energy-momentum** of $\tilde{\rho}$, and $\tilde{H}^0 \triangleq -\tilde{P}^0$, $\tilde{H}_0 \triangleq -\tilde{P}_0$ the **canonical energy** of $\tilde{\rho}$.

Discussion 5.4.3. Similar to Proposition 3.3.6.2, if and only if the evolution direction of $\tilde{\rho}$ is the gradient direction $\tilde{\nabla}\tilde{\rho}$ on (\tilde{M}, \tilde{g}) , the directional derivative is $\left\langle \tilde{m}_\tau \frac{d}{d\tilde{x}^\tau}, \tilde{m}_\tau d\tilde{x}^\tau \right\rangle = \left\langle \tilde{p}_\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial\tilde{x}^\mu}, \tilde{p}_\mu d\tilde{x}^\mu \right\rangle$, that is $\tilde{G}^{\tau\tau} \tilde{m}_\tau \tilde{m}_\tau = \tilde{G}^{\mu\nu} \tilde{p}_\mu \tilde{p}_\nu$, or $\tilde{m}_\tau \tilde{m}^\tau = \tilde{p}_\mu \tilde{p}^\mu$, which is the mathematical origin of energy-momentum equation of physics.

In addition, as what Proposition 3.3.6.3 says, according to evolution lemma, if and only if we take the gradient direction $\tilde{\nabla}\tilde{\rho}$, we have $\tilde{p}^\mu = \tilde{m}_\tau \frac{d\tilde{x}^\mu}{d\tilde{x}^\tau}$ and $\tilde{p}_\mu = \tilde{m}_\tau \frac{d\tilde{x}_\mu}{d\tilde{x}^\tau}$. This is the mathematical origin of traditional definition of momentum.

Similar to discussions of section 3.3.7 , denote

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\tilde{\rho}\tilde{\Gamma}_\omega] \triangleq [\tilde{\rho}_{\mu\nu}\tilde{\Gamma}_\omega] \triangleq \frac{\partial\tilde{\rho}}{\partial\tilde{x}^\omega} - \tilde{\rho}_{;\omega} \triangleq \frac{\partial\tilde{\rho}_{\mu\nu}}{\partial\tilde{x}^\omega} - \tilde{\rho}_{\mu\nu;\omega} = \tilde{\rho}_{\mu\chi}\tilde{\Gamma}_{\nu\omega}^\chi + \tilde{\rho}_{\chi\nu}\tilde{\Gamma}_{\mu\omega}^\chi, \\ [\tilde{\rho}\tilde{\Gamma}_\tau] \triangleq [\tilde{\rho}_{\mu\nu}\tilde{\Gamma}_\tau] \triangleq \frac{d\tilde{\rho}}{d\tilde{x}^\tau} - \tilde{\rho}_{;\tau} \triangleq \frac{d\tilde{\rho}_{\mu\nu}}{d\tilde{x}^\tau} - \tilde{\rho}_{\mu\nu;\tau} = \tilde{\rho}_{\mu\chi}\tilde{\Gamma}_{\nu\tau}^\chi + \tilde{\rho}_{\chi\nu}\tilde{\Gamma}_{\mu\tau}^\chi. \end{array} \right. \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\tilde{\rho}\tilde{\Gamma}^\omega] \triangleq \tilde{G}^{\chi\omega}[\tilde{\rho}\tilde{\Gamma}_\chi], \\ [\tilde{\rho}\tilde{\Gamma}^\tau] \triangleq \tilde{G}^{\tau\tau}[\tilde{\rho}\tilde{\Gamma}_\tau]. \end{array} \right.$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\tilde{\rho}\tilde{B}_{\rho\sigma}] \triangleq \tilde{\rho}_{\mu\chi} \left(\frac{\partial\tilde{\Gamma}_{\nu\sigma}^\chi}{\partial\tilde{x}^\rho} - \frac{\partial\tilde{\Gamma}_{\nu\rho}^\chi}{\partial\tilde{x}^\sigma} \right) + \tilde{\rho}_{\chi\nu} \left(\frac{\partial\tilde{\Gamma}_{\mu\sigma}^\chi}{\partial\tilde{x}^\rho} - \frac{\partial\tilde{\Gamma}_{\mu\rho}^\chi}{\partial\tilde{x}^\sigma} \right), \\ [\tilde{\rho}\tilde{R}_{\rho\sigma}] \triangleq \tilde{\rho}_{\mu\chi}\tilde{R}_{\nu\rho\sigma}^\chi + \tilde{\rho}_{\chi\nu}\tilde{R}_{\mu\rho\sigma}^\chi, \end{array} \right. \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\tilde{\rho}\tilde{F}_{\rho\sigma}] \triangleq \frac{\partial[\tilde{\rho}\tilde{\Gamma}_\sigma]}{\partial\tilde{x}^\rho} - \frac{\partial[\tilde{\rho}\tilde{\Gamma}_\rho]}{\partial\tilde{x}^\sigma}, \\ [\tilde{\rho}\tilde{E}_{\rho\sigma}] \triangleq [\tilde{\rho}\tilde{\Gamma}_\sigma]_{;\rho} - [\tilde{\rho}\tilde{\Gamma}_\rho]_{;\sigma}. \end{array} \right.$$

Then for the same reason as Proposition 3.3.7.2 , we can strictly prove the **Lorentz force** equation of $\tilde{\rho}$, which is $\tilde{F}_\rho \triangleq \frac{d\tilde{p}_\rho}{d\tilde{x}^\tau} = \frac{\partial\tilde{m}_\tau}{\partial\tilde{x}^\rho} - \tilde{p}_\sigma \frac{\partial\tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^\sigma}{\partial\tilde{x}^\rho} + [\tilde{\rho}\tilde{F}_{\rho\sigma}]\tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^\sigma$. And for the same reason as Proposition 3.3.7.5 , we have conservation of energy-momentum $\tilde{T}_{\mu\nu}{}^{;\mu} = 0$.

Definition 5.4.2. The following three conditions are uniformly called **traditional standard conditions**:

- (1) Rest mass condition: $\partial_\mu\tilde{m}_\tau = 0$.
- (2) Canonical mass condition: $\tilde{\Gamma}_{\nu\rho}^\mu\tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^\rho = 0$ and $\tilde{\Gamma}_{\nu\rho}^\mu\gamma^\rho = 0$, where γ^ρ are generators of Dirac algebra.
- (3) Simple perspective condition: $\partial_\nu\tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^\mu = 0$.

Remark 5.4.1. Conditions (1) and (3) make the above Lorentz force simplify to $\tilde{F}_\rho = [\tilde{\rho}\tilde{F}_{\rho\sigma}]\tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^\sigma$, which is the general essence of interaction force of physics, and also is the mathematical origin of Lorentz force $\mathbf{F} = q(\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B})$ or $F_\rho = j^\sigma F_{\rho\sigma}$ of electrodynamics. In this sense, we can argue that Lorentz force equation has become a theorem, and no longer as a principle.

Condition (2) is the general mathematical expression of the following example. Take electrodynamics with natural units for example. The canonical energy-momentum of electric charged particle is

$$H = E + q\varphi, \quad \mathbf{P} = \mathbf{p} + q\mathbf{A}.$$

We notice that there is no concept of canonical mass \tilde{M}_τ in physics. It is because that there is $H = q\varphi + \sqrt{(\mathbf{P} - q\mathbf{A})^2 + m^2}$ in electrodynamics, which indicates that electromagnetic potential field (φ, \mathbf{A}) contributes $q\varphi$ to energy and $q\mathbf{A}$ to momentum, but it contributes nothing to rest mass of q . This implies that if we define

$$\tilde{M}_\tau \triangleq \tilde{m}_\tau + q\tilde{A}_\tau, \quad \tilde{A}_\tau \triangleq \varphi\gamma + \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{u} = A_\rho \frac{dx^\rho}{d\tau},$$

then electrodynamics actually requires $\tilde{M}_\tau = \tilde{m}_\tau$, $\tilde{A}_\tau = A_\rho \frac{dx^\rho}{d\tau} = 0$ by default, the general mathematical expression of which is $\tilde{\Gamma}_{\nu\tau}^\mu \triangleq \tilde{\Gamma}_{\nu\rho}^\mu \tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^\rho = 0$. More importantly, Proposition 5.4.1 , Definition 5.5.1 and Proposition 5.6.1 are dependent on this condition.

In a word, the above three conditions are necessary for transitioning in pure mathematical sense to traditional theory of physics.

Discussion 5.4.4. Suppose $\tilde{C}_{(\tilde{x})\mu\nu}$ is a zero-order or two-order tensor, such as $\tilde{R}_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}\tilde{G}_{\mu\nu}\tilde{R}$, which just only depends on intrinsic geometrical properties of (\tilde{M}, \tilde{g}) , such that $\tilde{C}_{(\tilde{x})\mu\nu}{}^{;\mu} = 0$.

We distinguish them with index (\tilde{x}) . And suppose $T_{(\tilde{\rho})\mu\nu}{}^{i\mu} = 0$ is the conservation of energy-momentum of $\tilde{\rho}$. We distinguish various $T_{(\tilde{\rho})\mu\nu}$ with index $(\tilde{\rho})$. Hence, $\forall c^{(\tilde{x})}, c^{(\tilde{\rho})} \in \mathbb{R}$, we have

$$\left(\sum_{\tilde{x}} c^{(\tilde{x})} C_{(\tilde{x})\mu\nu} + \sum_{\tilde{\rho}} c^{(\tilde{\rho})} \tilde{T}_{(\tilde{\rho})\mu\nu} \right)^{i\mu} = 0.$$

If the ergodic ranges of the summations are sufficiently large, we immediately obtain

$$\sum_{\tilde{x}} c^{(\tilde{x})} C_{(\tilde{x})\mu\nu} + \sum_{\tilde{\rho}} c^{(\tilde{\rho})} \tilde{T}_{(\tilde{\rho})\mu\nu} = 0,$$

which is the general gravitational field equation, where the dimensions among various terms are harmonized by constants $c^{(\tilde{x})}, c^{(\tilde{\rho})}$. It is the mathematical origin of Einstein's gravitational field equation.

Definition 5.4.3. It is similar to Definition 3.3.6. Let $\tilde{\mathbb{L}}$ be the totality of paths on \tilde{M} from point a to point b . And let $L_{\tilde{\rho}} \in \tilde{\mathbb{L}}$, and parameter \tilde{x}^τ satisfy $\tau_a \triangleq \tilde{x}^\tau(a) < \tilde{x}^\tau(b) \triangleq \tau_b$. We say the functional

$$\tilde{s}_{\tilde{\rho}\tilde{W}}(L_{\tilde{\rho}}) \triangleq \int_{L_{\tilde{\rho}}} \tilde{D}\tilde{\rho} = \int_{L_{\tilde{\rho}}} \tilde{p}_\mu d\tilde{x}^\mu = \int_{\tau_a}^{\tau_b} \tilde{m}_\tau d\tilde{x}^\tau = \int_{\tau_a}^{\tau_b} \frac{d\tilde{x}^\tau}{d\tilde{x}^0} \left(\tilde{M}_\tau - [\tilde{\rho}\tilde{\Gamma}_\sigma]\tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^\sigma \right) d\tilde{x}^0$$

is the **action** of $\tilde{\rho}$. For the same reason as the proof of Proposition 3.3.6.4, we have the following theorem, which is the mathematical origin of the principle of least action of physics.

Proposition 5.4.1. (Theorem of least action) On the canonical mass condition, $L_{\tilde{\rho}}$ is the gradient line of $\tilde{\rho}$ if and only if $\delta\tilde{s}_{\tilde{\rho}\tilde{W}}(L_{\tilde{\rho}}) = 0$.

5.5 Intrinsic geometrical treatment of Legendre transformation and equation of motion

This section does not discuss the general abstract theory of Legendre transformation, but discusses the relationship between energy-momentum equation and the concrete construction of Legendre transformation.

Definition 5.5.1. Denote

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0 \triangleq \tilde{m}_\tau \frac{d\tilde{x}^\tau}{d\tilde{x}^0} = \frac{d\tilde{x}^\tau}{d\tilde{x}^0} \left(\tilde{M}_\tau - [\tilde{\rho}\tilde{\Gamma}_\sigma]\tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^\sigma \right), \\ \tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0 \triangleq \tilde{M}_\tau \frac{d\tilde{x}^\tau}{d\tilde{x}^0} = \frac{d\tilde{x}^\tau}{d\tilde{x}^0} \left(\tilde{m}_\tau + [\tilde{\rho}\tilde{\Gamma}_\sigma]\tilde{\varepsilon}_\tau^\sigma \right). \end{cases}$$

Evidently we have $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0 = \tilde{L}_0$ on canonical mass condition. We say $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0$ is **Lagrangian density** of $\tilde{\rho}$.

According to Definition 5.4.1, we have $\tilde{M}_\tau d\tilde{x}^\tau = \tilde{P}_k d\tilde{x}^k - \tilde{H}_0 d\tilde{x}^0$, therefore $\tilde{H}_0 = \tilde{P}_k \frac{d\tilde{x}^k}{d\tilde{x}^0} - \tilde{M}_\tau \frac{d\tilde{x}^\tau}{d\tilde{x}^0}$, that is $\tilde{H}_0 = \tilde{P}_k \frac{d\tilde{x}^k}{d\tilde{x}^0} - \tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0$. We say \tilde{H}_0 is **Hamiltonian density** of $\tilde{\rho}$. This is the intrinsic geometrical origin of Legendre transformation of physics.

Proposition 5.5.1. Denote $\tilde{v}^k \triangleq \frac{d\tilde{x}^k}{d\tilde{x}^0}$, and regard $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0 = \tilde{P}_k \tilde{v}^k - \tilde{H}_0$ as function $\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0(\tilde{x}^k, \tilde{v}^k)$. Thus, on traditional standard conditions we have $\frac{d}{d\tilde{x}^0} \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0}{\partial \tilde{v}^k} \right) - \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0}{\partial \tilde{x}^k} = 0$.

Proof. On traditional standard conditions, we can obtain Euler-Lagrange equation from the definition of Lagrangian density. Concretely:

$$\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0 \triangleq \tilde{M}_\tau \frac{d\tilde{x}^\tau}{d\tilde{x}^0} = \frac{d\tilde{\rho}}{d\tilde{x}^\tau} \frac{d\tilde{x}^\tau}{d\tilde{x}^0} = \frac{\partial\tilde{\rho}}{\partial\tilde{x}^\mu} \frac{d\tilde{x}^\mu}{d\tilde{x}^\tau} \frac{d\tilde{x}^\tau}{d\tilde{x}^0}.$$

Accordingly,

$$\frac{\partial\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0}{\partial\tilde{x}^\sigma} = \frac{\partial}{\partial\tilde{x}^\sigma} \left(\frac{\partial\tilde{\rho}}{\partial\tilde{x}^\mu} \frac{d\tilde{x}^\mu}{d\tilde{x}^\tau} \frac{d\tilde{x}^\tau}{d\tilde{x}^0} \right).$$

On traditional standard conditions,

$$\frac{\partial\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0}{\partial\tilde{x}^\sigma} = \frac{d\tilde{x}^\mu}{d\tilde{x}^\tau} \frac{d\tilde{x}^\tau}{d\tilde{x}^0} \frac{\partial}{\partial\tilde{x}^\sigma} \left(\frac{\partial\tilde{\rho}}{\partial\tilde{x}^\mu} \right) = \frac{d\tilde{x}^\mu}{d\tilde{x}^\tau} \frac{d\tilde{x}^\tau}{d\tilde{x}^0} \frac{\partial}{\partial\tilde{x}^\mu} \left(\frac{\partial\tilde{\rho}}{\partial\tilde{x}^\sigma} \right) = \frac{d\tilde{x}^\mu}{d\tilde{x}^\tau} \frac{d\tilde{x}^\tau}{d\tilde{x}^0} \frac{\partial\tilde{P}_\sigma}{\partial\tilde{x}^\mu} = \frac{d\tilde{P}_\sigma}{d\tilde{x}^0}.$$

Thus we obtain Euler-Lagrange equation $\frac{d\tilde{P}_k}{d\tilde{x}^0} - \frac{\partial\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0}{\partial\tilde{x}^k} = 0$. In consideration of $\tilde{P}_k = \frac{\partial\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0}{\partial\tilde{v}^k}$, then

$$\frac{d}{d\tilde{x}^0} \left(\frac{\partial\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0}{\partial\tilde{v}^k} \right) - \frac{\partial\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0}{\partial\tilde{x}^k} = 0. \quad \square$$

Remark 5.5.1. The above proposition is the mathematical origin of Euler-Lagrange equation of motion of physics. It should be clarified that the above Euler-Lagrange equation holds in arbitrary directions, while the Euler-Lagrange equation of traditional theory holds just only in gradient direction.

The reason why such a situation happens is that their definitions of momentum are different. Definition 3.3.6.1 defines the momentum in arbitrary directions. Due to Proposition 3.3.6.3 and Remark 3.3.6.1, $p^R = E^0 \frac{dx^R}{dx^0}$ and $\tilde{p}^\mu = \tilde{m}^\tau \frac{d\tilde{x}^\mu}{d\tilde{x}^\tau}$ just hold in gradient direction. But traditional theory denotes $p \triangleq mv$ in arbitrary directions. Such two different ways of defining momentum make the conditions of the holding of Euler-Lagrange equation different.

(1) When $\tilde{p}^\mu = \tilde{m}^\tau \frac{d\tilde{x}^\mu}{d\tilde{x}^\tau}$ holds just only in gradient direction, Euler-Lagrange equation holds in arbitrary directions. At this time, what we can obtain from Proposition 5.4.1 is just only the former.

(2) When we denote $p \triangleq mv$ in arbitrary directions, Euler-Lagrange equation holds just only in gradient direction. At this time, what we can obtain from Proposition 5.4.1 is just only the latter.

No matter which way of definition we use, there is always a formula that can describe gradient direction. It is either $\tilde{p}^\mu = \tilde{m}^\tau \frac{d\tilde{x}^\mu}{d\tilde{x}^\tau}$ or Euler-Lagrange equation.

5.6 Intrinsic geometrical treatment of Dirac equation and gauge transformation

In this section we prove two propositions. The first one illustrates the intrinsic geometrical origin of Dirac equation, and makes it no longer a principle but a theorem. The second one clarifies the intrinsic geometrical origin of gauge transformation and gauge invariance, and shows how a transformation of reference-systems characterizes a gauge transformation.

Proposition 5.6.1. On traditional standard conditions, suppose there is a smooth real function $f(\tilde{x}^\mu)$ on an isotropic (\tilde{M}, \tilde{g}) , and define Dirac algebras γ^μ and γ^α such that $\gamma^\mu = \tilde{C}_\alpha^\mu \gamma^\alpha$,

$\gamma^\alpha \gamma^\beta + \gamma^\beta \gamma^\alpha = 2\tilde{\delta}^{\alpha\beta}$, $\gamma^\mu \gamma^\nu + \gamma^\nu \gamma^\mu = 2\tilde{G}^{\mu\nu}$, $\tilde{\Gamma}_{\nu\sigma}^\mu \gamma^\sigma = 0$, $\gamma^\mu \frac{\partial f}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} = 0$, $\int f^2 dV = 1$. Suppose the charge $\tilde{\rho} \triangleq \tilde{\rho}_{\omega\nu}$ of reference-system \tilde{f} evolves on (\tilde{M}, \tilde{g}) , and denote

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{P} \triangleq \int \tilde{\rho} dV, & \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \triangleq \int \tilde{m}_\tau dV, & \tilde{S} \triangleq \int \tilde{s} dV, \\ \tilde{\rho} = f^2 \tilde{P}, & \tilde{m}_\tau = f^2 \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau, & \tilde{s} = \int \tilde{\mathcal{L}}_0 d\tilde{x}^0 = f^2 \tilde{S}. \end{cases}$$

Then denote $\psi(\tilde{x}^\mu) \triangleq f(\tilde{x}^\mu) e^{i\tilde{S}}$, $\tilde{D}_\mu \triangleq \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} - i[\tilde{P} \tilde{\Gamma}_\mu]$. If and only if we take the gradient direction $\tilde{\nabla} \tilde{\rho}$, equation $i\gamma^\mu \tilde{D}_\mu \psi = \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \psi$ holds.

Proof. Due to Discussion 5.4.3, if and only if we take the gradient direction of $\tilde{\rho}$ there exists energy-momentum equation $\tilde{\rho}_{;\mu} \tilde{\rho}^{;\mu} = \tilde{\rho}_{;\tau} \tilde{\rho}^{;\tau}$, that is $\tilde{G}^{\mu\nu} \tilde{\rho}_{;\mu} \tilde{\rho}_{;\nu} = \tilde{m}_\tau^2$ due to isotropy. Then, $(\gamma^\mu \tilde{\rho}_{;\mu})(\gamma^\nu \tilde{\rho}_{;\nu}) + (\gamma^\nu \tilde{\rho}_{;\nu})(\gamma^\mu \tilde{\rho}_{;\mu}) = 2\tilde{m}_\tau^2$, hence $(\gamma^\mu \tilde{\rho}_{;\mu})(\gamma^\nu \tilde{\rho}_{;\nu}) = \tilde{m}_\tau^2$, that is $(\gamma^\mu \tilde{\rho}_{;\mu})^2 = \tilde{m}_\tau^2$. Without loss of generality, we take $\gamma^\mu \tilde{\rho}_{;\mu} = -\tilde{m}_\tau$. Due to canonical mass condition $\tilde{\Gamma}_{\nu\sigma}^\mu \gamma^\sigma = 0$ we have $\gamma^\mu [\tilde{P} \tilde{\Gamma}_\mu] = 0$. And with condition $\gamma^\mu \frac{\partial f}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} = 0$ it can be obtained that

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma^\mu \tilde{\rho}_{;\mu} = -\tilde{m}_\tau &\Leftrightarrow \gamma^\mu \frac{\partial \tilde{s}}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} = -\tilde{m}_\tau \Leftrightarrow \gamma^\mu \frac{\partial \tilde{S}}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} = -\tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \Leftrightarrow \gamma^\mu \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{S}}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} - [\tilde{P} \tilde{\Gamma}_\mu] \right) = -\tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \\ \Leftrightarrow i\gamma^\mu \left(i \frac{\partial \tilde{S}}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} f e^{i\tilde{S}} - i[\tilde{P} \tilde{\Gamma}_\mu] f e^{i\tilde{S}} \right) &= \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau f e^{i\tilde{S}} \Leftrightarrow i\gamma^\mu \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} e^{i\tilde{S}} + i \frac{\partial \tilde{S}}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} f e^{i\tilde{S}} - i[\tilde{P} \tilde{\Gamma}_\mu] f e^{i\tilde{S}} \right) = \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau f e^{i\tilde{S}} \\ \Leftrightarrow i\gamma^\mu \left(\frac{\partial (f e^{i\tilde{S}})}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} - i[\tilde{P} \tilde{\Gamma}_\mu] f e^{i\tilde{S}} \right) &= \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau f e^{i\tilde{S}} \Leftrightarrow i\gamma^\mu \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} - i[\tilde{P} \tilde{\Gamma}_\mu] \psi \right) = \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \psi \\ \Leftrightarrow i\gamma^\mu \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} - i[\tilde{P} \tilde{\Gamma}_\mu] \right) \psi &= \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \psi \Leftrightarrow i\gamma^\mu \tilde{D}_\mu \psi = \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \psi. \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 5.6.1. Until now, Dirac equation has become a theorem. According to this theorem, Dirac equation also reflects the notion of gradient direction, it thereby describes the effects of intrinsic geometry of manifold on gradient direction. This is the mathematical origin of the effectiveness of Dirac equation of physics.

Proposition 5.6.2. On \tilde{M} let the slack-tights of \tilde{g} be \tilde{B}_μ^α and \tilde{C}_α^μ . Let the slack-tights of \tilde{k} be $\tilde{B}_{\mu'}^\mu$ and $\tilde{C}_{\mu'}^\mu$. Let $\tilde{g}' \triangleq L_{[\tilde{k}]}(\tilde{g})$, then the slack-tights of \tilde{g}' are $\tilde{B}_{\mu'}^\alpha = \tilde{B}_\mu^\alpha \tilde{B}_{\mu'}^\mu$, and $\tilde{C}_{\alpha'}^{\mu'} = \tilde{C}_\alpha^\mu \tilde{C}_{\mu'}^{\mu'}$.

Define Dirac algebras γ^α , $\gamma^\mu = \tilde{C}_\alpha^\mu \gamma^\alpha$ and $\gamma^{\mu'} = \tilde{C}_\alpha^{\mu'} \gamma^\alpha$, such that $\gamma^\alpha \gamma^\beta + \gamma^\beta \gamma^\alpha = 2\tilde{\delta}^{\alpha\beta}$, $\gamma^\mu \gamma^\nu + \gamma^\nu \gamma^\mu = 2\tilde{G}^{\mu\nu}$, $\gamma^{\mu'} \gamma^{\nu'} + \gamma^{\nu'} \gamma^{\mu'} = 2\tilde{G}'^{\mu'\nu'}$, where $\tilde{G}^{\mu\nu} = \tilde{\delta}^{\alpha\beta} \tilde{C}_\alpha^\mu \tilde{C}_\beta^\nu$ is the metric tensor of \tilde{g} , and $\tilde{G}'^{\mu'\nu'} = \tilde{\delta}^{\alpha\beta} \tilde{C}_\alpha^{\mu'} \tilde{C}_\beta^{\nu'}$ is the metric tensor of \tilde{g}' .

Let $\tilde{\rho}$ be a charge of \tilde{f} , and \tilde{D} be the simple connection on (\tilde{M}, \tilde{g}) and (\tilde{M}, \tilde{g}') . According to Proposition 5.6.1, suppose $(\tilde{\Gamma}_{\tilde{g}})_{\nu\sigma}^\mu \gamma^\sigma = 0$, the Dirac equation of $\tilde{\rho}$ on (\tilde{M}, \tilde{g}) is $i\gamma^\mu \tilde{D}_\mu \psi = \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \psi$, and suppose $(\tilde{\Gamma}_{\tilde{g}'})_{\nu'\sigma'}^{\mu'} \gamma^{\sigma'} = 0$, the Dirac equation of $\tilde{\rho}$ on (\tilde{M}, \tilde{g}') is $i\gamma^{\mu'} \tilde{D}_{\mu'} \psi' = \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_{\tau'} \psi'$.

Then we have the following conclusions under transformation $L_{[\tilde{k}]} : \tilde{g} \mapsto \tilde{g}'$.

(1) $L_{[\tilde{k}]} : \tilde{D}_\mu \mapsto \tilde{D}_{\mu'} = \tilde{B}_{\mu'}^\mu (\tilde{D}_\mu - i\partial_\mu \theta)$.

(2) $L_{[\tilde{k}]} : \psi \mapsto \psi' = \psi e^{i\theta}$.

(3) For a selected $\tilde{\rho}$, the smooth real function θ is determined by $L_{[\tilde{k}]} \in GL(M)$. See Discussion 2.3.1 for the definition of general linear group $GL(M)$.

(4) Suppose \tilde{g} satisfies the condition of Proposition 5.6.1 , then $|\psi|$ and $|i\gamma^\mu \tilde{D}_\mu \psi|$ are both universal geometrical properties of \tilde{M} .

(5) The necessary condition of simultaneous $(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}})^\mu_{\nu\sigma} \gamma^\sigma = 0$ and $(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}'})^{\mu'}_{\nu'\sigma'} \gamma^{\sigma'} = 0$ is that $L_{[\tilde{k}]}$ is an orthogonal transformation.

Proof. Under the transformation $L_{[\tilde{k}]} : \tilde{g} \mapsto \tilde{g}'$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} L_{[\tilde{k}]} : \tilde{B}_\mu^\alpha &\mapsto \tilde{B}_{\mu'}^\alpha = B_\mu^\alpha \tilde{B}_{\mu'}^\mu, \quad \tilde{C}_\alpha^\mu \mapsto \tilde{C}_{\alpha'}^{\mu'} = \tilde{C}_\alpha^\mu \tilde{C}_{\mu'}^{\mu'}, \quad \tilde{B}_\tau^\tau \mapsto \tilde{B}_{\tau'}^\tau = B_\tau^\tau \tilde{B}_{\tau'}^\tau, \quad \tilde{C}_\tau^\tau \mapsto \tilde{C}_{\tau'}^\tau = \tilde{C}_\tau^\tau \tilde{C}_{\tau'}^{\tau'}. \\ L_{[\tilde{k}]} : \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} &\mapsto \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}^{\mu'}} = \tilde{B}_{\mu'}^\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu}, \quad \frac{d}{d\tilde{x}^\tau} \mapsto \frac{d}{d\tilde{x}^{\tau'}} = \tilde{B}_{\tau'}^\tau \frac{d}{d\tilde{x}^\tau}. \\ L_{[\tilde{k}]} : \rho_{;\mu} &\mapsto \rho_{;\mu'} = \rho_{;\mu} \tilde{B}_{\mu'}^\mu, \quad \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \mapsto \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_{\tau'} = \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \tilde{B}_{\tau'}^\tau. \\ L_{[\tilde{k}]} : \gamma^\mu &\mapsto \gamma^{\mu'} = \tilde{C}_{\mu'}^{\mu'} \gamma^\mu. \end{aligned}$$

According to equation(21) below, it is obtained that

$$L_{[\tilde{k}]} : [\tilde{\mathbb{P}}\tilde{\Gamma}_\mu] \mapsto [\tilde{\mathbb{P}}\tilde{\Gamma}_{\mu'}] = \tilde{B}_{\mu'}^\mu([\tilde{\mathbb{P}}\tilde{\Gamma}_\mu] + r_\mu).$$

Correspondingly, the transformation of \tilde{D}_μ is

$$\tilde{D}_\mu \triangleq \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} - i[\tilde{\mathbb{P}}\tilde{\Gamma}_\mu] \mapsto \tilde{D}_{\mu'} \triangleq \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}^{\mu'}} - i[\tilde{\mathbb{P}}\tilde{\Gamma}_{\mu'}] = \tilde{B}_{\mu'}^\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial \tilde{x}^\mu} - i\tilde{B}_{\mu'}^\mu([\tilde{\mathbb{P}}\tilde{\Gamma}_\mu] + r_\mu) = \tilde{B}_{\mu'}^\mu(\tilde{D}_\mu - ir_\mu).$$

The transformation of ψ is

$$\psi = f e^{i \int (\tilde{\mathbb{P}}_{;\mu} + [\tilde{\mathbb{P}}\tilde{\Gamma}_\mu]) d\tilde{x}^\mu} \mapsto \psi' = f e^{i \int (\tilde{\mathbb{P}}_{;\mu'} + [\tilde{\mathbb{P}}\tilde{\Gamma}_{\mu'}]) d\tilde{x}^{\mu'}} = f e^{i \int (\tilde{\mathbb{P}}_{;\mu'} + \tilde{B}_{\mu'}^\mu([\tilde{\mathbb{P}}\tilde{\Gamma}_\mu] + r_\mu)) d\tilde{x}^{\mu'}},$$

that is $\psi \mapsto \psi' = \psi e^{i \int r_\mu d\tilde{x}^\mu}$. Denote $\theta \triangleq \int r_\mu d\tilde{x}^\mu$, $r_\mu = \partial_\mu \theta$, thus we obtain $\psi \mapsto \psi' = \psi e^{i\theta}$.

We have proved (1) and (2) as the above. Now in order to prove (4), we can substitute the above transformations into $i\gamma^\mu \tilde{D}_\mu \psi = \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \psi$ of \tilde{g} .

$$\begin{aligned} i\gamma^\mu \tilde{D}_\mu \psi &= \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \psi \\ \Leftrightarrow i \left(\tilde{B}_{\mu'}^\mu \gamma^{\mu'} \right) \left(\tilde{C}_{\mu'}^{\nu'} (\tilde{D}_{\nu'} + i\partial_{\nu'} \theta) \right) \left(\psi' e^{-i\theta} \right) &= \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \left(\psi' e^{-i\theta} \right) \\ \Leftrightarrow i\gamma^{\mu'} (\tilde{D}_{\mu'} + i\partial_{\mu'} \theta) \left(\psi' e^{-i\theta} \right) &= \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \psi' e^{-i\theta} \\ \Leftrightarrow i\gamma^{\mu'} \left(\partial_{\mu'} - i[\tilde{\mathbb{P}}\tilde{\Gamma}_{\mu'}] + i\partial_{\mu'} \theta \right) \left(\psi' e^{-i\theta} \right) &= \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \psi' e^{-i\theta} \\ \Leftrightarrow i\gamma^{\mu'} \partial_{\mu'} \psi' e^{-i\theta} + i\gamma^{\mu'} \psi' \partial_{\mu'} e^{-i\theta} + \gamma^{\mu'} [\tilde{\mathbb{P}}\tilde{\Gamma}_{\mu'}] \psi' e^{-i\theta} - \gamma^{\mu'} \psi' e^{-i\theta} \partial_{\mu'} \theta &= \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \psi' e^{-i\theta} \\ \Leftrightarrow i\gamma^{\mu'} \partial_{\mu'} \psi' + \gamma^{\mu'} \psi' \partial_{\mu'} \theta + \gamma^{\mu'} [\tilde{\mathbb{P}}\tilde{\Gamma}_{\mu'}] \psi' - \gamma^{\mu'} \psi' \partial_{\mu'} \theta &= \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \psi' \\ \Leftrightarrow i\gamma^{\mu'} \partial_{\mu'} \psi' + \gamma^{\mu'} [\tilde{\mathbb{P}}\tilde{\Gamma}_{\mu'}] \psi' &= \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \psi' \\ \Leftrightarrow i\gamma^{\mu'} \tilde{D}_{\mu'} \psi' &= \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \psi'. \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, $i\gamma^{\mu'} \tilde{D}_{\mu'} \psi' = \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \psi' = \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \psi e^{i\theta} = (i\gamma^\mu \tilde{D}_\mu \psi) e^{i\theta}$, hence $|i\gamma^{\mu'} \tilde{D}_{\mu'} \psi'| = |i\gamma^\mu \tilde{D}_\mu \psi|$. In addition, it is evident that $|\psi'| = |\psi|$. It indicates that $|i\gamma^\mu \tilde{D}_\mu \psi|$ and $|\psi|$ remain unchanged under transformation $L_{[\tilde{k}]}$. Due to the arbitrariness of $[\tilde{k}]$, according to section 2.6 , $|i\gamma^\mu \tilde{D}_\mu \psi|$ is a universal geometrical property of \tilde{M} .

Next we consider (5). The above $i\gamma^{\mu'} \tilde{D}_{\mu'} \psi' = \tilde{\mathbb{M}}_\tau \psi'$ is obtained in the case where \tilde{g} satisfies the condition $(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}})^\mu_{\nu\sigma} \gamma^\sigma = 0$ of Proposition 5.6.1 . When \tilde{g}' satisfies condition $(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}'})^{\mu'}_{\nu'\sigma'} \gamma^{\sigma'} = 0$,

according to Proposition 5.6.1 we have $i\gamma^{\mu'}\tilde{D}_{\mu'}\psi' = \tilde{M}_{\tau'}\psi'$. Compare such two equations we obtain $\tilde{M}_{\tau} = \tilde{M}_{\tau'}$, that is $\tilde{M}_{\tau} = \tilde{B}_{\tau'}^T\tilde{M}_{\tau}$, or $\tilde{B}_{\tau'}^T = 1$. According to Definition 5.2.2, $L_{[\tilde{k}]}$ is an orthogonal transformation.

In order to prove (3), we need to calculate r_{μ} . According to Proposition 2.7.2, we have $(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}'})^{\mu'}_{\nu'\sigma'} = (\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}})^{\mu}_{\nu\sigma}\tilde{C}_{\nu'}^{\mu'}\tilde{B}_{\nu'}^{\nu}\tilde{B}_{\sigma'}^{\sigma} + (\tilde{I}_{\tilde{k}})^{\mu'}_{\nu'\sigma'}$. Due to Discussion 5.4.3 we know $[\tilde{\rho}\tilde{I}_{\mu}] \triangleq [\tilde{\rho}_{\omega\nu}\tilde{I}_{\mu}] \triangleq \tilde{\rho}_{\omega\chi}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}})^{\chi}_{\nu\mu} + \tilde{\rho}_{\chi\nu}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}})^{\chi}_{\omega\mu}$ and $[\tilde{\rho}'\tilde{I}_{\mu'}] \triangleq [\tilde{\rho}_{\omega'\nu'}\tilde{I}_{\mu'}] = \tilde{\rho}_{\omega'\chi'}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}'})^{\chi'}_{\nu'\mu'} + \tilde{\rho}_{\chi'\nu'}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}'})^{\chi'}_{\omega'\mu'}$.

$$\begin{aligned} [\tilde{\rho}\tilde{I}_{\mu'}] &\triangleq [\tilde{\rho}_{\omega\nu}\tilde{I}_{\mu'}] \triangleq \tilde{C}_{\omega'}^{\omega'}\tilde{C}_{\nu'}^{\nu'}[\tilde{\rho}_{\omega'\nu'}\tilde{I}_{\mu'}] = \tilde{C}_{\omega'}^{\omega'}\tilde{C}_{\nu'}^{\nu'}\left(\tilde{\rho}_{\omega'\chi'}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}'})^{\chi'}_{\nu'\mu'} + \tilde{\rho}_{\chi'\nu'}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}'})^{\chi'}_{\omega'\mu'}\right) \\ &= \tilde{C}_{\omega'}^{\omega'}\tilde{C}_{\nu'}^{\nu'}\left(\tilde{\rho}_{\omega'\chi'}\left((\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}})^{\chi}_{\rho\mu}\tilde{C}_{\chi}^{\rho}\tilde{B}_{\nu'}^{\rho}\tilde{B}_{\mu'}^{\mu} + (\tilde{I}_{\tilde{k}})^{\chi'}_{\nu'\mu'}\right) + \tilde{\rho}_{\chi'\nu'}\left((\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}})^{\chi}_{\sigma\mu}\tilde{C}_{\chi}^{\sigma}\tilde{B}_{\omega'}^{\sigma}\tilde{B}_{\mu'}^{\mu} + (\tilde{I}_{\tilde{k}})^{\chi'}_{\omega'\mu'}\right)\right) \\ &= \tilde{\rho}_{\omega\chi}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}})^{\chi}_{\nu\mu}\tilde{B}_{\mu'}^{\mu} + \tilde{\rho}_{\chi\nu}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}})^{\chi}_{\omega\mu}\tilde{B}_{\mu'}^{\mu} + \tilde{\rho}_{\omega\chi'}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{k}})^{\chi'}_{\nu'\mu'}\tilde{C}_{\nu'}^{\nu'} + \tilde{\rho}_{\chi'\nu'}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{k}})^{\chi'}_{\omega'\mu'}\tilde{C}_{\omega'}^{\omega'} \\ &= \tilde{\rho}_{\omega\chi}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}})^{\chi}_{\nu\mu}\tilde{B}_{\mu'}^{\mu} + \tilde{\rho}_{\chi\nu}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{g}})^{\chi}_{\omega\mu}\tilde{B}_{\mu'}^{\mu} + \tilde{\rho}_{\omega\chi}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{k}})^{\chi'}_{\nu'\sigma'}\tilde{C}_{\mu'}^{\sigma'}\tilde{B}_{\chi'}^{\chi}\tilde{C}_{\nu'}^{\nu'}\tilde{B}_{\mu'}^{\mu} + \tilde{\rho}_{\chi\nu}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{k}})^{\chi'}_{\omega'\sigma'}\tilde{C}_{\mu'}^{\sigma'}\tilde{B}_{\chi'}^{\chi}\tilde{C}_{\omega'}^{\omega'}\tilde{B}_{\mu'}^{\mu} \\ &= \left([\tilde{\rho}\tilde{I}_{\mu}] + \tilde{\rho}_{\omega\chi}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{k}})^{\chi'}_{\nu'\sigma'}\tilde{B}_{\chi'}^{\chi}\tilde{C}_{\nu'}^{\nu'}\tilde{C}_{\mu'}^{\sigma'} + \tilde{\rho}_{\chi\nu}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{k}})^{\chi'}_{\omega'\sigma'}\tilde{B}_{\chi'}^{\chi}\tilde{C}_{\omega'}^{\omega'}\tilde{C}_{\mu'}^{\sigma'}\right)\tilde{B}_{\mu'}^{\mu}, \end{aligned}$$

hence

$$\begin{aligned} [\tilde{P}\tilde{I}_{\mu'}] &= \left([\tilde{P}\tilde{I}_{\mu}] + \tilde{P}_{\omega\chi}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{k}})^{\chi'}_{\nu'\sigma'}\tilde{B}_{\chi'}^{\chi}\tilde{C}_{\nu'}^{\nu'}\tilde{C}_{\mu'}^{\sigma'} + \tilde{P}_{\chi\nu}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{k}})^{\chi'}_{\omega'\sigma'}\tilde{B}_{\chi'}^{\chi}\tilde{C}_{\omega'}^{\omega'}\tilde{C}_{\mu'}^{\sigma'}\right)\tilde{B}_{\mu'}^{\mu} \\ &= \left([\tilde{P}\tilde{I}_{\mu}] + r_{\omega\nu\mu}\right)\tilde{B}_{\mu'}^{\mu} = \left([\tilde{P}\tilde{I}_{\mu}] + r_{\mu}\right)\tilde{B}_{\mu'}^{\mu}, \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where $r_{\mu} \triangleq r_{\omega\nu\mu} \triangleq \tilde{P}_{\omega\chi}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{k}})^{\chi'}_{\nu'\sigma'}\tilde{B}_{\chi'}^{\chi}\tilde{C}_{\nu'}^{\nu'}\tilde{C}_{\mu'}^{\sigma'} + \tilde{P}_{\chi\nu}(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{k}})^{\chi'}_{\omega'\sigma'}\tilde{B}_{\chi'}^{\chi}\tilde{C}_{\omega'}^{\omega'}\tilde{C}_{\mu'}^{\sigma'}$.

We notice that \tilde{C} and \tilde{B} in the above r_{μ} are slack-tights of $[\tilde{k}]$, and $(\tilde{I}_{\tilde{k}})^{\mu'}_{\nu'\sigma'} = \frac{1}{2}\tilde{C}_{\mu'}^{\mu'}\left(\frac{\partial\tilde{B}_{\nu'}^{\mu}}{\partial\tilde{x}^{\sigma'}} + \frac{\partial\tilde{B}_{\sigma'}^{\mu}}{\partial\tilde{x}^{\nu'}}\right)$ is simple connection of $[\tilde{k}]$, therefore for a selected $\tilde{\rho}$ we know r_{μ} is uniquely determined by $L_{[\tilde{k}]}$, and furthermore $\theta \triangleq \int r_{\mu}d\tilde{x}^{\mu}$ is uniquely determined by $L_{[\tilde{k}]}$. In consideration of that $L_{[\tilde{k}]}$ of \tilde{M} is determined by $L_{[k]}$ of M , so r_{μ} and θ are finally determined by $L_{[k]}$. \square

Remark 5.6.2. Conclusions (1)(2)(3) are the reasons why Definition 2.3.3 calls $L_{[k]}$ a general gauge transformation. Conclusion (4) can also be called the **gauge invariance**, which until now has become a theorem, no longer been as a principle. This proposition indicates that $\psi \mapsto \psi'$ and $\tilde{D}_{\mu} \mapsto \tilde{D}_{\mu'}$ and gauge invariance such three things have the same mathematical origin, which is the intrinsic transformation $L_{[k]}$, and their physical connotations just only come from the axiom and corollary of section 3.1. $L_{[k]}$ is an element of general linear group, therefore gauge fields and gauge transformations defined by whatever subgroup of general linear group can always be characterized by $[k]$ and $L_{[k]}$. This is the intrinsic geometrical origin of gauge field and gauge transformation.

In summary, without the points of view of intrinsic geometry, it is impossible to clarify that there exists a more fundamental mathematical essence than gauge transformations $\psi \mapsto \psi'$ and $\tilde{D}_{\mu} \mapsto \tilde{D}_{\mu'}$. In consideration of Discussion 5.4.2, total superiority of points of view of intrinsic geometry can be brought into full play just only on manifold M rather than \tilde{M} . Complete details of various intrinsic geometrical properties of gauge field can thereby be presented on M . Hence, next we are going to stop the discussions about intrinsic geometry of \tilde{M} , but to focus on intrinsic

geometry of M . The intrinsic geometrical properties of the following sections still can only be described by simple connection, but not Levi-Civita connection.

Definition 5.6.1. Let there be a geometrical manifold (M, k) , such that $M = P \times N$, $r \triangleq \dim P = 3$ and $\mathfrak{D} \triangleq \dim M = 5$ or 6 or 8 .

(1) $\forall p \in M$, suppose the coordinate representation of $k(p)$ takes the form of $x^{m'} = x^{m'}(x^m)$, $x^{i'} = \delta_i^{i'} x^i$, and k satisfies **internal standard conditions**: (i) $G_{mn} = \text{const}$, (ii) when $m \neq n$, $G_{mn} = 0$. We say k is a **typical gauge field**, and $L_{[k]}$ is a **typical gauge transformation**.

(2) $\forall p \in M$, suppose the coordinate representation of $k(p)$ takes the form of $x^{m'} = x^{m'}(x^M)$, $x^{i'} = x^{i'}(x^i)$. We say k is a **typical gauge field with gravitation**, and $L_{[k]}$ is a **typical gravitational gauge transformation**.

6 Several intrinsic geometrical properties in 5-dimensional case

Definition 6.1. Suppose geometrical manifold (M, f) satisfies $\mathfrak{D} = r + 2 = 5$. $\forall p \in M$, the coordinate representation of $f(p)$ takes the form of $\xi^a = \xi^a(x^m)$, $\xi^s = \delta_i^s x^i$. And f satisfies the internal standard conditions of Definition 5.6.1 (1) and $G^{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} = G^{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}}$. We say f is a **weak and electromagnetic unified field**. The reason for such naming lies in the following proposition.

Proposition 6.1. Let the simple connection of the above (M, f) be Λ_{NP}^M and Λ_{MNP} . And let the coefficients of curvature of (M, f) be K_{NPQ}^M and K_{MNPQ} . Denote

$$\begin{cases} B_P \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P} + \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}) \\ A_P^3 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P} - \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}) \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} A_P^1 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} + \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}) \\ A_P^2 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} - \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}) \end{cases}.$$

$$\begin{cases} B_{PQ} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (K_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}PQ} + K_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)PQ}) \\ F_{PQ}^3 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (K_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}PQ} - K_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)PQ}) \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} F_{PQ}^1 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (K_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}PQ} + K_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)PQ}) \\ F_{PQ}^2 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (K_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}PQ} - K_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)PQ}) \end{cases}.$$

And denote $g \triangleq \sqrt{(G^{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)})^2 + (G^{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}})^2}$. Thus the following equations hold, and they are all intrinsic geometrical properties of (M, f) .

$$\begin{cases} B_{PQ} = \frac{\partial B_Q}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial B_P}{\partial x^Q}, \\ F_{PQ}^3 = \frac{\partial A_Q^3}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial A_P^3}{\partial x^Q} + g (A_P^1 A_Q^2 - A_P^2 A_Q^1), \\ F_{PQ}^1 = \frac{\partial A_Q^1}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial A_P^1}{\partial x^Q} + g (A_P^2 A_Q^3 - A_P^3 A_Q^2), \\ F_{PQ}^2 = \frac{\partial A_Q^2}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial A_P^2}{\partial x^Q} - g (A_P^3 A_Q^1 - A_P^1 A_Q^3). \end{cases}$$

Proof. According to the definition, the slack-tights of f satisfy that $B_m^s = 0$, $C_a^i = 0$. $B_i^s = \delta_i^s$, $B_i^a = 0$, $C_s^i = \delta_s^i$, $C_s^m = 0$. The metric of f satisfies that $G_{mn} = 0(m \neq n)$, $G_{mn} = \text{const}$,

$G_{MN} \triangleq \delta_{AB} B_M^A B_N^B$ and $G^{MN} = \delta^{AB} C_A^M C_B^N$. Concretely:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} G_{ij} = \delta_{st} B_i^s B_j^t + \delta_{ab} B_i^a B_j^b = \delta_{st} \delta_i^s \delta_j^t = \delta_{ij} \\ G_{in} = \delta_{st} B_i^s B_n^t + \delta_{ab} B_i^a B_n^b = 0 \\ G_{mj} = \delta_{st} B_m^s B_j^t + \delta_{ab} B_m^a B_j^b = 0 \\ G_{mn} = B_m^{\mathfrak{D}-1} B_n^{\mathfrak{D}-1} + B_m^{\mathfrak{D}} B_n^{\mathfrak{D}} \end{array} \right. , \left\{ \begin{array}{l} G^{ij} = \delta^{st} C_s^i C_t^j = \delta^{st} \delta_s^i \delta_t^j = \delta^{ij} \\ G^{in} = \delta^{st} C_s^i C_t^n = 0 \\ G^{mj} = \delta^{st} C_s^m C_t^j = 0 \\ G^{mn} = C_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^m C_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^n + C_{\mathfrak{D}}^m C_{\mathfrak{D}}^n \end{array} \right.$$

Calculate the simple connection of f , that is $\Lambda_{NP}^M \triangleq \frac{1}{2} C_A^M \left(\frac{\partial B_N^A}{\partial x^P} + \frac{\partial B_P^A}{\partial x^N} \right)$ and $\Lambda_{MNP} \triangleq G_{MM'} \Lambda_{NP}^{M'}$, then we obtain

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Lambda_{NP}^i = 0 \\ \Lambda_{jk}^m = 0 \\ \Lambda_{nP}^m = \frac{1}{2} C_a^m \left(\frac{\partial B_n^a}{\partial x^P} + \frac{\partial B_P^a}{\partial x^n} \right) \\ \Lambda_{Np}^m = \frac{1}{2} C_a^m \left(\frac{\partial B_N^a}{\partial x^p} + \frac{\partial B_p^a}{\partial x^N} \right) \end{array} \right. , \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Lambda_{iNP} = G_{iM'} \Lambda_{NP}^{M'} = G_{ii'} \Lambda_{NP}^{i'} = 0 \\ \Lambda_{mjk} = G_{mM'} \Lambda_{jk}^{M'} = G_{mm'} \Lambda_{jk}^{m'} = 0 \\ \Lambda_{mnp} = \frac{1}{2} \delta_{ab} B_m^b \left(\frac{\partial B_n^a}{\partial x^p} + \frac{\partial B_p^a}{\partial x^n} \right) \\ \Lambda_{mNp} = \frac{1}{2} \delta_{ab} B_m^b \left(\frac{\partial B_N^a}{\partial x^p} + \frac{\partial B_p^a}{\partial x^N} \right) \end{array} \right.$$

Calculate the coefficients of curvature of f , that is

$$K_{nPQ}^m \triangleq \frac{\partial \Lambda_{nQ}^m}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Lambda_{nP}^m}{\partial x^Q} + \Lambda_{HP}^m \Lambda_{nQ}^H - \Lambda_{nP}^H \Lambda_{HQ}^m$$

and

$$K_{mnPQ} \triangleq G_{mM'} K_{nPQ}^{M'} = G_{mm'} K_{nPQ}^{m'}$$

then we obtain

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} K_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)PQ}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} = \frac{\partial \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q}^{\mathfrak{D}-1}}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1}}{\partial x^Q} + \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q}^{\mathfrak{D}} - \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}} \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}Q}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \\ K_{\mathfrak{D}PQ}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} = \frac{\partial \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}Q}^{\mathfrak{D}-1}}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1}}{\partial x^Q} + \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}Q}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} + \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}Q}^{\mathfrak{D}} - \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} - \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}} \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}Q}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \\ K_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)PQ}^{\mathfrak{D}} = \frac{\partial \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q}^{\mathfrak{D}}}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}}}{\partial x^Q} + \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}} \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} + \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}} \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q}^{\mathfrak{D}} - \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q}^{\mathfrak{D}} \\ \quad - \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}} \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}Q}^{\mathfrak{D}} \\ K_{\mathfrak{D}PQ}^{\mathfrak{D}} = \frac{\partial \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}Q}^{\mathfrak{D}}}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}}}{\partial x^Q} + \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}} \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}Q}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} - \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q}^{\mathfrak{D}} \end{array} \right.$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} K_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)PQ} = \frac{\partial \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q}}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}}{\partial x^Q} \\ \quad + G^{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}} (\Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q} - \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}Q}) \\ K_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)PQ} = \frac{\partial \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q}}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}}{\partial x^Q} + G^{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}} (\Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P} \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q} - \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}Q}) \\ \quad + G^{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} (\Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q} - \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q}) \\ K_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}PQ} = \frac{\partial \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}Q}}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P}}{\partial x^Q} + G^{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}} (\Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}Q} - \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P} \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}Q}) \\ \quad + G^{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} (\Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}Q} - \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q}) \\ K_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}PQ} = \frac{\partial \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}Q}}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P}}{\partial x^Q} + G^{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} (\Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}Q} - \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q}) \end{array} \right.$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} B_{PQ} &\triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (K_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}PQ} + K_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)PQ}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{\partial (\Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}Q} + \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q})}{\partial x^P} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{\partial (\Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P} + \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P})}{\partial x^Q} \\ &= \frac{\partial B_Q}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial B_P}{\partial x^Q}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} F_{PQ}^3 &\triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (K_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}PQ} - K_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)PQ}) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{\partial \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}Q}}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P}}{\partial x^Q} + G^{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} (\Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}Q} - \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q}) \right) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{\partial \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q}}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}}{\partial x^Q} + G^{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}} (\Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q} - \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}Q}) \right) \\ &= \frac{\partial A_Q^3}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial A_P^3}{\partial x^Q} + g (\Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}Q} - \Lambda_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} \Lambda_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)Q}) \\ &= \frac{\partial A_Q^3}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial A_P^3}{\partial x^Q} + g (A_P^1 A_Q^2 - A_P^2 A_Q^1). \end{aligned}$$

Similarly we also obtain $F_{PQ}^1 = \frac{\partial A_Q^1}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial A_P^1}{\partial x^Q} + g (A_P^2 A_Q^3 - A_P^3 A_Q^2)$ and $F_{PQ}^2 = \frac{\partial A_Q^2}{\partial x^P} - \frac{\partial A_P^2}{\partial x^Q} - g (A_P^3 A_Q^1 - A_P^1 A_Q^3)$. \square

Remark 6.1. Comparing the conclusions of the above proposition and the Glashow-Weinberg-Salam theory of physics, we know that this proposition gives another mathematical treatment of weak and electromagnetic field of physics. It does not abstractly define gauge potentials as the adjoint representation of group $U(1) \times SU(2)$, but gives concrete intrinsic geometrical constructions.

In addition, the following proposition will prove the characteristics of chirality of leptons from the perspective of intrinsic geometry. This is beyond the reach of the traditional method that abstractly regards leptons as the fundamental representation of group $U(1) \times SU(2)$.

Definition 6.2. Suppose f and g both satisfy Definition 6.1 . According to Definition 3.3.1.1 and Definition 3.3.5.2 , let ρ_{mn} of f evolve on (M, g) . Then $l \triangleq (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}, \rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}})$ is called **electric charged lepton**, and $\nu \triangleq (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)}, \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}})$ is called **neutrino**. l and ν are uniformly called **leptons**, denoted by L . And $L \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$ is called **left-handed lepton**, $L \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}$ is called **right-handed lepton**, denoted by

$$\begin{cases} l_L \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}}), & \begin{cases} \nu_L \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}}), \\ \nu_R \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)} - \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}}). \end{cases} \\ l_R \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} - \rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}}), & \end{cases}$$

On (M, g) we define

$$\begin{cases} W_P^1 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} + \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}), & \begin{cases} Z_P \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} + \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P}), \\ A_P \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} - \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P}), \end{cases} \\ W_P^2 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} - \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}), & \end{cases}$$

and say the intrinsic geometrical property A_P is **electromagnetic potential**, Z_P is **Z potential**, W_P^1 and W_P^2 are **W potential**. Then denote

$$\begin{cases} W_P^+ \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (W_P^1 - iW_P^2) \\ W_P^- \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (W_P^1 + iW_P^2) \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} l_L^+ = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (l_L - il_R) \\ l_L^- = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (l_L + il_R) \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} l_R^+ \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (l_R - il_L) \\ l_R^- \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (l_R + il_L) \end{cases}.$$

Proposition 6.2. If (M, g) satisfies symmetry condition $\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} = \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}$, then intrinsic geometrical properties l and ν of f satisfy the following conclusions on (M, g) .

$$\begin{cases} l_{L;P} = \partial_P l_L - gl_L Z_P - gl_R A_P - g\nu_L W_P^1, \\ l_{R;P} = \partial_P l_R - gl_R Z_P - gl_L A_P, \\ \nu_{L;P} = \partial_P \nu_L - g\nu_L Z_P - gl_L W_P^1, \\ \nu_{R;P} = \partial_P \nu_R - g\nu_R Z_P. \end{cases} \quad \begin{cases} l_{L;P}^- = \partial_P l_L^- - gl_L^- Z_P - gl_R^- A_P - g\nu_L W_P^-, \\ l_{L;P}^+ = \partial_P l_L^+ - gl_L^+ Z_P - gl_R^+ A_P - g\nu_L W_P^+, \\ l_{R;P}^- = \partial_P l_R^- - gl_R^- Z_P - gl_L^- A_P - ig\nu_L W_P^-, \\ l_{R;P}^+ = \partial_P l_R^+ - gl_R^+ Z_P - gl_L^+ A_P + ig\nu_L W_P^+, \\ \nu_{L;P} = \partial_P \nu_L - g\nu_L Z_P - gl_L^+ W_P^- - gl_L^- W_P^+, \\ \nu_{R;P} = \partial_P \nu_R - g\nu_R Z_P. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Due to $\rho_{mn;P} = \partial_P \rho_{mn} - \rho_{Hn} \Gamma_{mP}^H - \rho_{mH} \Gamma_{nP}^H = \partial_P \rho_{mn} - \rho_{hn} \Gamma_{mP}^h - \rho_{mh} \Gamma_{nP}^h$, we have

$$\begin{cases} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1);P} = \partial_P \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} - 2\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} - (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}}) \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}}, \\ \rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D};P} = \partial_P \rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}} - 2\rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}} \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}} - (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}}) \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1}, \\ \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1);P} = \partial_P \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)} - (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}}) - \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} + \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}}), \\ \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D};P} = \partial_P \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}} - (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}}) - \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} + \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}}). \end{cases}$$

$$\Rightarrow \begin{cases} l_{L;P} = \partial_P l_L - \sqrt{2}\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} - \sqrt{2}\rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}} \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}} - g\nu_L W_P^1, \\ l_{R;P} = \partial_P l_R - \sqrt{2}\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} + \sqrt{2}\rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}} \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}}, \\ \nu_{L;P} = \partial_P \nu_L - gl_L W_P^1 - \nu_L (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} + \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}}), \\ \nu_{R;P} = \partial_P \nu_R - \nu_R (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} + \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}}). \end{cases}$$

$$\Rightarrow \begin{cases} l_{L;P} = \partial_P l_L - gl_L Z_P - gl_R A_P - g\nu_L W_P^1, \\ l_{R;P} = \partial_P l_R - gl_R Z_P - gl_L A_P, \\ \nu_{L;P} = \partial_P \nu_L - g\nu_L Z_P - gl_L W_P^1, \\ \nu_{R;P} = \partial_P \nu_R - g\nu_R Z_P. \end{cases} \quad \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} l_{L;P}^- = \partial_P l_L^- - gl_L^- Z_P - gl_R^- A_P - g\nu_L W_P^-, \\ l_{L;P}^+ = \partial_P l_L^+ - gl_L^+ Z_P - gl_R^+ A_P - g\nu_L W_P^+, \\ l_{R;P}^- = \partial_P l_R^- - gl_R^- Z_P - gl_L^- A_P - ig\nu_L W_P^-, \\ l_{R;P}^+ = \partial_P l_R^+ - gl_R^+ Z_P - gl_L^+ A_P + ig\nu_L W_P^+, \\ \nu_{L;P} = \partial_P \nu_L - g\nu_L Z_P - gl_L^+ W_P^- - gl_L^- W_P^+, \\ \nu_{R;P} = \partial_P \nu_R - g\nu_R Z_P. \end{cases}$$

□

Discussion 6.1. According to Discussion 2.6.2, the transformation group of intrinsic geometry is the subgroup $\{e\}$ which is uniquely made up of the unit element e of general linear group. Its symmetry is the smallest and never breaks, because it is too small to break. In other words, intrinsic geometry is the largest geometry of geometrical manifold, and its geometrical properties

are the richest, so that any irregular smooth shape is an intrinsic geometrical property, it thereby can anyway be precisely characterized by slack-tights.

We can obtain whatever subgeometry of intrinsic geometry by way of restricting slack-tights via some *symmetry conditions*, like what section 2.4 and section 2.5 do. $\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} = \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}$ in Proposition 6.2 is just exactly such a symmetry condition, which can be regarded as an equivalent condition to define a kind of subgeometry of intrinsic geometry to describe the weak and electromagnetic unified field. In summary:

(1) The traditional physics starts from a very large symmetry group, and reduces symmetries in way of symmetry breaking to approach the target geometry.

(2) The point of view of intrinsic geometry starts from the smallest symmetry group $\{e\}$, and adds symmetries in way of symmetry condition to approach the target geometry.

Such two ways must lead to the same destination. They both go towards the same specific geometry.

From the perspective of unification of time and space, it is better to focus on concrete geometrical construction than to focus on abstract algebraic structure, and it is better to study how to add symmetry conditions than to introduce symmetry breaking.

Remark 6.2. If we do not consider from the perspective of intrinsic geometry, the Hilbert's 6th problem can never be solved at the most basic level. In addition:

(1) Proposition 6.2 gives the mathematical essence of Glashow-Weinberg-Salam theory from the perspective of intrinsic geometry, even the coupling constant g becomes an intrinsic geometrical property. Furthermore, we are able to study Dirac equations of l_L, l_R, ν_L, ν_R in way of section 5.6, and moreover to construct complex-valued Lagrangian density, and to treat QFT from the perspective of intrinsic geometry in sense of section 3.4. However, such topics are beyond the subject of this paper, we will not discuss them.

(2) We notice that the coupling constants of Z_P and A_P in Proposition 6.2 satisfy $g_Z = g_A = g$, which is comprehensible, because it is just a conclusion at the most basic level. Only when we consider a kind of medium that is called Higgs field, there appears a Weinberg angle and thereby we have $g_Z \neq g_A$. When we consider Higgs boson as a zero-spin pair of neutrinos, the Higgs boson will lose its fundamentality and it thereby does not have enough importance in theory of the most basic level. This paper does not concern such non-fundamental objects and properties.

(3) The mixing of leptons of three generations will automatically appear as an intrinsic geometrical property on the geometrical manifold of Definition 8.1.

7 Several intrinsic geometrical properties in 6-dimensional case

Definition 7.1. Suppose geometrical manifold (M, f) satisfies $\mathfrak{D} = r + 3 = 6$. $\forall p \in M$, the coordinate representation of $f(p)$ takes the form of $\xi^a = \xi^a(x^m)$, $\xi^s = \delta_i^s x^i$. And f satisfies the

internal standard conditions of Definition 5.6.1 (1) and $G^{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} = G^{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} = G^{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}}$. We say f is a **strong interaction field**.

Definition 7.2. Suppose f and g both satisfy Definition 7.1 . According to Definition 3.3.1.1 and Definition 3.3.5.2 , let ρ_{mn} of f evolve on (M, g) . Define

$$\begin{cases} d_1 \triangleq (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}, \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) \\ d_2 \triangleq (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}, \rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}}) \\ d_3 \triangleq (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}}, \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \end{cases}, \begin{cases} u_1 \triangleq (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}, \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \\ u_2 \triangleq (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}}, \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) \\ u_3 \triangleq (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-2)}, \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)\mathfrak{D}}) \end{cases}.$$

We say d_1 and u_1 are **red color charge**, d_2 and u_2 are **blue color charge**, d_3 and u_3 are **green color charge**. Then d_1, d_2, d_3 are called **down-type color charge**, uniformly denoted by d , and u_1, u_2, u_3 are called **up-type color charge**, uniformly denoted by u . d and u are uniformly called **color charge**, denoted by q . We say $q\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$ is **left-handed color charge**, and $q\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}$ are called **right-handed color charge**. They are

$$\begin{cases} d_{1L} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) \\ d_{2L} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}}) \\ d_{3L} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \end{cases}, \begin{cases} d_{1R} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} - \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) \\ d_{2R} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} - \rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}}) \\ d_{3R} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}} - \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \end{cases}.$$

$$\begin{cases} u_{1L} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \\ u_{2L} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) \\ u_{3L} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)\mathfrak{D}}) \end{cases}, \begin{cases} u_{1R} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} - \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \\ u_{2R} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}} - \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) \\ u_{3R} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-2)} - \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)\mathfrak{D}}) \end{cases}.$$

On (M, g) we denote

$$g_s \triangleq \sqrt{(G^{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)})^2 + (G^{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}})^2} = \sqrt{(G^{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)})^2 + (G^{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)})^2} = \sqrt{(G^{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)})^2 + (G^{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}})^2}.$$

$$\begin{cases} U_P^1 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)P} + \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}) \\ V_P^1 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)P} - \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}) \end{cases}, \begin{cases} X_P^{23} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} + \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-2)P}) \\ Y_P^{23} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} - \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-2)P}) \end{cases},$$

$$\begin{cases} U_P^2 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} + \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P}) \\ V_P^2 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} - \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P}) \end{cases}, \begin{cases} X_P^{31} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} + \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}) \\ Y_P^{31} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} - \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}) \end{cases},$$

$$\begin{cases} U_P^3 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P} + \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)P}) \\ V_P^3 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P} - \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)P}) \end{cases}, \begin{cases} X_P^{12} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-2)P} + \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)\mathfrak{D}P}) \\ Y_P^{12} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-2)P} - \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)\mathfrak{D}P}) \end{cases}.$$

We notice that there are just only three independent ones in $U_P^1, U_P^2, U_P^3, V_P^1, V_P^2$ and V_P^3 . Without loss of generality, let

$$\begin{cases} R_P \triangleq a_R U_P^1 + b_R U_P^2 + c_R U_P^3 \\ S_P \triangleq a_S U_P^1 + b_S U_P^2 + c_S U_P^3 \\ T_P \triangleq a_T U_P^1 + b_T U_P^2 + c_T U_P^3 \end{cases}, \begin{cases} U_P^1 \triangleq \alpha_R R_P + \alpha_S S_P + \alpha_T T_P \\ U_P^2 \triangleq \beta_R R_P + \beta_S S_P + \beta_T T_P \\ U_P^3 \triangleq \gamma_R R_P + \gamma_S S_P + \gamma_T T_P \end{cases},$$

where the coefficients matrix are non-singular.

Proposition 7.1. Let λ_a ($a = 1, 2, \dots, 8$) be the Gell-Mann matrices, and $T_a \triangleq \frac{1}{2}\lambda_a$ the generators of $SU(3)$ group. When (M, g) satisfies symmetry condition $\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)P} + \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} + \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P} = 0$, denote

$$A_P \triangleq \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} A_P^{11} & A_P^{12} & A_P^{13} \\ A_P^{21} & A_P^{22} & A_P^{23} \\ A_P^{31} & A_P^{32} & A_P^{33} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \begin{cases} A_P^{32} \triangleq X_P^{23} + iY_P^{23} \\ A_P^{23} \triangleq X_P^{23} - iY_P^{23} \\ A_P^{11} \triangleq S_P + \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}}T_P \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} A_P^{31} \triangleq X_P^{31} + iY_P^{31} \\ A_P^{13} \triangleq X_P^{31} - iY_P^{31} \\ A_P^{22} \triangleq -S_P + \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}}T_P \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} A_P^{21} \triangleq X_P^{12} + iY_P^{12} \\ A_P^{12} \triangleq X_P^{12} - iY_P^{12} \\ A_P^{33} \triangleq -\frac{2}{\sqrt{6}}T_P \end{cases}.$$

Thus, $A_P = T_a A_P^a$ if and only if $A_P^1 \triangleq X_P^{12}$, $A_P^2 \triangleq Y_P^{12}$, $A_P^3 \triangleq S_P$, $A_P^4 \triangleq X_P^{31}$, $A_P^5 \triangleq Y_P^{31}$, $A_P^6 \triangleq X_P^{23}$, $A_P^7 \triangleq Y_P^{23}$ and $A_P^8 \triangleq T_P$.

Proof. We just need to substitute the Gell-Mann matrices

$$\lambda_1 \triangleq \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda_2 \triangleq \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda_3 \triangleq \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda_4 \triangleq \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\lambda_5 \triangleq \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda_6 \triangleq \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda_7 \triangleq \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda_8 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -2 \end{pmatrix}.$$

into $A_P = T_a A_P^a$ and directly verify them. \square

Remark 7.1. On one hand, the above proposition indicates that Definition 7.1 is another mathematical treatment of strong interaction field. It does not anymore define the gauge potentials abstractly like QCD based on $SU(3)$ theory, but gives concrete intrinsic geometrical constructions. On the other hand, the above proposition implies that if we take appropriate symmetry conditions, the algebraic properties of $SU(3)$ group can be described by the transformation group $GL(3, \mathbb{R})$ of internal space of g . In other words, exponential map $e : GL(3, \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow U(3)$, $[B_m^a] \mapsto e^{iT_m^a B_m^a}$ defines a covering homomorphism, and $SU(3)$ is a subgroup of $U(3)$.

8 Several intrinsic geometrical properties in 8-dimensional case

Definition 8.1. Suppose geometrical manifold (M, f) satisfies $\mathfrak{D} = r + 5 = 8$. $\forall p \in M$, the coordinate representation of $f(p)$ takes the form of $\xi^a = \xi^a(x^m)$, $\xi^s = \delta_i^s x^i$. And f satisfies the internal standard conditions of Definition 5.6.1 (1) and $G^{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} = G^{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}$ and $G^{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} = G^{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} = G^{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}}$. We say f is a **typical unified gauge field**.

Definition 8.2. Suppose f and g both satisfy Definition 8.1. According to Definition 3.3.1.1 and Definition 3.3.5.2, let ρ_{mn} of f evolve on (M, g) . Define

$$\begin{cases} l \triangleq (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}, \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \\ d_1 \triangleq (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}, \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) \\ d_2 \triangleq (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}, \rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}}) \\ d_3 \triangleq (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}}, \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} \nu \triangleq (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}, \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \\ u_1 \triangleq (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}, \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \\ u_2 \triangleq (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}}, \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) \\ u_3 \triangleq (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-2)}, \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)\mathfrak{D}}) \end{cases}.$$

And Denote

$$\begin{cases} l_L \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \\ l_R \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} - \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} \nu_L \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \\ \nu_R \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} - \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \end{cases},$$

$$\begin{cases} d_{1L} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) \\ d_{2L} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}}) \\ d_{3L} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} d_{1R} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} - \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) \\ d_{2R} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} - \rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}}) \\ d_{3R} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}} - \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \end{cases},$$

$$\begin{cases} u_{1L} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \\ u_{2L} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) \\ u_{3L} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)\mathfrak{D}}) \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} u_{1R} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} - \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \\ u_{2R} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}} - \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) \\ u_{3R} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-2)} - \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)\mathfrak{D}}) \end{cases}.$$

On (M, g) we denote

$$\begin{cases} g \triangleq \sqrt{(G^{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-4)})^2 + (G^{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-3)})^2}, \\ g_s \triangleq \sqrt{(G^{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)})^2 + (G^{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}})^2} = \sqrt{(G^{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)})^2 + (G^{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)})^2} = \sqrt{(G^{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)})^2 + (G^{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}})^2}, \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} Z_P \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-4)P} + \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-3)P}) \\ A_P \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-4)P} - \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-3)P}) \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} W_P^1 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-3)P} + \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-4)P}) \\ W_P^2 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-3)P} - \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-4)P}) \end{cases},$$

$$\begin{cases} U_P^1 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)P} + \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}) \\ V_P^1 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)P} - \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}) \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} X_P^{23} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} + \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-2)P}) \\ Y_P^{23} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} - \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-2)P}) \end{cases},$$

$$\begin{cases} U_P^2 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} + \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P}) \\ V_P^2 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} - \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P}) \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} X_P^{31} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} + \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}) \\ Y_P^{31} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}P} - \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}) \end{cases},$$

$$\begin{cases} U_P^3 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P} + \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)P}) \\ V_P^3 \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P} - \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)P}) \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} X_P^{12} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-2)P} + \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)\mathfrak{D}P}) \\ Y_P^{12} \triangleq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (\Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-2)P} - \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)\mathfrak{D}P}) \end{cases}.$$

Definition 8.3. Define the symmetry condition of unification:

(1) Basic conditions, No.1:

$$\begin{cases} G^{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} = G^{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}, \\ G^{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} = G^{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} = G^{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}}, \end{cases}$$

(2) Basic conditions, No.2:

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-4)P} = \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-3)P}, \\ \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)P} + \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)P} + \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}P} = 0, \end{cases}$$

(3) MNS mixing conditions of weak interaction, No.1:

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} = c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-3}, & \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} = c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-4}, & \begin{cases} c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} = c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}-2}, \\ c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} = c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}-1}, \\ c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}} = c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}}. \end{cases} \\ \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} = c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-3}, & \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} = c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-4}, \\ \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)P}^{\mathfrak{D}} = c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-3}, & \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)P}^{\mathfrak{D}} = c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-4}, \end{cases}$$

(4) MNS mixing conditions of weak interaction, No.2:

$$\begin{cases} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}, & \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}, \\ \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}, & \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}, \\ \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)} = \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)}, & \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}}, \end{cases}$$

(5) CKM mixing conditions of strong interaction, No.1:

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} = c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-3}, & \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} = c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-4}, & \begin{cases} c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} = c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} = c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-4}, \\ c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} = c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} = c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-3}, \end{cases} \\ \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} = c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-3}, & \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} = c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-4}, \\ \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} = c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-3}, & \Gamma_{\mathfrak{D}P}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} = c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} \Gamma_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)P}^{\mathfrak{D}-4}, \end{cases}$$

(6) CKM mixing conditions of strong interaction, No.2:

$$\begin{cases} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} = \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)}, & \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}}, \\ \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} = \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)}, & \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}}, \end{cases}$$

where c_n^m are constants.

Proposition 8.1. When (M, g) satisfies the symmetry conditions of Definition 8.3, denote

$$\begin{aligned} l' \triangleq & \left(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}-2}}{2} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \right. \\ & + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}-1}}{2} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}}}{2} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}}), \\ & \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}-2}}{2} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \\ & \left. + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}-1}}{2} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}}}{2} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}}) \right). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nu' \triangleq & \left(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}-2}}{2} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \right. \\ & + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}-1}}{2} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}}}{2} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}}), \\ & \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}-2}}{2} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \\ & \left. + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}-1}}{2} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}}}{2} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}}) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the intrinsic geometrical properties l and ν of f satisfy the following conclusions on (M, g) .

$$\begin{cases} l_{L;P} = \partial_P l_L - g_L Z_P - g_L A_P - g \nu'_L W_P^1, \\ l_{R;P} = \partial_P l_R - g_L Z_P - g_L A_P, \\ \nu_{L;P} = \partial_P \nu_L - g \nu_L Z_P - g l'_L W_P^1, \\ \nu_{R;P} = \partial_P \nu_R - g \nu_R Z_P. \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

Proof. First, ρ_{mn} of f can be calculated as below:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{mn;P} &= \partial_P \rho_{mn} - \rho_{Hn} \Gamma_{mP}^H - \rho_{mH} \Gamma_{nP}^H \\ &= \partial_P \rho_{mn} - \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)n} \Gamma_{mP}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} - \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)n} \Gamma_{mP}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} - \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)n} \Gamma_{mP}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} - \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)n} \Gamma_{mP}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} - \rho_{\mathfrak{D}n} \Gamma_{mP}^{\mathfrak{D}} \\ &\quad - \rho_{m(\mathfrak{D}-4)} \Gamma_{nP}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} - \rho_{m(\mathfrak{D}-3)} \Gamma_{nP}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} - \rho_{m(\mathfrak{D}-2)} \Gamma_{nP}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} - \rho_{m(\mathfrak{D}-1)} \Gamma_{nP}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} - \rho_{m\mathfrak{D}} \Gamma_{nP}^{\mathfrak{D}}. \end{aligned}$$

According to Definition 8.2 and Definition 8.3, by calculation we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} l_{L;P} &= \partial_P l_L - g_L Z_P - g_L A_P - g \nu_L W_P^1 \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \left[c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) + c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) \right] \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \left[c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) + c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) \right] \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \left[c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}}) + c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}}) \right] \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1, \end{aligned}$$

$$l_{R;P} = \partial_P l_R - g_L Z_P - g_L A_P,$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_{L;P} &= \partial_P \nu_L - g \nu_L Z_P - g l_L W_P^1 \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \left[c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) + c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \right] \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \left[c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) + c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \right] \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \left[c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}}) + c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \right] \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1, \end{aligned}$$

$$\nu_{R;P} = \partial_P \nu_R - g \nu_R Z_P.$$

Then, according to definitions of l' and ν' , we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} l'_L &= l_L \\ &\quad + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}-2}}{2\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}-1}}{2\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}}}{2\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}}) \\ &\quad + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}-2}}{2\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}-1}}{2\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}}}{2\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nu'_L &= \nu_L \\ &\quad + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}-2}}{2\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}-1}}{2\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-3}^{\mathfrak{D}}}{2\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}}) \\ &\quad + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}-2}}{2\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}) + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}-1}}{2\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}) + \frac{c_{\mathfrak{D}-4}^{\mathfrak{D}}}{2\sqrt{2}} (\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}}). \end{aligned}$$

Substitute them into the previous equations, and we obtain that

$$\begin{cases} l_{L;P} = \partial_P l_L - g l_L Z_P - g l_R A_P - g \nu'_L W_P^1, \\ l_{R;P} = \partial_P l_R - g l_R Z_P - g l_L A_P, \end{cases}, \quad \begin{cases} \nu_{L;P} = \partial_P \nu_L - g \nu_L Z_P - g l'_L W_P^1, \\ \nu_{R;P} = \partial_P \nu_R - g \nu_R Z_P. \end{cases}$$

□

Remark 8.1. Reviewing Discussion 6.1 , we know the above proposition gives the mathematical essence of MNS mixing of weak interaction from the perspective of intrinsic geometry. In mathematics, the MNS mixing automatically appears as an intrinsic geometrical property, therefore it is not necessary to postulate artificially like that in physics.

In physics, e , μ and τ have just only ontological differences, but they have no difference in mathematical connotation. By contrast, Proposition 8.1 tells us that leptons of three generations should be constructed by different linear combinations of $\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}$, $\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}$, $\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}$, $\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}$, $\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)}$, $\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}}$, $\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}$, $\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)}$, $\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}$, $\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)}$, $\rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)}$ and $\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}}$. Thus, e , μ and τ may have concrete and distinguishable mathematical connotations. For example, suppose a_τ , b_τ , $a_{\tau_n}^m$, $b_{\tau_n}^m$ are constants, then we can imagine that

$$\begin{cases} e \triangleq l = (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}, \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}), \\ \nu_e \triangleq \nu = (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}, \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}). \\ \mu \triangleq a_\mu e + \frac{1}{2} \left(a_{\mu_{\mathfrak{D}-4}}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + a_{\mu_{\mathfrak{D}-4}}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + a_{\mu_{\mathfrak{D}-4}}^{\mathfrak{D}} \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)}, \right. \\ \quad \left. a_{\mu_{\mathfrak{D}-3}}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + a_{\mu_{\mathfrak{D}-3}}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + a_{\mu_{\mathfrak{D}-3}}^{\mathfrak{D}} \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)} \right). \\ \nu_\mu \triangleq b_\mu \nu_e + \frac{1}{2} \left(b_{\mu_{\mathfrak{D}-3}}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + b_{\mu_{\mathfrak{D}-3}}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)} + b_{\mu_{\mathfrak{D}-3}}^{\mathfrak{D}} \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)}, \right. \\ \quad \left. b_{\mu_{\mathfrak{D}-4}}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + b_{\mu_{\mathfrak{D}-4}}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)} + b_{\mu_{\mathfrak{D}-4}}^{\mathfrak{D}} \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)} \right). \\ \tau \triangleq a_\tau \mu + \frac{1}{2} \left(a_{\tau_{\mathfrak{D}-4}}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + a_{\tau_{\mathfrak{D}-4}}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + a_{\tau_{\mathfrak{D}-4}}^{\mathfrak{D}} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}}, \right. \\ \quad \left. a_{\tau_{\mathfrak{D}-3}}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + a_{\tau_{\mathfrak{D}-3}}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + a_{\tau_{\mathfrak{D}-3}}^{\mathfrak{D}} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}} \right). \\ \nu_\tau \triangleq b_\tau \nu_\mu + \frac{1}{2} \left(b_{\tau_{\mathfrak{D}-3}}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + b_{\tau_{\mathfrak{D}-3}}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + b_{\tau_{\mathfrak{D}-3}}^{\mathfrak{D}} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}}, \right. \\ \quad \left. b_{\tau_{\mathfrak{D}-4}}^{\mathfrak{D}-2} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + b_{\tau_{\mathfrak{D}-4}}^{\mathfrak{D}-1} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + b_{\tau_{\mathfrak{D}-4}}^{\mathfrak{D}} \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}} \right). \end{cases}$$

Proposition 8.2. When (M, g) satisfies the symmetry conditions of Definition 8.3 , denote

$$\begin{aligned} d'_{1L} &\triangleq \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \\ d'_{2L} &\triangleq \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \\ d'_{3L} &\triangleq \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}} c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
u'_{1L} &\triangleq \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-3}(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-4}(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-3}(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-4}(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \\
u'_{2L} &\triangleq \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-3}(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-4}(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-3}(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-4}(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \\
u'_{3L} &\triangleq \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-3}(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-4}(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-3}(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-4}(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}).
\end{aligned}$$

Then the intrinsic geometrical properties d_1, d_2, d_3, u_1, u_2 and u_3 of f satisfy the following conclusions on (M, g) .

$$\begin{aligned}
d_{1L;P} &= \partial_P d_{1L} - g_s d_{1L} U_P^1 + g_s d_{2L} V_P^1 - g_s d_{3L} V_P^1 \\
&\quad - g_s u_{1L} X_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} X_P^{31} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} Y_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} X_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} Y_P^{12} - g u'_{1L} W_P^1 \\
d_{2L;P} &= \partial_P d_{2L} - g_s d_{2L} U_P^2 + g_s d_{3L} V_P^2 - g_s d_{1L} V_P^2 \\
&\quad - g_s u_{2L} X_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} X_P^{12} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} Y_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} X_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} Y_P^{23} - g u'_{2L} W_P^1 \\
d_{3L;P} &= \partial_P d_{3L} - g_s d_{3L} U_P^3 + g_s d_{1L} V_P^3 - g_s d_{2L} V_P^3 \\
&\quad - g_s u_{3L} X_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} X_P^{23} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} Y_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} X_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} Y_P^{31} - g u'_{3L} W_P^1 \\
d_{1R;P} &= \partial_P d_{1R} - g_s d_{1L} V_P^1 + g_s d_{2L} U_P^1 - g_s d_{3L} U_P^1 \\
&\quad + g_s u_{1L} Y_P^{23} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} X_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} Y_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} X_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} Y_P^{12} \\
d_{2R;P} &= \partial_P d_{2R} - g_s d_{2L} V_P^2 + g_s d_{3L} U_P^2 - g_s d_{1L} U_P^2 \\
&\quad + g_s u_{2L} Y_P^{31} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} X_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} Y_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} X_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} Y_P^{23} \\
d_{3R;P} &= \partial_P d_{3R} - g_s d_{3L} V_P^3 + g_s d_{1L} U_P^3 - g_s d_{2L} U_P^3 \\
&\quad + g_s u_{3L} Y_P^{12} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} X_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} Y_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} X_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} Y_P^{31} \\
u_{1L;P} &= \partial_P u_{1L} - g_s u_{1L} U_P^1 - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} X_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} Y_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} X_P^{31} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} Y_P^{31} \\
&\quad - g_s d_{1L} X_P^{23} + g_s d_{2L} Y_P^{23} - g_s d_{3L} Y_P^{23} - g d'_{1L} W_P^1 \\
u_{2L;P} &= \partial_P u_{2L} - g_s u_{2L} U_P^2 - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} X_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} Y_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} X_P^{12} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} Y_P^{12} \\
&\quad - g_s d_{2L} X_P^{31} + g_s d_{3L} Y_P^{31} - g_s d_{1L} Y_P^{31} - g d'_{2L} W_P^1 \\
u_{3L;P} &= \partial_P u_{3L} - g_s u_{3L} U_P^3 - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} X_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} Y_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} X_P^{23} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} Y_P^{23} \\
&\quad - g_s d_{3L} X_P^{12} + g_s d_{1L} Y_P^{12} - g_s d_{2L} Y_P^{12} - g d'_{3L} W_P^1 \\
u_{1R;P} &= \partial_P u_{1R} - g_s u_{1R} U_P^1 + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2R} X_P^{12} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2R} Y_P^{12} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3R} X_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3R} Y_P^{31} \\
u_{2R;P} &= \partial_P u_{2R} - g_s u_{2R} U_P^2 + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3R} X_P^{23} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3R} Y_P^{23} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1R} X_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1R} Y_P^{12} \\
u_{3R;P} &= \partial_P u_{3R} - g_s u_{3R} U_P^3 + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1R} X_P^{31} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1R} Y_P^{31} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2R} X_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2R} Y_P^{23}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Substitute Definition 8.2 into ρ_{mn} and consider Definition 8.3, then by calculation we finally obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
d_{1L;P} &= \partial_P d_{1L} - g_s d_{1L} U_P^1 + g_s d_{2L} V_P^1 - g_s d_{3L} V_P^1 \\
&\quad - g_s u_{1L} X_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} X_P^{31} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} Y_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} X_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} Y_P^{12} \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 \\
d_{2L;P} &= \partial_P d_{2L} - g_s d_{2L} U_P^2 + g_s d_{3L} V_P^2 - g_s d_{1L} V_P^2 \\
&\quad - g_s u_{2L} X_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} X_P^{12} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} Y_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} X_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} Y_P^{23} \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 \\
d_{3L;P} &= \partial_P d_{3L} - g_s d_{3L} U_P^3 + g_s d_{1L} V_P^3 - g_s d_{2L} V_P^3 \\
&\quad - g_s u_{3L} X_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} X_P^{23} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} Y_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} X_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} Y_P^{31} \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 \\
d_{1R;P} &= \partial_P d_{1R} - g_s d_{1L} V_P^1 + g_s d_{2L} U_P^1 - g_s d_{3L} U_P^1 \\
&\quad + g_s u_{1L} Y_P^{23} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} X_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} Y_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} X_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} Y_P^{12} \\
d_{2R;P} &= \partial_P d_{2R} - g_s d_{2L} V_P^2 + g_s d_{3L} U_P^2 - g_s d_{1L} U_P^2 \\
&\quad + g_s u_{2L} Y_P^{31} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} X_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} Y_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} X_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} Y_P^{23} \\
d_{3R;P} &= \partial_P d_{3R} - g_s d_{3L} V_P^3 + g_s d_{1L} U_P^3 - g_s d_{2L} U_P^3 \\
&\quad + g_s u_{3L} Y_P^{12} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} X_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} Y_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} X_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} Y_P^{31} \\
u_{1L;P} &= \partial_P u_{1L} - g_s u_{1L} U_P^1 - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} X_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} Y_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} X_P^{31} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} Y_P^{31} \\
&\quad - g_s d_{1L} X_P^{23} + g_s d_{2L} Y_P^{23} - g_s d_{3L} Y_P^{23} \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 \\
u_{2L;P} &= \partial_P u_{2L} - g_s u_{2L} U_P^2 - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} X_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3L} Y_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} X_P^{12} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} Y_P^{12} \\
&\quad - g_s d_{2L} X_P^{31} + g_s d_{3L} Y_P^{31} - g_s d_{1L} Y_P^{31} \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-3} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 - \frac{1}{2} c_{\mathfrak{D}-1}^{\mathfrak{D}-4} (\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)}) \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} W_P^1 \\
u_{3L;P} &= \partial_P u_{3L} - g_s u_{3L} U_P^3 - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} X_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1L} Y_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} X_P^{23} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2L} Y_P^{23} \\
&\quad - g_s d_{3L} X_P^{12} + g_s d_{1L} Y_P^{12} - g_s d_{2L} Y_P^{12}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\frac{1}{2}c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-3}(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-4)})\frac{g}{\sqrt{2}}W_P^1 - \frac{1}{2}c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-3}(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-4)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-4)})\frac{g}{\sqrt{2}}W_P^1 \\
& -\frac{1}{2}c_{\mathfrak{D}-2}^{\mathfrak{D}-4}(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)\mathfrak{D}} + \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-3)})\frac{g}{\sqrt{2}}W_P^1 - \frac{1}{2}c_{\mathfrak{D}}^{\mathfrak{D}-4}(\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-3)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} + \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-3)})\frac{g}{\sqrt{2}}W_P^1 \\
u_{1R;P} &= \partial_P u_{1R} - g_s u_{1R} U_P^1 + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2R} X_P^{12} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2R} Y_P^{12} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3R} X_P^{31} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3R} Y_P^{31} \\
u_{2R;P} &= \partial_P u_{2R} - g_s u_{2R} U_P^2 + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3R} X_P^{23} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{3R} Y_P^{23} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1R} X_P^{12} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1R} Y_P^{12} \\
u_{3R;P} &= \partial_P u_{3R} - g_s u_{3R} U_P^3 + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1R} X_P^{31} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{1R} Y_P^{31} + \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2R} X_P^{23} - \frac{g_s}{2} u_{2R} Y_P^{23}.
\end{aligned}$$

Then we just need to substitute the definitions of d'_{1L} , d'_{2L} , d'_{3L} , u'_{1L} , u'_{2L} , u'_{3L} into the above equations. \square

Remark 8.2. The above proposition gives the mathematical essence of CKM mixing of strong interaction from the perspective of intrinsic geometry. In mathematics, d'_{1L} , d'_{2L} , d'_{3L} , u'_{1L} , u'_{2L} , u'_{3L} automatically appear as intrinsic geometrical properties, which are thereby not necessary to be postulated artificially like that in physics.

Definition 8.4. If reference-system f satisfies $\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} = \rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)\mathfrak{D}} = \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-1)} = \rho_{\mathfrak{D}(\mathfrak{D}-2)} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)\mathfrak{D}} = 0$, we say f is a **lepton field**, otherwise f is a **hadron field**. Suppose f is a hadron field. For d_1 , d_2 , d_3 , u_1 , u_2 , u_3 , if f satisfies that five of them are zero and the other one is non-zero, we say f is a **single quark**.

Proposition 8.3. There does not exist a single quark. In other words, if five of d_1 , d_2 , d_3 , u_1 , u_2 , u_3 are zero, then $d_1 = d_2 = d_3 = u_1 = u_2 = u_3 = 0$.

Remark 8.3. For a single down-type quark, the above proposition is evident. Without loss of generality let $u_1 = u_2 = u_3 = 0$ and $d_1 = d_2 = 0$, thus $\rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-2)(\mathfrak{D}-2)} = \rho_{(\mathfrak{D}-1)(\mathfrak{D}-1)} = \rho_{\mathfrak{D}\mathfrak{D}} = 0$, hence we must have $d_3 = 0$.

For a single up-type quark, this paper has not made progress on the proof yet. Anyway, in consideration of that in physics the color confinement has no clear mathematical connotation, by contrast, Proposition 8.3 explicitly gives the mathematical connotation of color confinement from the perspective of intrinsic geometry. This proposition itself is very significant.

9 Summary

1. The fundamental theory of intrinsic geometry.

(1) Riemannian manifold is generalized to geometrical manifold.

(2) The expression form of Erlangen program is improved. The concept of intrinsic geometry is generalized, so that the Riemannian intrinsic geometry based on the first fundamental form becomes a subgeometry of the generalized intrinsic geometry, and thereby Riemannian geometry can be incorporated into the geometrical framework of improved Erlangen program.

(3) The concept of simple connection is discovered, which reflects more intrinsic properties of manifold than Levi-Civita connection.

2. The application of intrinsic geometry to Hilbert's 6th problem.

(1) This paper applies the generalized intrinsic geometry to Hilbert's 6th problem at the most basic level, so that the kernel concepts, conclusions, postulates and equations of fundamental physics can be strictly defined, constructed and proved in pure mathematical sense.

(2) Gravitational field and gauge field have been unified essentially via the concepts of reference-system and simple connection. Intrinsic geometry of external space describes gravitational field, and intrinsic geometry of internal space describes typical gauge field. They have been unified into intrinsic geometry.

(3) The points of view of section 3.4 make gravitational theory and quantum mechanics have the same view of time and space and unified description of evolution, so we say they are unified into intrinsic geometry.

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